

**The Potential Implications of Arabic Diglossia on the Pedagogy of
Simultaneous Interpreting in Algeria**

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Thesis submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements
of the University of the West of Scotland
for the award of Doctor of Philosophy

Declaration

I hereby declare that this thesis is the result of my own work except for citations and quotations, which have been explicitly acknowledged in the text, and that this work has not been conferred for award of other degree at the University of the West of Scotland or any other institution.

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Abstract

The Algerian society is considered to be diglossic due the prevalence of two linguistic forms: Standard Arabic (the High variety) and Dialectal Arabic (the Low variety) although diglossia as a concept is itself under debate with literature suggesting that many countries have a triglossic or even a multiglossic language. The proposed study investigates the potential impact of Arabic diglossia on the participants' perceptions of SI. All of my participants had been SI students. It further sets out to explore the challenges that Algerian students of simultaneous interpreting in one of the Algerian universities go through in relation to diglossia during their interpreting practice. This dissertation addresses the question of how learners can fulfil the interpreting tasks that require a full mastery of the formal style (Modern Standard Arabic), without being influenced by the low language (Dialectal Arabic), the language variety that is used in daily life interactions. The study further explores to what extent course designers of simultaneous interpreting take into consideration the concept of Diglossia. These research questions were answered through the lens of a mixed research methodology that included questionnaires and individual interviews. One of the key findings is that MSA was a significant challenge according to the participants' perceptions, whereas it has been perceived that the foreign language was also a problem. Furthermore, the findings highlight that it was very challenging for the students to interpret from and into MSA and English as the participants claimed that they encountered linguistic difficulties in both languages. Despite the vast studies that were conducted on diglossia in teaching and learning contexts in the last decade, investigating the impact that diglossia may have on the teaching and learning of simultaneous interpreting is rarely tackled especially in Algeria, and this is a gap in literature. The findings of this study have importance because they inform the pedagogy of SI through an exploration of the SI students' perceptions when interpreting from and into a diglossic language. Hence, it is anticipated that the expected outcomes will contribute to raise Algerian teachers and learners' awareness of the various effects that Arabic diglossia may have on simultaneous interpreting.

Keywords: *diglossia, Arabic diglossia, simultaneous interpreting, teaching methods, Modern Standard Arabic, dialectal Arabic, multilingualism, high variety, low variety, language policy, Arabization.*

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List of Abbreviations

AIIC	International Association of Conference Interpreters
CA	Classical Arabic
DA	Dialectal Arabic
ESA	Educated Spoken Arabic
L1	First Language
MSA	Modern Standard Arabic
SI	Simultaneous Interpreting
SL	Source Language
TL	Target Language

Chapter 1: Introductory Chapter

1.1. Introduction

This study aims to investigate the potential implications of Arabic diglossia on my participants' perceptions of the pedagogy of simultaneous interpreting studies at university level in Algeria, in order to explore the difficulties that students of SI may experience when interpreting simultaneously from a non-L1 to a non-L1, that is to say MSA-English-MSA. Moreover, this research explores SI students' perceptions of MSA use in SI classes and the difficulties resulting from using a form of language, that the students are not exposed to in daily life interactions, in a task as complex as SI. Moreover, this study explores to what extent are postgraduate learners of SI aware of Arabic diglossia.

Overall, in this study, quantitative methodology is used as a complementary method, as the emphasis is on the qualitative methodology. Consequently, an interpretivist research approach is adopted for this study since this research aims to gather descriptive data, in this case the perceptions of Algerian students of SI on the impact of Arabic diglossia on the pedagogy of SI through mixed methods. A mixed methods approach was chosen for this research, as explained further in section 4.7 in the methodology chapter, since the study focuses on exploring how Arabic diglossia affects the participants' perceptions of the pedagogy of SI in Algeria, which entails the need for in-depth data. The questionnaires enabled me to frame my interview questions.

This research project adopts mixed methods for data collection in order to increase the validity of the findings. By using mixed methods the researcher benefits from the strengths of both qualitative and quantitative methods and therefore the weaknesses of the two are minimised (Denscombe, 2014).

1.2. Issues Addressed

According to my experience as a student of SI in Algeria during my MA degree speciality of translation and translation studies, where SI was taught as a module in the second year along with other types of interpreting and translation (consecutive interpreting, sight translation), I figured out that students, including myself, were facing difficulties when interpreting from and into Arabic/English. By Arabic, I mean MSA since it is the only form used in formal education. Among the hardships and constraints we were facing, was our lack of competence in MSA that tends to increase when interpreting in comparison to translating due to time factors and high

requirements embedded in the process of interpreting. On the other hand, teachers were assuming that students are fully competent in the Arabic language (MSA) since they studied it for at least twelve years before reaching the higher education level without taking into consideration the fact that Arabic is a diglossic language. It is to be noted that MA degree in English literature in Algeria consists of two years whereas bachelor's degree is for three years following the LMD system (license, master and doctorate). Therefore, the lack of competence in MSA among Algerian students, despite the fact that they studied MSA for a minimum of twelve years, makes interpreting simultaneously from and into non-L1 languages (MSA and English) even more challenging. Moreover, it is assumed that students already master MSA since they use Arabic for daily life communications without taking into consideration that the form of Arabic used in daily life is the 'Low' variety and not the 'High' variety required in formal education. As a result to this assumption, students are not required to pass a language test to assess their command of MSA, in other words, they get accepted at university to study translation and interpreting based on other criteria such as the overall score that the university demands but not an MSA language test. In this light, Napier, Rohan and Slatyer (2005) write "professional education programmes for interpreters expect a minimum level of bilingual proficiency for acceptance onto the course (whether this is formally assessed or not)" (p.192). Similarly for teachers, they often assume that being a citizen of an Arabic speaking country, and have studied MSA for at least twelve years, as in Algeria, through formal education, the student is competent in the Arabic language with its two forms H and L. In this light, Masoud (1988) asserts "more often than not, new translators dive into translation work thinking that because they speak two languages, they are qualified for the task" (as cited in Deeb, 2005, pp.1-2). This research hypothesizes that diglossia has an impact on the educational system in the Arabic speaking countries, precisely the pedagogy of SI in Algeria.

Consequently, all these factors contributed to the interest of conducting the current study that aims to investigate to what extent students of SI are aware of Arabic diglossia and therefore suggest recommendations that may help the pedagogy of SI in Algeria and raise awareness of the impact of this linguistic phenomenon on the methods of teaching and learning SI.

1.3. The Rationale of the Study

Many previously conducted studies revealed that Arabic diglossia has a negative impact on the educational system in the Arabic speaking countries (among many others, Abdulaziz, 1986;

Maamouri, 1998; Haeri, 2000; Cote, 2009; Ibrahim, 2009; Dendane, 2015) and also on teaching Arabic as a foreign language, as reviewed in the relevant literature.

Moreover, after reviewing the existing literature, it is evident that very little research was undertaken to tackle the implications of translating and interpreting from and into two non-L1 languages. Furthermore, this issue is not tackled in classroom contexts when teaching translation and interpreting, SI precisely, from a non-L1 to a non-L1 where one of the working languages is considered to be diglossic.

1.4. Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to explore a phenomenon in order to identify the cause and effect relationship; in other words, how does Arabic diglossia affect my participants' perceptions of the pedagogy of SI in Algeria. It is neither undertaken to compare between two phenomena nor to find solutions to scientific or non-scientific problems. As Kothari (2004, p.2) explains, research objectives fall into four broad categories defining the type of research that are explained as follows:

- 1) Exploratory or formulative studies aiming at discovering new facts.
- 2) Descriptive studies aiming at identifying the features of an individual, social phenomena or a particular situation.
- 3) Diagnostic studies with the purpose of identifying "the frequency with which something occurs or with which it is associated with something else"
- 4) Hypothesis-testing studies with the objective of testing hypotheses.

Furthermore, Kothari (2004, pp. 2-4) outlines the basic types of research, which will be explained below.

Descriptive vs. Analytical research: while descriptive research aims at describing the present state of a phenomenon with the researcher acting as a describer of what has happened or what is happening in the present, whereas in analytical research the researcher relies on existing information and facts in order to analyse them and provide an evaluation.

Applied vs. Fundamental research: applied or action research is concerned with discovering a solution for a practical problem whereas fundamental or basic research aims to find information that has a broad base of applications.

Quantitative vs. Qualitative: quantitative method is used to collect and analyse numerical data in phenomena that can be studied in terms of quantity. Qualitative research involves collecting

and analysing non-numerical data in order to gather attitudes, opinions and in-depth insights into the topic under investigation.

Conceptual vs Empirical: conceptual research focuses on abstract ideas or theory whereas empirical or experimental research aims at gathering knowledge through observation or experiment.

1.5. Outline of the Thesis

The present thesis consists of six chapters and is structured as follows:

The first chapter provides a broad background for the topic of the study and discusses the language-planning situation in Algeria and its impact on the educational system.

Chapter two puts the context of the language planning in Algeria

Chapter three reviews the literature in order to generate knowledge of the studies that have been undertaken in this field of research and therefore enables the researcher to identify the research gap.

Chapter four introduces the research design and methods used in this study that aim to answer the research questions and it also discusses limitations and ethics around this study

In chapter five, data analysis and findings resulting from the online survey and the online semi-structured interviews are analysed and discussed. One of the key findings from the survey was that MSA was a significant challenge according to the participants, whereas it has been perceived that the second language was also a problem, which was unexpected. Furthermore, the interview data revealed that it was very challenging for the students to interpret from and into MSA and English as the participants claimed that they encountered linguistic difficulties in both languages, which was also unexpected.

Chapter six presents answers to the research questions along with a discussion of the limitations of the study, recommendations, autobiographical reflections and areas for future research.

Chapter 2: Contextual Background

2.1. Introduction

In order to better understand the linguistic situation in Algeria and its impact on the educational system in Algeria, a brief overview of the country will be provided. The first section will tackle the geographical location of the country and its relationship with the neighbouring countries with which it has a common linguistic history. The second section will discuss the Algerian educational system starting with primary education: kindergarten, middle school and secondary school as well as higher education. The third section will provide a historical overview of Algeria and how it affected the language-planning situation, including the policies that the country undertook which will be reviewed chronologically including the three eras: pre-colonial, colonial and post-colonial.

2.2. The Maghreb: Definition, Geography, Ethnography and Languages

In this section, a brief historical and geographical background of the Maghreb will be reviewed in order to demonstrate how the language situation developed and is still evolving with special reference to Algeria, as it is the focus of the proposed study.

Maghreb is an Arabic term literally meaning the “West”. It refers to the western part of the Arabic Speaking World (Roberts, and Roberts, 2003; Aitsiselmi and Marley, 2008) and it is also known as, the Greater Maghreb: this area is situated in the farthest area of northwest Africa bordered by the Mediterranean Sea from the North and the Atlantic Ocean from the West. Maghreb countries have a common linguistic history (Garcia, 2009) and they consist of Algeria, Libya, Mauritania, Morocco, Tunisia and Western Sahara (Roberts, and Roberts, 2003, p.xxiii).

In 1989, a union called the “*Union du Maghreb Arabe*” (Arab Maghreb Union) was established involving five countries, known as “*Le Grand Maghreb*” (the Great Maghreb), which are Morocco, Algeria, Tunisia, Libya and Mauritania (Aitsiselmi and Marley, 2008, p.186).

By the mid nineteenth century, parts of the Arabic speaking world were colonized by France, Britain and Italy. The latter justifies later the integration of the colonizers’ languages as foreign languages into the schooling system of the concerned Arab regions (Garcia, 2009). According to Loomba (2007), colonialism is defined as “the conquest and control of other people’s land and goods” (p.2). France colonized Algeria, Tunisia, and

Morocco by the end of the nineteenth century, in Algeria, during the French colonization era, Arabic was banned and French was the official language (Al-Khatib, 2008).

After these Arabic speaking countries gained their independence, they reacted by removing the ex-colonizer traces, and to retain their identities, the Arabization movement took place, as will be explained further in section (2.4.3.1), as a reaction to Western imperialism (Garcia, 2009). In the case of the Maghreb (Algeria, Morocco, and Tunisia) Arabic was the only official language by that time with French used in limited contexts (Garcia, 2009).

2.3. The Context of Language in Algeria

Algeria's historical background shaped its language repertoire; Algeria is a multilingual society as various languages coexist, each with a definite role as will be explained below.

Djennane (2016) identifies three languages that are used side by side in Algeria currently, each with its defining role, which are as follows:

1. Berber: the language of the natives of the Maghreb, which after a long struggle enjoys currently the status of joint-official language.
2. Arabic, incorporating its two forms literary and vernacular, emerged from the Arab invasion to North Africa in the 7th century and is considered as the country's official language after its independence.
3. French: which is a language of the colonial legacy that is regarded as a prestigious and powerful language that politically occupies the role of a "foreign language but it has, on linguistic grounds, the stand of a second language" (Djennane, 2016, p.66).

To these languages, Aitsiselmi and Marley (2008) add the English language, which is currently associated with modern technology and the use of English is increasingly wide spreading especially among young Algerians. Furthermore, European empires colonized various parts of the Arabic speaking countries, and as a result, these European languages, precisely English and French, became foreign languages in these countries and therefore included in their educational system (Al-Khatib, 2006).

The decision over whether to consider Standard Arabic and spoken Arabic vernaculars as two varieties of the same language, or to consider them as two separate languages is debatable due to the huge gap that exists between the two varieties (Ibrahim, 1989). In this respect Ma'mouri

et al. (1983), as cited in Ibrahim (1989, p. 39), tackled this issue and claimed that the two linguistic varieties are considered as two separate languages rather than two varieties belonging to the same language. The association of religion with language is manifested in the Arabic language and Islam. Thus, the Arabic language gained its power from religion and the initiation of written forms of language had a key role in preserving Quran, the religious book, from corruption (Ibrahim, 1989).

Written Arabic is acquired through formal education as Ibrahim (1986, p.118) notes: “unlike L, H is not acquired natively by any individual. The acquisition (more accurately, the learning) of H is a function of formal instruction and education. But there are millions of individuals who never learn H because they have not had any education”. ‘L’ refers to the low variety of language or the dialectal variety whereas ‘H’ refers to the high variety, which is the standard form.

Similarly, Ibrahim (1989); Kaye (1994); Ibrahim (2011) emphasise that MSA is not acquired, rather it is learnt through formal education as opposite to colloquial Arabic, which is acquired with no formal teaching. The latter is the mean of communication in informal settings: with friends and family, on radio and in TV whereas no Arabic speaker uses MSA for the purposes listed above, the majority speaks colloquial Arabic in daily interactions while some might use French and/or English as well (Kaye, 1994). An explanation of the huge gap that exists between the spoken and the written forms of Arabic is well explained in Ibrahim’s (1989) argument, which he made three decades ago.

Ibrahim (1989) argues that education in the Arabic speaking countries occurs exclusively in the written form of Arabic, that is to say, MSA. This statement is debateable as it is valid in primary and secondary education but not in higher education where a number of specialties are taught in French or English.

From the above discussion, a question arises concerning what status does MSA have and whether it is considered as a regular second language, if it is the case, from a cognitive perspective, are Arabic speaking children exposed to both forms similar to bilinguals in other languages? In an attempt to answer this question, Ibrahim and Aharon-Peretz (2005) conducted a study in which they investigated how daily use of MSA and spoken Arabic may influence the lexical organization of the two in the cognitive linguistic system of adults whose L1 is a spoken variety. The findings of their study revealed the following “despite the intensive daily use adult

native Arabic speakers make of SA and LA, and despite their shared origin, the two languages retain their status as first and second languages in the cognitive system” (Ibrahim and Aharon-Peretz, 2005, p.51). This argument is discussed further by referring to the participants’ perceptions in section 5.2.3 of the findings’ chapter.

2.4. The History of Algeria

The following section provides an overview on the Algerian history, focusing mainly on the French conquest as it is the most recent and because it left a significant impact on Algeria’s present. The first part describes Algeria’s population and the sociolinguistic status before the French conquest whereas the second part tackles the period of French colonisation from 1830 onwards. The focus will be on the educational system and the linguistic situation in Algeria since they are the focus of this study.

Benrabah (2007) identifies three stages that contributed to shaping the language situation in Algeria, which are as follows:

The first stage involves the dominance of the French language in the educational system along with the Arabic language progression as a result of the French occupation heritage.

The second stage is the “nationalist transition” which lasted for around thirty years from the 1960s to the 1990s and was characterised by reforming the educational system through introducing progressively the Arabic language in schools. This phase later resulted in Algeria’s civil war.

The third stage took place in the 2000s and was marked by the realization that monolingual education, Arabic in Algeria, is unsuccessful.

2.4.1. Pre- French Colonial Period

Berbers inhabited Northern Africa, from the Atlantic to the Egyptian borders and are the indigenous people of that geographical area (Benrabah, 2005). Benrabah (2013) claims that a number of invaders attempted to conquer Algeria due to the fact that Berbers were lacking leadership competence. The invaders include Phoenicians, the Romans, the Vandals and the Romanized Byzantines, the Islamo-Arabo-Berbers, the Turks and the French. Consequently, all these invasions affected Algeria’s history and language situation, which resulted in multilingualism “Berber-Punic, Berber-Punic-Latin, Berber-Arabic, Berber-Arabic-Spanish-Turkish, Berber-Arabic-French and so on” (Benrabah, 2013, p.23).

In the seventh century, the Arab-Islamic invasion introduced Classical Arabic to Algeria along with the spread of Islam that most Berbers were converted to. The language spread easily because of its connection to religion and because it is widely believed that in order to pray, one should employ Arabic (Belmihoub, 2012).

In terms of the linguistic situation of the French pre-colonial period, the languages spoken at that time were Berber and Arabic, as Benrabah (2013) states “the Berber-speaking community represented over 50% of Algeria’s population, and literacy in Arabic was estimated at 40-50%” (p.24).

In this respect, Benrabah (2013, p.23) describes Algeria’s sociolinguistic situation at the period of the Ottoman occupation, which lasted for around three centuries, as a “mosaic of ethnic group and languages” since controlling the population would become easier when it is divided. Furthermore, Benrabah (2013) claims that:

The sociolinguistic structure in cities and towns was as complex and varied as the population: multilingualism prevailed and involved approximately 15 languages. Turks used the official language, Osmanli Turkish. Dialectal or colloquial Arabic remained important: not only was it spoken by the old towns people and Andalusian immigrants (Moors) who had left Spain after its *Reconquista*, but also it was the only tongue understood by tribesman in the surrounding country where Berber dominated (p.23).

Prior to the French conquest, the schooling system in Algeria concentrated mainly on reading, writing, arithmetic and Muslim law beginning from the age of fifteen in secondary schools (Le Roux, 2017).

2.4.2. The French Occupation

Algeria was under the French colonization for a century and thirty-two years (Benrabah, 2005), which contributed largely to the complexity and sensitivity of the language situation in Algeria after independence (Le Roux, 2017). Benrabah (2005, p.380) uses “quite complex” as a description to refer to the Algerian language situation. Berger (2002) considers the linguistic issue as “the most severe problem of Algeria in its present and troubled state” as cited in (Benrabah, 2005, p.379). This occupation affected not only the linguistic situation but also the cultural identity (Aitselmi and Marley, 2008). Therefore, in comparison with Morocco and Tunisia, Algeria was most resilient to recuperate language and identity after independence

(Benrabah, 2005). The aim of the following section is to discuss the linguistic consequences of this conquest that contributed directly to shaping the current language situation in Algeria.

In the period of the French occupation, from 1830 to 1962, the French language symbolised power and prestige consequently it was exclusive to the elite in the Algerian society (Aitsiselmi and Marley, 2008). Le Roux (2017, p.114) asserts that “the assimilation of Algerians into French culture was most clearly demonstrated in and through education”; Ladjal and Bensaid (2012) agree that France targeted education in Algeria believing that it is “the only key for political stability and the extinction of revolutions” (p.5). Therefore, the educational system in Algeria was affected by the French conquest. In 1830, French language was introduced at schools with the intention to eliminate the languages that existed at that time, which were Berber and Algerian Arabic (Belmihoub, 2012). Consequently, French replaced Arabic and had the position of the country’s official language (Turin, 1983 as cited in Le Roux, 2017, p.114). Spoken Algerian Arabic and Tamazight had no official status (Le Roux, 2017) whereas Classical Arabic was the language of academics employed in traditional and religious schools (Mostari, 2005). It is to be noted that the Tamazight language refers to the language of Berbers, the natives of the Maghreb (Aitsiselmi and Marley, 2008), also refers to as Berber language.

Not only Arabs and Berbers’ languages were ousted but also their culture and value system (Le Roux, 2017). Algeria’s educational system witnessed several reformulations during the French conquest; the latter attempted to integrate Algeria into France as stated earlier through education, thus several projects took place under what is known as “assimilation policy” (Le Roux, 2017). The French educational system was adopted in Algeria by the French invasion but it was customised to suit the Algerian community (Le Roux, 2017).

Assimilation policy, as the name denotes, refers to the complete integration of the Algerian community into the French culture through education with no intention to improve the schooling system in Algeria but “to extinguish the remnants of their resistance through *French education*” (Ladjal and Bensaid, 2012, p.5). This integration involved not only the French culture but also the French mindset, language and lifestyle; not only Algerians rejected this policy but also the French settlers who were against any educational reforms of Algerian natives (Ladjal and Bensaid, 2012). French authorities used religion as a weapon to oppress Algerians because they were aware of the power of this weapon; as a result, they requested verdicts from the most reliable mosques in the Muslim countries to convince Algerians that leaving their country was illegitimate (Ladjal and Bensaid, 2012). In this light, Ladjal and

Bensaid (2012) argue “the perception of the Catholic Church was, somewhat different from others with regards to assimilation; as it associated assimilation with its missionary mandate of proselytisation, instead of simply acculturating Algerians according to the French style” (p.7).

2.4.3. Post-French Colonial Period

After 1962, when Algeria got its independence, 90% of the population was illiterate with a Francophone Muslim minority. As a result, and with a reaction towards eliminating the French language and substituting it with Arabic, Algeria requested teachers from Egypt to come to Algeria and teach Arabic. This policy is known as “Arabization Policy” as will be discussed below. The Egyptian president Gamal Abdel Nasser responded to Algeria’s request by explaining that there were no qualified teachers sufficient to fulfil this task, the Algerian president Ben Bella emphasized the need of teachers “even if they were greengrocers” (Grandguillaume, 2004) as cited in Benrabah (2013, p.56). Consequently, this resulted in incompetent teachers teaching the Arabic language with a spoken Arabic incomprehensible to Algerians (Benrabah, 2014). Consequently, by mid to the late 1970s, Algerians who received education in Arabic struggled to find jobs as the main state corporations favoured employers who were fluent and literate in European languages (Roberts and Roberts, 2003).

2.4.3.1. Arabization Policy

Various parts of the Arabic speaking region undertook the policy of Arabization with the increase of Arab nationalism (Garcia 2009). Arabization can be defined as a policy that aimed to flourish the Arabic language and to spread its use in various sectors and in parallel attempts to eliminate the ex-colonizer languages (Aitsiselmi and Marley, 2008; Djennane, 2016). This policy was introduced in Algeria after its independence in 1962 (Le Roux, 2017).

In Algeria, and after the country got its independence, the declaration of Arabic as the country’s official and national language was associated with the declaration of Islam as the state’s religion (Djennane, 2016).

Moreover, Roberts and Roberts (2003) state that Arabisation policy aimed at asserting MSA, the lingua franca of the Mashriq (*the east*), as the national language of Algeria neglecting the existing spoken languages (French, colloquial Arabic and Berber) claiming that none of them could be used in the pedagogical system. This policy took place in Algeria in the early 1960s (Garcia, 2009) and it started with the educational system to impact later sectors of the state administrations (Roberts and Roberts, 2003). In this respect, “the imposition of an exclusively

Arabic monolingual schooling system implemented during the second or nationalist transition phase is considered to be a major source of the current failure in education” (Le Roux, 2017, p.113). As a result, in the late 20th century, job opportunities were very hard to obtain for a large proportion of Arabized public school graduates (Benrabah, 2007). Despite the efforts made to Arabize the country, the French language continues to have an important role in the ex-French colonies, namely in Algeria (Aitsiselmi and Marley, 2008). Aitsiselmi and Marley (2008, p.187) justify this phenomenon by asserting that “the proximity of the Maghreb to Metropolitan France, the extremely high numbers of Maghrebians living in France, and the volume of trade and business between France and the countries of the Maghreb all contribute to the continued impact of the French language and culture on the Maghreb”.

However, conflicts over language and identity continued to emerge by the 1990s defending the rights of the other native Algerian linguistic varieties such as Berber and Algerian colloquial Arabic that were overlooked during the French occupation. As a solution, Benrabah suggested integrating Algerian Arabic vernaculars and Berber in the schooling system primarily for young children (Benrabah, 2007).

The conflict in post-independent Algeria over language, particularly in the educational sector, is ongoing and the language planning situation is controversial.

At first, and before the 2000s, the linguistic conflict was mainly over maintaining monolingual education, Arabic, or the application of bilingual education, Arabic/French. Supporters of Arabisation defended the first argument whereas the second one was upheld by francophones (Benrabah, 2007).

In this respect, Benrabah (2007) notes:

Transition towards a market economy and the demands of internationalism have led the authorities to commit the educational sector to new reforms that would re-establish Arabic–French bilingualism and the pre-eminence of French as the tool for the teaching of science and technology. Indeed, since September 2003, French has been introduced as the first mandatory foreign language in Grade Two (6–7 year olds) of the primary cycle and English in the first grade of Middle Schools.⁵⁵ Despite the recommendations made by the National Commission for the Reform of the Educational System in mid-March 2001, French has not been re-introduced as the medium for teaching scientific disciplines in secondary education (p.199).

On the other hand, the Tamazight language was allowed in the educational system in 2003 (Garcia, 2009). Now in Algeria, Arabic is the language of instruction except when teaching foreign languages (Garcia, 2009).

In 1963, an Algerian writer envisaged how language status would be in the post-independent Algeria by arguing: “in ten to fifteen years..., Arabic will have replaced French completely and English will be on its way to replacing French as a second language. French is a clear and beautiful language, ...but it holds too many bitter memories for us” (Benrabah, 2007, pp.193-4). Furthermore, Kateb Yacine, an Algerian writer, states “I write in French to tell the French that I am not French; the French language is our spoil of war” as cited in (Belmihoub, 2012, p.4).

Form the previous quotations, it is clear that Algerians’ attitudes towards the French language are complex, due to its connection with the French colonisation that symbolises a tough period to the Algerian people (Benrabah, 2007). This contributed to enhancing the substitution of French by Arabic as an act of removing colonisation traces which is known as “Arabization” policy (Benrabah, 2007, p.194).

In this respect, Benrabah (2007) reviews the status of Arabic, French and English in Algeria after independence along with their roles and integrations in the educational system. In the end of 1970’s to the early 1990’s, both French and English languages were considered as foreign languages introduced in the educational system. On the one hand, French was a compulsory first foreign language taught in primary schools that at that time consisted of six grades. In the fourth grade, pupils had to learn French as a foreign language. On the other hand, the English language occupied the role of the second foreign language taught in the eighth grade of middle school. In 1992, the Algerian educational system witnessed some changes: French was no more imposed on pupils of primary school, accordingly they had the opportunity to decide which foreign language to learn first either French or English in grade four (Garcia, 2009). From that time and until 1997, this policy was unsuccessful and French returned to be the first mandatory foreign language in primary schools (Benrabah, 2007). Moreover, Arabization policy that aimed to arabize the schooling system and to exclude French, was unsuccessful as well and “Algeria is the second largest French-speaking community in the world” (Benrabah, 2007, p.194).

Benrabah (2007) adds:

In the educational sector, a shift to Literary Arabic as the language of instruction has occurred since 1962 mainly at primary and secondary levels. But in universities French is still the key language for studies in scientific disciplines and has remained the language with higher social status and prestige. Apart from the ministries where Arabization is complete or partial, in the other government departments not all official documents are exclusively written in Arabic: they are often written in French and then only translated into Arabic when required (p.195).

From the above quotation, it can be revealed as previously mentioned, that currently in Algeria there exist two High varieties Literary Arabic and French along with various spoken dialects. Belmihoub (2012, p.5) claims that since 1962 various languages and varieties are employed in Algeria “Algerian Arabic, Berber, Modern Standard Arabic, French and later (1980s-1990s) English”.

2.5. Algeria’s Educational System

The previous section discussed the linguistic situation in Algeria by giving an overview of the languages used in different contexts. The following section will tackle the educational system in Algeria along with the languages employed with special reference to simultaneous interpreting as a field of study since it is the core of this study.

In this respect, the gap between the two forms of Arabic affects education in the Arab region; according to Ibrahim (2009) “this gap could be a major cause of low learning achievement in schools and low adult literacy levels everywhere in the Arab region.” (cited in Dendane, 2015, p.135). Algeria is no exception as Berger (2002, p.8) describes the language issue in Algeria as “the most severe problem of Algeria in its present and troubled state” due to the numerous language reforms that Algeria underwent and is still going through in language planning policy. The latter has negatively affected the schooling system in Algeria as previously discussed. This argument is supported by the Algerian Presidents Mohamed Boudiaf and Abdelaziz Bouteflika who both perceives the Algerian educational system as “doomed” (Benrabah, 2007, p.228). Similarly, Baldauf and Kaplan (2007, p.7) argue “the most severe problem that Algeria has had to cope with since its independence lies in language”.

The pedagogical system in post-independent Algeria consists of two phases: primary and secondary education (primary school, middle school and high school) and higher education (undergraduate and postgraduate levels). The primary education per se is categorised as

bilingual education in primary school (MSA and French) and multilingual education in middle school and high school (MSA, French, English and other languages for students of foreign languages). In this regard, Garcia (2009, p.390) defines bilingual education as the education that “uses two or more languages in instruction” and adds, “bilingual education does not focus on the acquisition of a second language at the expense of one’s native language”.

2.5.1. First Language Instruction

In relation to this, in his article Dendane (2015) tackled the issue of diglossia in relation to formal education in Algeria through observing kindergarten children who were gradually exposed to MSA while practising various activities. The study revealed that children perform better at school if their L1 is the same as the language of formal education, but although this is not the case in Algeria, it is still possible to achieve this through exposing children to standard Arabic for a two to three year period prior to their education. The researcher also suggested two possible options to overcome the potential impact of diglossia on formal education in Algeria giving the advantages and disadvantages of each. The first one is to teach the L1 in primary school, as though this, children will not face any kind of disruption, as their L1 will be the same as the medium of instruction. However, this proposition may not be feasible in Algeria since there exists more than one Arabic language variety in addition to Berber and its various local forms.

The second suggestion is to use MSA in kindergartens before school claiming that this option will allow children to focus mainly on reading and writing when reaching school because listening and speaking are already acquired. Unlike the first option, Dendane (2015) claims that there exists only one form of MSA across the Arabic speaking world, consequently it is more practical than the first. In addition to this advantage, children can be easily exposed to MSA.

However, several recent studies in this field have shown that there exists different MSA’s. Thus, this might affect the reliability of the aforementioned proposed argument, as there is not one unified form of MSA.

In this light, Garcia (2009, pp.15-6) cites the UNESCO (2003) statement that supports children’s bilingualism and multilingualism education, which states that:

In regions where the language of the learner is not the official or national language of the country, bilingual and multilingual education can make mother tongue instruction

possible while providing at the same time the acquisition of languages used in larger areas of the country and the world.

The case of diglossic languages is slightly different, in Algeria, the students' L1 is one of the spoken vernaculars, and the characteristics of the low varieties might not allow them to be used in formal education.

Chapter 3: Literature Review

Arabic is considered a diglossic language due to the existence of two forms of Arabic used interchangeably: Modern Standard Arabic, hereafter MSA, and regional spoken Algerian dialects along with a bunch of local dialects such as Berber, with its regional varieties, which is the language of the indigenous people of Algeria.

MSA is used in academic contexts whereas spoken Algerian Arabic is used in daily life interactions and in less formal settings. The existence of two forms belonging the same language, each with a distinct role is referred to as “diglossia” (Ferguson, 1959).

Diglossia has a potential impact on the linguistic situation of the country in general and on the educational system in particular. In this case, people in Algeria in general and university students of SI (MSA/English/ MSA) in particular, do not use MSA in daily life interactions. However, they are required to interpret simultaneously from and into MSA assuming that they master Arabic (with its two forms) because it is Algeria’s official language and because students studied MSA for a minimum of twelve years before reaching university.

In addition to that, even within Algeria, there are various and different regional Algerian Arabic dialects as well as Berber dialects that are totally different from Arabic, and which are unintelligible to even Algerian Arabic speakers. Although this is a minority but it should be taken into account since Algerian university programmes are designed on a national basis.

The process of translating and interpreting is not a substitution of a given word in a given language (the source language) for another word in the (target language) but instead it is a mean to transfer culture and knowledge into another language and for another recipient community. That demands a wide knowledge in both the source and the target languages. Therefore, a good command of both interpreting languages is required.

Research in Arabic diglossia has intensified over the past decade or so, however despite the growing body of literature in this field, the impact of diglossia on the educational system in the Arabic speaking countries is still understudied.

According to my experience as a student of SI in Algeria during an MA degree with a speciality in translation and translation studies, where SI was taught as a module in the second year, I observed that students, including myself, were facing difficulties when interpreting from and into Arabic/English. By Arabic, I am referring to MSA since it is the only form of Arabic used in formal education. It is important to note that in SI classes, interpreting was only from English

into MSA and vice versa. Dendane (2010) explains, “MSA is now the common acronym that represents a modern form of Arabic that stems from Classical Arabic. It is the standard variety used, across the whole Arab world, in formal situations, in written text, in education, etc. MSA is not the mother tongue of Arabic speakers” (np).

On the other hand, translation, interpreting and learning foreign languages have always been areas of interest to me, which is what led me to think of an interdisciplinary research topic. In addition to that, encountering various challenges in SI when I was an MA student drove me to question the pedagogy of SI at my university. I was constantly working on improving my English language level but had never paid attention to my MSA level. All these factors contributed to choosing to investigate this area of research.

Among the difficulties and constraints we were encountering as students of SI was our lack of competence in spoken MSA; this led to particular difficulties when interpreting (spoken) in comparison to translating (written) due to several factors. This include time pressure; the high demand of successful linguistic communication; the necessity to handle the speaker’s articulation; the possibility of technical flaws; and no chance for corrections to be made once the interpretation is delivered (Riccardi, 2002). On the other hand, teachers assume that students are fully competent in the Arabic language (MSA) since everybody in Algeria studies it for at least twelve years before reaching the higher education level. Furthermore, this teaching approach does not reflect the fact that Arabic is a diglossic language; it is often taken for granted that being a citizen in an Arabic speaking country, one is able to translate from and into Arabic (Masoud, 1988, as cited in Deeb, 2005, pp.1-2).

Moreover, it is assumed that students already master MSA since they use Arabic for daily life communication without taking into consideration that the form of Arabic used in daily life is dialectal Arabic and not the MSA form required in formal education. Ferguson (1959) refers to these two varieties in diglossia as the high variety (H) and the low variety (L) (p.327).

As a result of this assumption, students are not required to pass a language test to assess their command of MSA; in other words, they are accepted at university to study translation and interpreting based on other criteria, such as the overall score that the university demands, but not an MSA language test. Consequently, all these factors contributed to my interest in conducting the current study.

This study is based upon the proposition that Arabic diglossia has a negative impact on the educational system in the Arabic speaking world and teaching Arabic as a foreign language as well. As shown in the literature (among many others, Abdulaziz, 1986; Maamouri, 1998; Haeri, 2000; Cote, 2009; Ibrahim, 2009; Dendane, 2015) and therefore hypothesises that it has an impact on the pedagogy of SI in Algeria. Thus, this study sets out to explore the potential implications of Arabic diglossia on my participants' attitudes towards the pedagogy of SI in Algeria. Whilst this study was not about teaching pedagogy, it explores the participants' perceptions of SI pedagogy. However, it would be important to do further research on the SI students perceptions of SI pedagogy.

3.1. The Etymology of Diglossia

Diglossia as a term originally emanates from the Greek term '*diglōssos*' meaning two tongues in 'Greek' describing the use of two languages (Leikin, Schwartz and Tabin, 2011). In fact, according to Baker (2011), bilingualism denotes the use of two languages in daily life by an individual whereas diglossia refers to the use of two languages in a society. Similarly, García (2009) agrees with Baker that diglossia "is the term generally used to study bilingualism at the societal, rather than individual level" (p.75). However, bilingualism and diglossia will be discussed further in section 3.5.

Ferguson (1959) referred to diglossia as the use of forms belonging to the same language, which means that there are cases that require more prestigious varieties called '(H) variety' standing for "high" whereas other cases such as ordinary conversations that demand a (L) variety referring to "low" of the same language as will be explained further in the following sections. Later, Fishman (1972, 1980) expanded and redefined the concept to the coexistence of two languages in a society (Baker, 2011).

However, the etymology of the term diglossia is debatable; according to Husni & Newman (2015), the Greek philologist Psicharis is the one who advanced this term, describing the Greek bilingual situation. On the other hand, other scholars, such as Leikin, Schwartz & Tabin (2011) and Albirini (2016), claimed that the term diglossia dates back to 1902, and that Krumbacher pioneered the use of the term. What is certain is that the meaning of the term has changed significantly over time.

3.1.1. The History of Greek Diglossia

It is important to discuss the Greek linguistic situation since it informs that of the Algerian context. In order to better understand the Greek diglossic situation, it is essential to have an understanding of the Greek linguistic situation; what led to the coexistence of two linguistic varieties in Greece, which consequently made the Greek language diglossic.

The decision on the official language is of high importance when a state gains its independence. Thus, Greece after being under the Ottoman occupation for four centuries gained independence in 1830. As a result, the choice of a national and official Greek language led to a series of disputes between conservative Greeks and more radical ones; namely the language of education in Greece, which is the written form, was the foremost concern at that time (Andriotis, 1992, as cited in Gkaragkouni, 2009, p.31).

The reason why Greek language was diglossic is due to the existence of two language varieties belonging to the same language. The first one was Common Modern Greek, known as Dimotiki: it is the variety used by all Greeks to communicate and was derived from the Athenian dialect, whereas the second form was called Katharevusa or the “pure” language, which was similar to Ancient Greek. Common Modern Greek is also named the new Athenian dialect, which is classified as a southern dialect that is dissimilar to the dialects of the north and as previously mentioned, it was means of communication for all Greeks’. Forms of other dialects were employed within the new Athenian dialect, which resulted in making Common Modern Greek’s rules less severe. In addition to this cause, the existence of a higher form of language made educated Greeks very insecure in their linguistic habits (Petrounias, 1970).

3.2. Definitions of Diglossia

The French Arabist Marçais (1930) was the pioneer scholar who introduced the notion of diglossia in the Arabic context; according to Husni and Newman (2015), Marçais differentiated between two Arabic forms: the written, standard Arabic; and the vernacular, spoken varieties, which are used as a means of communication in everyday situations. “According to Marçais diglossia clearly marks the duality of spoken language versus written language” (Van Mol, 2003, p.41).

Ferguson initiated the term diglossia in English and in sociolinguistic literature and it was first analysed and defined in his article in 1959 (Gkaragkouni, 2009). Four languages were selected as prototypes of his study: Arabic, Modern Greek, Swiss German and Haitian Creole; in each

of these four instances, a standard form of a language is used alongside numerous regional dialects (Ferguson, 1959). The article analysed the language situation in four linguistic communities: the Arab world, Greece, Switzerland, and Haiti (Van Mol, 2003) then provided the definition of diglossia, which is as follows:

Diglossia is a relatively stable language situation in which, in addition to the primary dialects of the language (which may include a standard or regional standards), there is a very divergent, highly codified (often grammatically more complex) superposed variety, the vehicle of a large and respected body of written literature, either of an earlier period or in another speech community, which is learned largely by formal education and is used for most written and formal spoken purposes but is not used by any sector of the community for ordinary conversation (Ferguson, 1959, p.336)

Marçais's and Ferguson's definitions are noticeably close. Both definitions refer to diglossia as a linguistic phenomenon in which two linguistic varieties of the same language exist together.

Ferguson (1959) differentiated between the two varieties as follows: (H) variety referring to the high variety utilized by officialdom and in formal contexts whereas (L) variety denotes the low language that is employed in daily interactions within the context of family and friends.

In this respect, Ferguson notes that using high language (H) when the speaker should use low language (L) is awkward, a similar outcome is common when using (L) when (H) should be employed (Ferguson, 1959). Sebba (2011) supported this argument by saying that "H and L have disjoint functions: where H is appropriate, L is inappropriate and vice versa" (as cited in Djennane, 2014, p.52). Ferguson referred to the two codes as 'superposed languages' (Fishman, 1967, p. 30). In this light, Ferguson (1959, p.325) explains that superposed "means that the variety in question is not the primary, "native" variety for the speakers in question but may be learned in addition to this".

Ferguson (1959, p. 328) stipulates that "one of the most important features of diglossia is the specialization of function for H and L. In one set of situations only H is appropriate and in another only L, with the two sets overlapping only very slightly". In other words, functional differentiation is said to govern the choice of the employed code. In this respect, and according

to the languages that his study examined; along with function the study suggests eight other characteristics of diglossia explained below.

Firstly, Ferguson (1959) refers to prestige and claims that H is perceived ‘superior’ to L, and that in some instances the preference of H is due to its association with religion. Furthermore, it is also believed that the H variety is prettier and is more likely to convey important thoughts in comparison with L.

In addition to that, the literary heritage, which is written in H, “is held in high esteem by the speech community”.

There is a significant difference between the acquisition of H and L. Children from their very early stage of learning are exposed to L at home without learning grammar explicitly, whereas H is learnt at schools or through any kind of formal education such as private tutors.

Standardization: the variation in H is confined due to the explicit rules provided in grammar, orthography, pronunciation etc. However, studies of L variety are not sufficient or almost do not exist and frequently the pioneers who tackled such studies are mainly foreigners and the data is presented in foreign languages. L has a sizable variation in pronunciation, grammar and vocabulary but no established orthography.

Furthermore, Ferguson (1959) refers to stability to explain that diglossia is unlikely to be a stable language situation, asserting that “the communicative tensions which arise in the diglossia situation may be resolved by the use of relatively uncodified, unstable, intermediate forms of the language and repeated borrowing of vocabulary items from H to L” (p.332). That is to say, in the case of the Arabic language for instance, “*al-lughah al-wusta*” or the middle language is used in semi-formal settings with a mixture of H and L characteristics.

In terms of grammar structures, there are “extensive differences” between H and L in terms of grammatical categories, system of nouns and verbs, word order. That is to say, the grammatical structure of L varieties is less complex than that of H.

Another feature of diglossia is lexicon differentiation, generally speaking, in the case of non-diglossic languages, for instance the American and English parallels, Ferguson (1959) gives the example of *purchase* and *buy* to demonstrate that “both words may be written and both may be used in ordinary conversations” (p.334). In contrast, in diglossic languages, there exist H

and L words describing common H and L concepts, whereas H vocabulary is never used for conversational purposes and L terminology is not used in normal written Arabic.

The last characteristic of diglossia concerns phonology, H and L phonologies might be either a bit similar to each other, or slightly different or highly different (pp. 328-335).

It is important to refer to the questions that Ferguson highlighted in order to better understand the difference between diglossia and a standard language with several dialects, the familiarity of diglossia across space, time and linguistic families and lastly the factors behind the emergence of diglossia along with the language situations in which it probably evolves (Ferguson, 1959).

It is evident from the above discussion that these different components are illustrated in the Arabic language, Arabic speakers use the H variety in formal settings, whereas the L variety or the vernacular is used for daily interactions.

3.3. Emergence of Diglossia

According to Ferguson (1959, p.338), diglossia emerges on account of three circumstances:

(a) When there is a large amount of literature representing some of the underlying values of the community in a given language, linked with or similar to the natural language used in that speech community;

(b) When literacy is exclusive to the upper class;

(c) When there is a lapse of time between the existence of the first and the second factors.

Snow (2013) on the other hand explains the emergence of diglossia by referring to (Ferguson, 1959; Hudson, 2002), H original forms remain unchangeable whereas L forms change over time which leads to diversion of the two forms of that language engendering the linguistic phenomenon 'diglossia'. He added another factor responsible for the emergence of diglossia by stating that "diglossia in pre-modern societies also arises from a second mechanism in which a society borrows the civilization of a prestigious neighbor, including not only its religion and court culture, but also its sacred language" (Snow 2013, p.64).

3.4. Extended Definitions of Diglossia and Comments on Ferguson's Proposal

Since Ferguson's original formulation of diglossia that was introduced in 1959, a number of scholars attempted to provide modifications and reconceptualization of the term over the years

including (Gumperz 1962, 1964, 1971; Fishman 1972, 1980; Fasold 1984; and Husdon 2002) among others. On the one hand, some scholars proposed an expansion to the notion while others introduced different terms to describe broader and different diglossic situations as will be discussed below.

To begin with, Gumperz (1962, 1964, 1971) provided an extension to the term and argued that the varieties are dialects and registers, as opposed to the varieties suggested by Ferguson which are highly divergent or separated languages, focussing mainly on the functional differentiation that is present in varieties that are perceived as one language. On the other hand, Fishman (1972, 1980) also re-conceptualized and extended the meaning of diglossia to cover situations where there is a coexistence of two languages in a society rather than two forms of the same language as proposed by Ferguson (Baker, 2011), provided that these two or more languages are compartmentalized by territory or language (García, 2013).

Fishman (1972, 1980) redefined and extended the meaning of diglossia to the coexistence of two languages in a society rather than two forms of the same language as proposed by Ferguson (Baker, 2011).

Fishman used the expression “functional separation” in connection with societal diglossia and explained that the use of different codes depends on each code’s different function. On the other hand, Fishman argued that individual bilingualism is related to the choice of language that is not stable and indeed other factors (Fishman, 1967, p. 30). In this respect, he labelled the language used in education and religion (High) language whereas the language used in everyday communication a (Low) language (Fishman, 1967).

3.5. Bilingualism and Diglossia

Fishman differentiated between diglossia and bilingualism by relating diglossia to societies that use two or more language varieties for communication, each used to fulfil a given purpose within society. On the other hand, he related bilingualism to the use of more than one language variety by individuals (De Mejía, 2002). In this regard, Fishman suggested a more detailed distinction between bilingualism and diglossia by stating that “bilingualism is essentially a characterization of individual linguistic behaviour whereas diglossia is a characterization of linguistic organization at the socio-cultural level” (Fishman, 1967, p.34). Furthermore, he explained the relationship between the two concepts and introduced four language situations shown as follows:

	DIGLOSSIA	
	+	-
+ 1. Both diglossia and bilingualism		3. Bilingualism without diglossia
BILINGUALISM _ 2. Diglossia without bilingualism		4. Neither bilingualism nor diglossia

Table 1: The relationships between bilingualism and diglossia, Fishman (1967, p.30)

The first case refers to communities where there exists both diglossia and bilingualism and in which almost every speaker in that community uses both H and L languages or varieties, each is allocated to one set of functions. Among the examples suggested by Fishman is the Arabic situation where Classical Arabic, vernacular Arabic and usually a foreign language are all in use (Fishman, 1967). This tends to be the case in most Arabic speaking countries in which there exists Classical Arabic, spoken dialects belonging to that country along with a foreign language, most of the time it is either French or English with the position of an official or a second language as a result of colonialism.

The second case refers to diglossia without bilingualism. This case refers to existence of two or more languages or varieties in a given territory that is regarded as a result of two or more speech communities united, in which one elite speaks one language whereas the other speaks another language. Historically speaking, in colonized communities, the more powerful elite might speak the H language or variety while the less powerful might speak the L language or variety (Fishman, 1967).

The third case involves bilingualism without diglossia. In such communities, the majority of population is bilingual. Thus, what characterizes this type is that not each language is allocated to a specific set of functions such as the case of diglossic situations. In contrast, both languages can be employed for almost every function (Fishman, 1972, 1980 as cited in Baker, 2011, p.68). Furthermore, in the absence of functional differentiation, the connection between the two languages can result in language shift where the more powerful language will be widespread whereas the less powerful language may be limited (Fishman, 1967).

The fourth case that involves neither diglossia nor bilingualism is somehow less common and can be present either in societies that have been forced to be monolingual or societies that have little interaction with other neighbouring speech communities and who use their minority language in all situations (Fishman, 1967).

It is to be noted that Fishman spoke of territorial principle and personality principle as two social arrangements for bilingualism, which will be explained below as cited in García (2009):

1. Territorial principle refers to cases in a state where a language holds an official position in a certain geographical territory and therefore this territory employs a language different from the language employed in another territory. Giving the example of Belgium in which three languages are regarded as official languages in three different geographical areas: the north, the south and the east.
2. Personality principle is related to a social group's choice to use different languages to fulfil different functions.

Furthermore, Fishman underlined the importance of diglossia by claiming that “no society needs two languages for one and the same set of functions” (García, 2013, p.156). However, Fishman stated that “not every instance of societal multilingualism is diglossic. Far from it” (Fishman, 2002, p.97). Likewise, García agrees with Fishman's argument and refers to diglossia as “it is the term generally used to study bilingualism at the societal, rather than individual level” (García, 2009, p.75).

Fishman used the expression “functional separation” (Fishman, 1967, p.30) in connection with societal diglossia and explained that the use of different codes depends on each code's different function. In this respect, he labelled the language used in education (High) language whereas the language used in everyday settings a (Low) language (Fishman, 1967, p.30).

Furthermore, Fasold (1984) suggested a broader extension of the definition of diglossia by stipulating that:

BROAD DIGLOSSIA is the reservation of highly valued segments of a community's linguistic repertoire (which are not the first to be learned, but are learned later and more consciously, usually through formal education), for situations perceived as more formal and guarded; and the reservation of less highly valued segments (which are learned first with little or no conscious effort), of any degree of linguistic relatedness to the higher valued segments, from stylistic differences to separate languages, for situations perceived as more informal and intimate (p.53).

Among the critics and discussion of Ferguson's first definition of diglossia, the case studies seem to be quite distinct at the level of various factors such as while some instances involve one region to represent one language, others involve several countries (Snow, 2013). An

example of this can be the case of Arabic that is represented by the Arabic-speaking world as a prototype despite the differences that occur not only when moving from one Arab country to another but also within the same countries in which there exist numerous regional differences. Those local dialects are worth investigating separately rather than to be considered as one single instance.

Furthermore, according to the examples that Ferguson (1959) provided, it is clear that the study shed light on Egyptian dialects as a case study to represent and illustrate Arabic low varieties although, as noted above, these Egyptian low varieties may be quite different from the spoken Arabic dialects in Gulf and Maghreb countries. Accordingly, a generalization cannot be made.

3.6. Types of Diglossia

Snow (2013) suggests a revision of Ferguson's description of diglossia and provides three classifications of diglossia, which will be explained as follows:

3.6.1. Traditional diglossia: similar to the definition proposed by Ferguson, it occurs in situations where a variety of spoken L exists along with a shared H language or “a sacred language” as Anderson (2006) refers to it (as cited in Snow, 2013, p.63). H could be classical languages, prestige languages or literary languages. Furthermore, H is often linked to religion as noted by Ferguson: “in some cases the superiority of H is connected with religion” (Ferguson, 1959, p.238). Traditional diglossia emerged in pre-modern communities where only a small proportion of the society has access to literacy and masters H, which makes H more prestigious than L, while the other proportion knows just L vernaculars. Although diglossia is a “stable social pattern”, diglossic patterns are changeable. For instance in some cases of diglossia, L substituted H in several or all domains but it is not the case for Arabic-speaking countries with special reference to Egypt where spoken L is used in formal vernacular situations and even in written situations such as advertising.

3.6.2. Revived diglossia: the most significant characteristic that this case of diglossia has is that the H variety, which is the ancient and unused language, was revived and renewed in order to be used as a symbol to show that a particular community has a powerful past. Furthermore, the H variety is considered as a sacred language due to its connection with religion as stated by Ferguson (1959). The case of revived diglossia is intended by scholars, as noted above, with the purpose of demonstrating the community's glorious past. On the other hand, traditional diglossia is spread unintentionally. In this case of

diglossia, the H and L varieties are genetically related, for the speech community considers the H variety as a proof of its glorious past, that has to be revived and learnt as part of the educational system or in private schools, rather than a variety obtained from foreigners such as colonists. However, unlike instances of traditional diglossia that consider people who master H as educated, the cases of revived diglossia aim to show that the community has an ancient civilization and an identity.

3.6.3. Modern diglossia: as opposed to instances of traditional diglossia, which distinguish members who have a command of H from the rest of population and perceive them as cultivated, this is not the case in patterns of modern diglossia as the majority of population markedly masters H. Moreover, Modern diglossia is not as widespread phenomenon as traditional diglossia. The prestige of the H variety in modern diglossia is not obtained from prestigious literary traditions, sacred languages that are associated with glorious past such as in cases of traditional and revived diglossia respectively but rather from “high utility value” (Snow, 2013, p.69) because it is used by a community proportion who is powerful and wealthy.

Furthermore, Tollefson (1983) also commented on Ferguson’s original definition by explaining its importance in terms of differentiating situations that are diglossic from others where a standard language is used in conjunction with regional dialects. In addition to this argument, functional differentiation between High and Low varieties seems to be considered as a crucial point in showing that there are situations where each of the varieties is employed and perceived as appropriate. Moreover, Tollefson (1983) pointed out that Ferguson’s cases of study “limited diglossia to situations in which the varieties are structurally and historically related” (Tollefson, 1983, p.2).

Recent studies extended and modified the definition of diglossia and Ferguson’s definition is referred to as “classical diglossia” (Sayahi, 2014, p.6). Accordingly, a number of scholars introduced and employed the term triglossia with reference to different situations such as Carter (2010), Youssi (1995), Romaine (1989) and Mkilifi (1972).

In his article, Carter (2010) points out that the term diglossia was substituted by triglossia which has the meaning of “three languages with a middle form neither purely colloquial nor purely classical” and he claimed that absolute diglossia does not exist (Carter, 2010, p.115). Furthermore, Youssi (1995) argues that the co-existence of these languages results in a linguistic situation called Triglossia. With regard to this, Romaine (1989, as cited in Sayahi,

2007, p.41) also employed the term triglossia with special reference to Tunisia to explain that there exists two high varieties consisting of Standard Arabic and French, and one L variety consisting of Tunisian Arabic, as opposed to the diglossic situation where there exists one H variety in conjunction with one L variety. This Tunisian prototype suggested by Romaine seems to be similar to the Algerian linguistic situation in which two H varieties are in use along with one L variety. Similarly Mkilifi (1972, p.198) defines triglossia as situations where:

There exists side by side (a) regional or vernacular languages whose basic role is in oral intra-group communication, (b) a local standardized lingua franca which is used extensively in the education system, mass media and in government administration but which is not developed enough to cover all settings of modern urban technological culture, and (c) a world language.

In other words, the above quotation can describe the Algerian linguistic situation with (a) representing Arabic vernaculars and Berber dialects, (b) representing MSA whereas (c) representing the French language.

Following the previous discussion, it is remarkable that the definition of triglossia seems to be quite similar over time since it encompasses the existence of three languages each having a distinct role. Another argument suggested by Fishman (1967) provides an idea that is somehow related to diglossia but seems to be more likely close to triglossia in the light of the aforementioned definitions. Thus, from a perspective different from Ferguson's that limits the classification to the binary of H and L, among the crucial points that differentiate Fishman and Ferguson's definition is that Fishman (1967) claimed that the functional differentiation could imply more than two varieties. He argues that "the use of several separate codes within a single society (and their stable maintenance rather than the displacement of one by the other over time) was found to be dependent on each code's serving functions distinct from those considered appropriate for the other" (Fishman 1967, p.29). Tollefson supported this argument by giving the example of the existence of a foreign language used for instance in science and technology; a classical variety such as classical Arabic employed in religious contexts; and other H situations as well as a spoken dialect used in daily communication and L situations (Tollefson, 1983).

Platt (1977) introduced the term polyglossia by referring to the case of the multilingual English-educated Chinese residents living in Malaysia and Singapore. He explained that there exist two

H varieties; two “dummy high varieties”, prestigious but less employed by this segment; one medium variety and numerous L varieties (as cited in Sayahi, 2014, p.7).

In addition to the aforementioned proposed revisions to the concept of diglossia, Mkilifi (1978) suggested the term double overlapping diglossia to refer to the existence of three varieties, each of them can function as H and L depending on the variety it is compared to, with special reference to Tanzania (as cited in Sayahi, 2014, p.40).

Therefore, for the purpose of this study, triglossia as defined and explained by Mklifi (1972) is chosen to describe the linguistic situation in Algeria. However, the focus will be on diglossia since the Arabic language is diglossic and this study explores the potential impact of the latter on the student participants’ perceptions of the pedagogy of SI in Algeria.

3.7. Arabic Diglossia

In this section, I will be first highlighting the fundamental differences between Modern Standard Arabic (MSA); Classical Arabic (CA), Arabic spoken dialects or Non-standard Arabic (NSA) and Formal Spoken Arabic (FSA) or Educated Spoken Arabic (ESA) while providing brief definitions for each.

CA as defined by Saidat (2010, p.235) is “in fact, a language form that is mostly used in prayers and which could be distinguished from MSA semantically, morphologically and syntactically”. Haeri (2000) as cited in Cote (2009, p.77) explain the use of CA by asserting that

For most Arabs, Classical Arabic had not been a language they had to learn to write in or take exams in, but one that belonged to readings of the Qur’an and their obligatory daily prayers. Little knowledge of its syntax or any of its intricacies, rhetorical styles, genres, and so on, was necessary for such ritual activities.

MSA is not similar to CA, MSA is used in writing whereas CA is used when reading the Quran and in reading the sayings of the prophet Muhammed (Saidat 2010). MSA is also called ‘Fus’ha’ (Cote, 2009, p.75). Moreover, Kaye (1994) and Cote (2009) claim that MSA is derived from Classical Arabic and is considered as its modernised form.

Dialectal Arabic or Colloquial Arabic as a term covers the linguistic variations that characterise each part of the Arabic Speaking countries along with the variations that exist in each country per se (Djennane, 2016).

FSA for Formal Spoken Arabic, some refer to it as Educated Spoken Arabic, Middle Arabic, the Third Language, or Cultivated Spoken Arabic with the meaning of “the oral medium used among educated Arabs who come from various dialectal backgrounds and who find it cumbersome or artificial to use the literary language” (Abu-Absi, 1986 as cited in Cote, 2009, p.86). This form of language will be discussed further in the following section.

It is crucial at this point to highlight the definition of national/official language(s). National language(s) “are taught in schools as subjects and are also used in schools to teach other subjects. For some children this means learning to read and write, and then speak, a different language from the language of the home (or a new variety of their home language)” (Byram 2010, p.5).

3.8. Formal Spoken Arabic (FSA)

To begin with, Ferguson (1959, p. 332) provides a definition to FSA as follows:

In Arabic, for example, a kind of spoken Arabic much used in certain semiformal or cross-dialectal situations has a highly classical vocabulary with few or no inflectional endings, with certain features of classical syntax, but with a fundamentally colloquial base in morphology and syntax, and a generous admixture of colloquial vocabulary.

According to Ferguson (1959, p.332), this form of language emerged because of “the communicative tensions which arise in the diglossia situation may be resolved by the use of relatively uncodified, unstable, intermediate forms of the language (...) and repeated borrowing of vocabulary items from H to L”.

Furthermore, more recent claims such as Benrabah (2005) and Benali (2002) agreed that the need for Arabs to communicate in regard to the linguistic variations that exist in each country contributed to the emergence of FSA as an intermediate form that meets their communication needs. Both arguments reveal that mutual intelligibility between Arabic speakers from different linguistic backgrounds seems to be the purpose of the emergence of FSA.

In this respect, Mahmoud (1982) as cited in Ibrahim (2009, p.17) also adds elements contributing to the emergence of this form:

The coming of age of many Arab countries both politically and economically, the massive spread of education and the sweeping changes that catapulted some of these

countries into the technological age has produced a new elite with different communicative needs than those Ferguson may have encountered in the 1950's or the 1960's. This elite is comprised mostly of those who have completed their university education either at home or abroad. They did not feel comfortable using MSA, either because they did not master it, or because it was not modernized enough to adequately express the technological and educational advances that have shaped their lives. The lower form, on the other hand, while suitable for mundane needs, was deemed equally inadequate. In order to resolve this communicative dilemma, and in the absence of a common foreign or second language, they had to resort to a type of intermediate Spoken Arabic that cut across regional dialects and could be understood by the educated and uneducated alike.

However, implications of Arabic diglossia seem to affect not only Arabic speakers but also non-native Arabic speakers who aim to learn Arabic as a foreign language. Hence pedagogically speaking, learners, despite the education they acquire which is in MSA, fail to obtain communicative proficiency and serve their conversational needs due to the existence of more than one language variant. In respect to this, a form of spoken Arabic labelled Formal Spoken Arabic (FSA) or Educated Spoken Arabic (ESA) came into existence for this purpose to fit in situations that are semiformal where the standard Arabic is too formal and the dialectal Arabic is too informal and thus inappropriate. The Foreign Service Institute took this issue into consideration and consequently, this semiformal form is taught in conjunction with MSA so that learners of Arabic as a foreign language will not be facing to the lack of communicative competence (Ryding, 1991).

Ryding (1991) defines FSA as follows:

It is not the vernacular of a circumscribed geographical region, but nonetheless represents a real segment of or the continuum of spoken Arabic variants--a supra-regional, prestige form of spoken Arabic practical as a means of communication throughout the Arabic-speaking world. It is also referred to as Educated Spoken Arabic (ESA) in much of the research literature (p.212).

(Ryding, 1991, p.213) asserts that Arabic “exhibits widely divergent regional varieties linked by history and culture to a common written standard but at the same time diffused by the centrifugal forces of great geographical distance and the influence of substratum languages”.

Spoken linguistic varieties across the Arabic speaking world differ not only in terminology but also in pronunciation of some letters and gender differentiation. When dialectal Arabic is written, it is often written whether in Arabic script or in Latin letters in various circumstances such as when using text messages or on social media. In the second case, Latin letters, numbers are opted for to refer to letters that exist in the Arabic language but have no equivalent in the Latin letters. It does not seem that FSA would be effective in terms of teaching it as a spoken variety to learners of Arabic as a foreign language for a number of reasons. First, it may confuse learners who are more likely to encounter the acquisition of two forms of the same language, which will result in learning a literary form, MSA, but not using it as a vernacular and learning another form, different from MSA in order to use it for everyday use. Second, using MSA among Arabic speakers in daily interactions might seem awkward.

However, it does not seem to be the case for non-native speakers of Arabic when they communicate verbally in MSA which is assumed to meet their needs as it is understood by a large proportion in the Arabic speaking world despite its absence in oral communication. Last but not least, it could be proposed that learners of Arabic as a foreign language would learn a vernacular variety that is understood by almost every individual in the Arabic speaking world such as the Middle Eastern dialects due to their huge dominance and presence in media nowadays.

In the light of the above discussion, and with special reference to written Arabic dialects in Latin letters, Daoudi (2018) shares this argument by referring to Daoudi (2017) in her article, that tackles the language situation in Algeria and the aspects that shaped this linguistic profile. The latter will be explained below, while she explains further this situation by giving it the name of “e-Arabic” which according to her is:

A variety of language used on the internet and mobile telephony. The basis of e-Arabic is both MSA and Arabic dialects. It allows the use of dialects in writing (something that was not permitted by traditionalists). It also borrows and adapts words from languages like English and French; it allows code switching and code mixing, and uses numbers to represent missing sounds in French and English Alphabets. Additionally, it permits the use of Romanised Arabic. Furthermore, e-Arabic is not bound by the traditional syntactic, semantic and lexical rules, as one of its characteristics is “language distortion” in order to create “impact”, aiming to engage not only with the globalised

discourse as such, but also to highlight the specific ways in which the local frames the global (p.463).

In other words, Daoudi (2018) refers to “e-Arabic” as the form of language that emerged as a result of globalization, which affected the Arabic speaking world without exception disregarding rules of grammar, lexis and syntax. This language variety is used by Arabs on the internet including YouTube and blogs as well as social media such as Facebook among others. She refers to this as what is known as “Computer-mediated communication” (Daoudi, 2018, p. 463). In the Algerian context, Daoudi (2018) discusses the relationship between language and politics and the latter’s implications on Algeria’s linguistic profile. According to her, two projects or powers contributed to that which are “hard power” and “soft power” as theorised by Nye (2004). The two powers refer to “Frenchification and “Arabization” respectively as explained earlier in the sections discussing the colonial and postcolonial eras.

3.9. Written Arabic Vernaculars

Arguments over the possibility of having spoken dialects written are controversial. Arabic vernaculars are considered as low varieties with no accurate grammar rules and orthography as opposed to MSA, which is more formal and can be both spoken and written. In this respect, Holes (2004, p.75) argues “native speakers of Arabic often say that their dialects are not written languages. It would be more accurate to say that dialectal Arabic is not felt by native speakers to be an *appropriate* variety of the language for writing in most contexts”.

Concerning the field of translation, attempts have been made to translate literary works into local Arabic dialects. To mention one, the novella entitled “Le Petit Prince” written by Antoine de Saint-Exupéry is among the most translated books into numerous languages and dialects including Arabic with its variety of spoken dialects. The dialects that the novella was translated into were Ancient Egyptian, Arabic Algerian, Arabic Hassaniya, Arabic Lebanese, Arabic Moroccan, Arabic Tunisian and Literary Arabic. The translations were in Arabic script as well as Latin script. Therefore, contrary to the statement that Ibrahim (1983) expresses about MSA that it is “virtually the only written variety the exclusion to all spoken vernacular”, many literary works have been written or translated into colloquial Arabic (Kaye, 1994, p.49).

In this regard, Holes (2004) also gives an example of *the Thousand and One Nights*, a literary work written in a style different from the formal one of that time.

3.10. Media: Films/ Music and the Language Commercialisation of Everyday Usage

As previously mentioned, social media contributed to a wide extent to the increase of writing spoken Arabic vernaculars, with the spread use of short text messages and instant chat. In his article, Younes (2009, p.59) shares this argument and states, “it is true that the use of CV [Colloquial Variety] for reading and writing is increasing with the spread of the internet (chat rooms, text messaging, etc.)”. Accordingly, students of Arabic as a foreign language may face an issue, which is that in class, they learn to write and speak MSA, but outside the classroom, MSA is not used for daily life interactions, therefore they are less likely to understand Arabic speakers communicating using colloquial vernaculars.

As an alternative, Younes (2009) suggests that if the classes of Arabic as a foreign language are taught in an Arabic speaking country, then the dialect of that country takes priority. On the other hand, if the program is taught elsewhere, then the choice is subjected to the students’ needs. He continues to explain that it is sufficient to master one Arabic spoken dialect to communicate with speakers of other vernaculars. However, it would be difficult for the ministry of higher education to prioritise one dialect over the other.

3.11. Linguistic Diversity in Algerian Schools: Bilingual Education

García (2009, p.7) illustrates the differences between bilingual education and language education as shown in the following table:

	<i>Bilingual Education</i>	<i>Foreign or Second-Language Education</i>
<i>Overarching goal</i>	Educate meaningfully and some type of bilingualism	Competence in additional language
<i>Academic goal</i>	Educate bilingually and be able to function across cultures	Learn an additional language and become familiar with an additional culture
<i>Language use</i>	Languages used as media of instruction	Additional language taught as subject
<i>Instructional Use of Language</i>	Uses some form of two or more language	Uses target language mostly
<i>Pedagogical Emphasis</i>	Integration of language and content	Explicit language instruction

Table 2: The differences between bilingual education and language education

García (2009) highlights the difference between the two types and explains that:

- 1- Bilingual education attempts to help students coming from a linguistic background distinct from the one of the society and schools. Bilingual education tends to use a language that is not the students' first language in teaching. In general, the target language of the classroom is distinct from the home language of pupils. This enables students to engage in other cultures and languages and to be open to diversity rather than focusing on teaching only an additional language.
- 2- Traditional second or foreign language education tends to teach the language as a subject. In other words, no translation is provided. The main aim is to teach another language. The students learn from being immersed in that language, no translation is provided. Furthermore, the main aim is that the students learn the language that is being used continuously in the classroom.

Skutnabb-Kangas and Toukomaa (1976) pinpoint the difference between “surface fluency” and “academically related aspects of language competence” as follows: surface fluency, or language for social purposes, indicates the ability to communicate in daily life interactions, giving the example of in a shop or in the street and it can be acquired faster in comparison to academically related aspects of language competence. Language for academic purposes takes longer to acquire, from eight to five years or longer (Baker, 2011, p.11).

According to Baker (2011, p.12) functional bilingualism is “an individual’s use of their bilingual ability (functional bilingualism) moves away from the complex arguments about language proficiency that tend to be based around school success and academic performance. Functional bilingualism moves into language production across an encyclopedia of everyday events”. This definition is noticeably close to the definition of “surface fluency”. Thus, both definitions describe individual’s everyday usage of language apart from academic proficiency. That is to say, in order to clearly differentiate between bilingualism and diglossia, a society might be diglossic, whereas bilingualism refers to individuals.

3.12. Bilingualism, Multilingualism and Code-switching

It is important to note that a wide range of concepts may overlap with the notion of diglossia, to mention but a few: bilingualism, multilingualism, code switching, and what Ferguson names

“standard with dialects” (Ferguson, 1959, p. 336), among others. Therefore, these concepts are often confused with diglossic situations as will be explained below. In this section, I will be defining each of the aforementioned concepts and explaining how each of them is distinct from diglossia. However, a distinction between bilingualism and diglossia proposed by Fishman (1967) was discussed in details in section (3.5.).

3.12.1. Bilingualism

Bilingualism as a concept is controversial; in this light, Baker (2006, p.16) states “defining exactly who is or is not bilingual is essentially elusive and ultimately impossible”. On the other hand, other scholars perceive bilinguals as anyone who knows two languages (one of them is their native language) such as (Mackey, 1962; Macmara, 1967a; Haugen, 1953; Baker, 2006; Edward, 2006; Garcia, 2009) while others limit the definition to those who have a native-like competence in two languages such as Bloomfield (1933) amongst others. The two points of view will be explained in this section along with typologies of bilingualism.

It is important at this point to highlight that there is a difference between bilingualism and bilinguality. Regardless of the level of proficiency, bilingualism or societal bilingualism refers to the use of two languages for the same interaction within a given society. This type embodies also bilinguality since it indicates that there are bilinguals in that society. On the other hand, bilinguality or individual bilingualism refers to “the psychological state of an individual who has access to more than one linguistic code as a means of social communication” (Hamers 1981, as cited in Hamers, Blanc and Blanc, 2000, p.6). This point is also explained in Baker (2011) who differentiates between individual and societal bilingualism.

In regard to the first point of view that perceives bilingualism as a minimal competence in two languages, Mackey (1962) states that bilingualism is “the ability to use more than one language” (as cited in Herlina, 2009, p.129). In this light, Edward (2006) considers that:

Everyone is bilingual. That is, there is no one in the world (no adult, anyway) who does not know at least a few words in languages other than the maternal variety. If, as an English speaker, you can say *c'est la vie* or *gracias* or *guten Tag* or *tovarisch*—or even if you only understand them—you clearly have some command of a foreign tongue... The question, of course, is one of degree (p.7).

The literature around bilingualism has developed over the years, from Bloomfield (1933) there has been a long debate around bilingualism.

Similarly, Haugen (1953) bilingualism begins “at the point where the speaker of one language can produce complete meaningful utterances in the other language” (Haugen, 1953, as cited in Beardsmore, 1986, p.6). From his viewpoint, Weinreich (1967, as cited in Wada, 2006, p.64) equally agrees with Edward (2006) and regards bilingualism as “the practice of alternately using two languages”. Macmura (1967a) also suggests that a bilingual is anyone who “possesses a minimal competence in one of the four language skills, as listening comprehension, speaking, reading and writing in a language other than the individual mother tongue” (as cited in Hamers and Blanc, 1989, p.6).

On the other hand, in contrast to the understanding that bilingualism is the basic knowledge of two languages regardless of the degree of competence, some scholars insist on proficiency and competence in the second language and therefore narrow the definition of bilingualism. This argument is simply explained in the definition of Bloomfield (1933) who, amongst others, argues that “bilingualism is the native-like control of two languages” (as cited in Fornusková, 2011, p.3). Baker (2011, p.6) comments on Bloomfield’s definition by describing it as “too extreme and maximalist”, questioning the meaning of native-like control and upon which reference this argument is built. These opinions altogether are perceived as limitations of this definition. Therefore, Baker (2001, p.6) refers to these two contrasting arguments as “minimal” and “maximal” bilingualism respectively.

Minimal bilingualism as the name suggests refers to minimal competence in L2 (Baker, 2011). Furthermore, Baker (2011, p.6) uses the term ‘incipient bilingualism’ introduced by Diebold (1964) to refer to individuals with basic competence in a second language which permits them to be included in the bilingual classification using tourists and business people, who know a few words in a second language, as an illustration.

Maximal bilingualism denotes equal fluency in both L1 and L2. However, as explained earlier this type of bilingualism is “ambiguous” and “maximalist” as Baker (2011, p.6) puts it.

Continuing with Baker’s (2011) categorization of bilinguals, the terms “equilingual”, “ambilingual” or “balanced bilingual”, which is more frequently used, all refer to the type of

bilinguals that have almost an equal command of both languages, across different contexts. On the other hand, Fishman (1972) claims that having a balanced competence in two languages and various contexts is rare. Baker (2011) comments on this argument by stating that most bilinguals' choice of language depends on the situation and the interlocutor. Thus, the same person might use one language at work and the other language at home. He adds, "communicative competence in one of a bilingual's two languages may be stronger in some domains than in others. This is natural and to be expected" (Baker, 2011, p.9). Grosjean (1996) agrees with Fishman and Baker's arguments, and considers equal fluency in both languages rare. He adds the need for that language or skill monitors the competence in that language. For instance one may be able to speak in one of the languages in only a specific domain or subject, or can read and write in one of the languages but not speak it if that language is used with only specific people or particular situations.

The issue with this type of bilinguals is as Baker (2011, p.7) puts it "who is judged normal, proficient, skilled, fluent or competent? Who judges? The danger may be in using monolinguals as the point of reference". In this respect, it could be suggested that language tests such as IELTS (International English Language Testing System), TOFEL (Test of English as a Foreign Language) in terms of English language, could be a way of evaluating one's proficiency in that language covering its four skills: listening, reading, writing and speaking. However, this raises a question; do all existing languages have these kind of tests? Another limitation to this suggestion is the illiterate proportion of whom for instance grew up in an environment speaking two languages but never received formal education in one or the two languages therefore are able to speak that language but not write it. In this light, Baker (2011, p.10) perceives these language tests as "insensitive to the qualitative aspects of languages and to the great range of language competences". He adds "language tests may measure a small, unrepresentative sample of a person's daily language behaviour" (Baker, 2011, p.10).

Far from dominant and balanced bilinguals, the term 'semilinguals' or 'double semilinguals' refers to the category of bilinguals who have limited competence in either language (Baker, 2011, p.). Bilingualism is a "language phenomenon that indicates that an individual functions, in varying degrees of competence, in at least two languages" (Okurinmeta, 2013, as cited in Velez and Rabanes, 2016, p.7).

Beardsmore (1986, p.7) uses the term “ambilingual” to refer to the individual who has approximately an equal competence, in all contexts, and in both languages, thus no language influences the other. However, Beardsmore (1986, p.7) claims that such individuals form a “rare if not non-existent species”. Baker (2011, p.8) comments on that by stating “most bilinguals will use their two languages for different purposes and with different people”.

Beardsmore (1986, p.5) suggests three types of bilingualism as will be discussed below:

1. Horizontal bilingualism
2. Vertical bilingualism
3. Diagonal bilingualism

In terms of dimensions of bilingualism, Baker (2011) refers to the six classifications of bilingualism that Valdés and Figueroa (1994) suggest which are: age, ability, balance of two languages, development, contexts, circumstantial and elective bilingualism. Baker (2011) explains the difference between circumstantial and elective bilingualism:

- Circumstantial bilingualism refers to the situation in which an individual learns a language for the sake of surviving and functioning in a society in which they live and where the language used in that society is different from their L1 such as immigrants. In this case, their L1 is at risk of being substituted by L2. He adds “circumstantial bilinguals are groups of individuals who must become bilingual to operate in the majority language society that surrounds them” (2011, p.4).
- Elective bilingualism is optional, it occurs in groups that choose to learn a second language through classroom education without losing their L1.

3.12.2. Multilingualism

Multilingualism can be discussed at the individual level, referring to an individual’s ability to use two languages or more, as well as the societal level, which describes the use of languages in a society (Cenoz, 2013). Societal multilingualism refers to “the presence in a geographical area, large or small, of more than one ‘variety of language’. . .; in such an area individuals may be monolingual, speaking only their own variety” (Cenoz, 2013, p.6). In this regard, Aronin, and Hufeisen (2009) refer to McArthur (1992) to explain that at the individual level, a multilingual is a person who is able to use three or more language with different degrees of

competence and for different purposes. Other terms such as “polyglot” or “plurilingual” are also used to distinguish individual multilinguals (Aronin, and Hufeisen, 2009, p.15).

Multilingualism differs from diglossia as the latter denotes the coexistence of several varieties belonging to the same language, each with a distinct role whereas multilingualism refers to the existence of several languages within a country or a community. Multilingualism is evidenced in Algeria by the use of Arabic, French and Berber.

3.12.3. Code-switching

Code-switching is also understood as code-mixing or borrowing and the distinction between the three often fails (Eastman, 1992).

Baker (2011) distinguishes between code-switching and code-mixing. Code-mixing occurs in situations in which changes are made in a sentence referring either to a change of a word or a few words in a sentence resulting in a mixed language sentence. On the other hand, codeswitching refers to for instance using two sentences, the first is in a given language while the second is in another language. He also highlights that codeswitching now refers to any change in a conversation either at word or sentence level.

Baker (2011) claims that monolinguals interpret bilinguals’ code-switching as an inadequate competence in both language, which results in using words from another language to fill in the lacuna. Nevertheless, bilinguals justify that by “laziness or sloppy language habits” (Baker, 2011, p.101).

Grosjean (1992, p.23) envisioned the concepts of “monolingual mode” and “bilingual mode” to differentiate between bilingual’s modes while mentioning that between the two there might exist intermediate modes. The two modes are explained below:

- Monolingual mode denotes the situation in which bilinguals employ one of the languages they know (including speaking, signing and writing) as a medium of interaction with monolinguals of that language. It is to be noted that in this mode bilinguals opt for the language of the recipient(s) they are addressing and tend to deactivate the other language(s). However it is hard to totally deactivate the other language(s), this is referred to as “between-language deviations”. These deviations or interferences comprises of two types: static interferences and dynamic interferences. The first type refers to “permanent traces of one language on the other such as

permanent accent”. On the other hand, dynamic interferences mean “the ephemeral intrusions of the other language (as in the case of the accidental slip on the stress pattern of a word due to stress rules of the other language...)” Grosjean (1992, p.23).

- Bilingual mode represents the situation in which bilinguals interact with other bilinguals who know the same languages as them and have the freedom to switch languages.

Muysken (1995) suggests two approaches to code-switching and explains:

There are two dominant approaches to intra-sentential code-switching: those in terms of the alternation of the languages involved in the switch, and those in terms of a single-language matrix structure into which insertion of a constituent from another language takes place. Under this latter view we can conceive of the process of code-switching as something akin to borrowing: the insertion of an alien lexical or phrasal category into a given structure. The difference would simply be the size and type of element inserted, e.g. noun in borrowing vs noun phrase in code-switching (p.180).

The term matrix refers to “the language in which the majority of morphemes in a given conversation occur” (Eastman, 1992, p.2).

In light of the above Muysken’s (1995) quotation, Baker (2011) also distinguishes between language borrowing and language interference (Baker, 2011, p.101) that are relatively similar to Muysken’s distinction of borrowing and insertion respectively.

1. Language borrowing is the result of code-switching, it denotes permanent borrowing of words or phrases from other languages which become a part of that language. Giving the use of ‘*le weekend*’ as an instance of a borrowing from English into the French language.
2. Language interference, also known as ‘transfer’ or ‘crosslinguistic influence’, is the result of mixing two languages when acquiring them. The child tends to mix the two languages to facilitate the comprehension of their speech.

This is particularly relevant to the Algerian context where it happens that numerous French words are used in the dialectal Arabic. That is to say, the Arabic used in daily life interactions is very distant from the MSA used in formal education; as a result, interpreters need to be aware of this.

3.12.4. Standard with Dialects as Ferguson (1956, p.336) refers to it

It is common that variations occur in every language including national, regional, and ethnic variations in addition to variations according to class, gender, age, among others (Piller, 2001) resulting in the emergence of various dialects belonging to one language. However, in the case of diglossia, Ferguson (1956) notes that there is a distinction between diglossic situations and cases of “standard with dialects”. He continues to say that in diglossic situations, H is not used in daily interactions and if used, this will sound, “pedantic and artificial... or else in some sense disloyal to the community” (Ferguson, 1956, p.337). On the other hand, there are cases where a standard language coexists with a variety of dialects, that is to say “the standard is often similar to the variety of a certain region or social group ... which is used in ordinary conversation more or less naturally by members of the group and as a superposed variety by others” (Ferguson, 1956, p.337). Following the above discussion, in regard to the Arabic language, it has the characteristics of a diglossic language and not a standard language with various dialects as the high variety, which is MSA, is not used in daily life interactions, instead Arabic speakers use DA.

3.13. Bilingualism and Translation

One might think that any bilingual could translate/interpret regardless their level of proficiency in both languages and whether they studied translation/interpreting. In this light, Grosjean, (1996) states:

Most people think that bilingualism is a rare phenomenon found only in such countries as Canada, Switzerland, and Belgium and that bilinguals have equal speaking and writing fluency in their languages, have accentless speech, and can interpret and translate without any prior training. The reality is in fact quite different; bilingualism is present in practically every country of the world, in all cases of society and in all age groups (...) As for bilinguals themselves, the majority acquired their languages at various points during their lives and are rarely equally fluent in them. Furthermore, few bilinguals are proficient interpreters and translators (pp.20-21).

The Code of Professional Ethics of the Translator’s Guild of Great Britain states:

A translator shall work only *into* the language (in exceptional cases this may include a second language) of which he has native knowledge. ‘Native knowledge’ is defined as the ability to speak and write a language so fluently that the expression of thought is

structurally, grammatically and *idiomatically* correct (Meuss, 1981 as cited in Baker, 2011, p.68).

In this light, Garcia (2009, pp.15-6) cites UNESCO (2003) statement that supports children's bilingualism and multilingualism education, which states that:

In regions where the language of the learner is not the official or national language of the country, bilingual and multilingual education can make mother tongue instruction possible while providing at the same time the acquisition of languages used in larger areas of the country and the world.

UNESCO (2003) suggests three basic guiding principles focused on intercultural multilingual education as a source for all as discussed below:

- 1- Mother tongue instruction as a means of improving educational quality by building upon the knowledge and experience of learners and teachers;
- 2- Bilingual and/or multilingual education at all levels of education as a means of promoting both social and gender equality and as a key element of linguistically diverse societies;
- 3- Language as an essential component of inter-cultural education in order to encourage understanding between different population groups and ensure respect for fundamental rights.

This is relevant to the discussion of the Algerian context, as in Algeria the first language is not used in formal education. This has a negative impact on the educational system in Algeria.

3.14. The implications of Diglossia on Teaching Arabic as a Foreign Language

Taking into consideration all of the above raises one main question that is how Arabic as a foreign language is taught to non-native Arabic speakers? More precisely, which spoken vernacular, among the various existing ones, is selected by teachers or institutions to be taught to learners so that one is able to communicate verbally in Arabic? The following section is devoted to discussing the potential implications of diglossia on TAFL in order to better understand Arabic diglossia outside the Arabic speaking world along with its impact on non-Arabic speakers. Furthermore, this section introduces the emergence of Educated Spoken Arabic as a form that is neither standard nor colloquial in the context of teaching Arabic as a foreign language and how it can be used to reduce the impact of Arabic diglossia on the pedagogy of SI in the Arabic speaking countries.

As explained in the previous sections, the fact that the Arabic language is characterized by diglossia makes it more complicated to be taught as a foreign language to non-native Arabic speakers. Learners of Arabic as a foreign language are exposed to situations where MSA, the form of language they learn, does not meet their oral communicative needs and therefore cannot be used in daily life interactions as Heath (1990, p.43) puts it:

Teaching students only MSA severely hampers their ability to communicate in the language they have striven so hard to learn. Given that Arabs will understand what such students are saying, the students themselves will not understand anything said to them outside the limited MSA linguistic register they have mastered. Most native speakers use colloquial in their local context. At most they mix registers, moving between colloquial and modern written Arabic.

Heath (1990, p.43) claims that this lack of oral communicative skills results in “students who are functionally deaf”. In other words, MSA and the Arabic spoken dialects are remarkably divergent; when students learn Arabic as a foreign language, they learn MSA whereas when they communicate with Arabic speakers outside the classroom, they will not understand the spoken dialects. This consequently hinders their interactions with Arabic speakers.

As a solution to the aforementioned issue, ESA is suggested to substitute the spoken form of MSA in terms of teaching Arabic as a foreign language.

In order to avoid unintelligibility in communication among Arabic speakers from different linguistic backgrounds (speaking different local dialects) MSA is chosen or “inter-Arabic” or ESA or “middle Arabic” with the use of borrowed terms from spoken dialects (Newman, 2002).

“Inter Arabic speech” is a term proposed by Blanc (1960) after conducting an experimental study that consisted of observing and recording language contact between a small sample of Arabic speakers mainly from Baghdad, Jerusalem and Aleppo, the participants were from different Arabic speaking regions and were living in the United States (Van Mol, 2017). This study proves that Arabic dialects are intelligible despite Chang’s statement to the contrary which states that “spoken varieties of Arabic differ significantly from region to region and are not mutually intelligible throughout the Arab world” (Chang, 2009, p.61). In this regard, Ryding’s point of view is more enlightened than Van Mol and Chang’s. Ryding (2006) claims that the unintelligibility of other Arabic vernaculars among Arabic speakers increases when the countries are geographically distant.

Blanc (1960) named five varieties of Arabic called: Standard Arabic, Modified Classical, Semiliterary or Elevated Colloquial, Koineized Colloquial and Plain Colloquial.

Later, in 1973, Badawi suggested five levels of Arabic after analysing radio broadcasts in Egypt that are as follows: *Fusha al-turath* (Classical Arabic of the heritage), *Fusha al-ashr* (Contemporary Classical Arabic), *Ammiyyat al-muthaqqafin* (Colloquial of the educated), *Ammiyat al-mutanawwarin* (Colloquial of the enlightened) and *Ammiyat al-ummiyin* (Colloquial of the illiterate) (Elgibali and Badawi, 1996).

Meiseles (1980) also suggested four types of Arabic categorized as follows: Literary Arabic or Standard Arabic, Oral Literary Arabic, Educated Spoken Arabic and Plain Vernacular.

Badawi (2006), as cited in Khalil (2011, p.4), claims

Modern learners face the unenviable task of trying to learn an ill-defined, ill-researched, socially diffused phenomenon whose properties and functions are badly and disparately understood by non-native and native speakers alike. The lack of clearly defined language objectives that the teaching profession is suffering from today is a function of the lack of a clear understanding (or at least appreciation) of the sociolinguistic role it plays in present-day Arab societies.

Chouairi (2009) explains the hardships that students of Arabic as a foreign language encounter when only one form of language is taught. Chouairi (2009) asserts that it is possible for students to be understood in an Arabic speaking country using the H variety (MSA), however they will not be able to understand colloquial Arabic used in daily life interactions unless they are reading newspaper articles or watching evening news for instance in which MSA is used. Consistent with Chouairi's argument, Ryding (2009) affirms "the more advanced a student becomes in literary or theoretical Arabic studies, the more acutely he or she experiences a disjuncture between his or her classroom achievement and the lack of ability to deal with the most basic quotidian matters" (p.16).

On the other hand, when students are taught the L spoken variety, this widens their horizons and allows them to integrate into the society and interact with Arabic speakers. Therefore, H teaching is centred on reading and writing "literacy" but not on oral proficiency "orality" (Ryding, 2009, p.44).

Correspondingly, Ryding (2009) clarifies the shift between the two varieties of language and the result of this shift by stating that:

Where Arabic speakers re-calibrate into a less regionally colloquial and more formal level of speech, some researchers have identified a variant of spoken Arabic, an intermediate level that is termed “cultivated,” “literate,” “formal,” or “educated” spoken Arabic or the inter-regional koine. Thus, the Arabic language situation is not characterized as a sharp separation between written forms and spoken forms, but as a spectrum or continuum of gradations from “high” (very literary or formal) to “low” (very colloquial), with several levels of variation in between (p.49).

From the above quotation, it can be noted that communicative tensions are resolved by the use of lingua franca or as Ryding (2009, p.49) names it “inter-regional koine” which has been referred to by educated spoken Arabic as explained and defined previously.

Byrnes (2002), as cited in Ryding (2009, p.16), refers to Gee (1998) to differentiate between two types of discourse “primary discourse” and “secondary discourse”. “Primary discourses of familiarity among family and friends, generally within settings that are presumed to be known or at least highly predictable” whereas “secondary discourses of public life in a vast range of settings” (as cited in Ryding, 2009, p.16).

In the case of teaching Arabic as a foreign language, Ryding (2009) claims

It struck me as I read these astute observations about the teaching of most European languages that in the field of Arabic teaching and curriculum development, we have traditionally done the opposite. We have privileged the secondary discourses of literature and the academy over the privileged discourses of familiarity (p.17).

In other words, much attention is paid to secondary discourses with little attention to primary discourses (Ryding 2009). He refers to this as “reverse privileging” (2009, p.16). Reverse privileging plays a crucial role in increasing the difficulties of teaching Arabic as a foreign language that is caused by the lack of primary discourse and accordingly results in low communicative competence.

3.15. The History and Forms of the Arabic Language

In the following section, I will begin by providing an overview of the history of Arabic as a language, its roots and how it developed through time. Then discuss the emergence of its

written inscription concluding by reviewing its use in the Arabic speaking countries, highlighting the group of variations that this language comprises.

Furthermore, the emphasis will be put on Algeria since it is the case study of this research. In addition to that, this section will discuss the Arabic language used in media across the Arabic speaking countries and its intelligibility among the people of these countries.

The Arabic language belongs to the Semitic group and it is the official language of twenty countries (Holes, 2004). Cote (2009, p.75) argues:

Arabic is spoken by more than 400 million persons in nearly two dozen countries and holds the dual distinction of being the fifth most widely spoken as well as one of the fastest growing languages in the world. However, it also faces the challenge of being a diglossic language, one with two distinct forms, where Modern Standard Arabic coexists with numerous national vernaculars".

3.15.1. Classical Arabic

Classical Arabic (CA) is the language of the Qur'an, the sacred book of Islam. Also defined by Parkinson (1991, p.33) as "the Arabic of the medieval heritage of Arabic and Islamic literature and religion". Gruyter (2014) asserts that CA is considered as the purest form of Arabic.

On the other hand, MSA, which is a modernised form of CA that coexists with a group of spoken varieties, affects the educational system in the Arabic speaking world for two reasons, among others. The first reason is that not all Arabic speakers master CA and MSA. The second reason is that there are minorities in the Arabic speaking world who use local linguistic variations quite distinct from Arabic and this contributed to making the linguistic position of the language more complicated (Strengolt, 2008).

Two groups perceive the Arabic linguistic situation differently. One group regards CA as a sacred language due to its relatedness to religion and therefore cannot be modernised. In contrast others support the point of view that tolerates the changes that might occur in the Arabic language as part of language development that affects any existing language, in order to enable it to cope with the other developments, ensuring that its connection to religion is reserved (Strengolt, 2008).

In this respect, the following argument supports the point of view that is for modernizing the language. Hence Al-Khatib (1995) states:

Those who look at this phenomenon separately from the changes happening all over the modern world, tend to exaggerate the issue. It can't be denied that most modern writers [...] have a weak style and their writing sometimes deviates from the rules of Arabic. We agree with those who want this [new] generation to have better knowledge of Arabic for religious reasons and for unity among Arab countries. But we would like to clarify two points: First, education in our country does not yield its expected fruit. [...] The new generation is [...] not active in acquiring the Arabic language. [...] Secondly, [...] most nations complain that their people, even writers, do not master their language (as cited in Strengholt, 2008, p.85).

In other words, he believes that it is required to preserve CA for religious purposes while taking into consideration that there is a need to modernise CA to meet contemporary needs. Owens (2019) supports Al-Khatib's argument concerning the lack of mastery of Arabic and claims that only a minority in the Arabic speaking world is fluent in MSA but still makes grammatical mistakes. Ibrahim's (2009) position is clearly close to Owens's and Al-Khatib's, accordingly he asserts that there is a need for a spoken form of MSA, and this fact is assumed to be the reason behind the emergence of ESA. Therefore, at present the need for modernizing the language in order to meet contemporary needs is becoming requisite (Ibrahim, 2009). Shvitiel (1999) adds that many words and meanings used today do not have equivalents in Arabic.

This resulted in the existence of borrowed vocabulary from other languages in order to fill in the lexical gap, without forgetting to mention the various Arabic spoken dialects along with the fact that MSA is nobody's L1. These factors all together contributed to increasing the linguistic complexity of the Arabic language. However one question remains unanswered so far in this section that is, since there exists already the notion of MSA which is considered as a modernized form of CA, why is there still a debate over whether to modernize the language or not?

3.15.2. Modern Standard Arabic

The Arab League is an association founded in 1945 and is made of twenty-two countries provided that the population of its member states are Arabic speakers or Arabic is considered as an official language in that member state (BBC News, 2017). The form of language used in this association is MSA, which is quite different from CA in terms of rules and vocabulary (Strengholt, 2008). Furthermore, in his article, Saidat (2010, p.235) states that CA differs from MSA "semantically, morphologically and syntactically" and highlights the main difference

between these forms in terms of usage which is that MSA in Arabic speaking countries is confined to writing whereas CA is used for religious purposes such as reading the Qur'an, the sayings of the prophet and praying.

According to Parkinson (1991) MSA is defined as:

The variety of Arabic that is used in newspapers, magazines, textbooks, academic books, novels, short stories and other "serious" writing. It is used orally in some university contexts, in political and other "read" speeches and in the delivery of the news on radio and television (p.32).

It can be inferred from the above quotation that since newspapers are read easily by a vast amount of population, there are two hypotheses. The first one is that the majority are fluent in MSA whereas the second one is that the form used in newspapers is not MSA in the first place but rather as Parkinson (1991, p.33) describes it as "colloquial" or "a form highly influenced by colloquial".

Saidat (2010) argues that the majority of Arabic speakers are not competent in MSA including some of the ones who are supposed to master this form of language but still make grammatical mistakes when using it supporting his argument by referring to Al-Assaf (2003):

There could hardly come a day without televisions and radios broadcasting interviews and speeches of highly respected officials from different sectors who would speak about the relationship between their countries and other countries using poor MSA. It is surprising and shocking how poor their MSA is. They do not even know how to apply the simplest grammatical rule. I do not see how they have earned their degrees? (Saidat, 2010, p.236)

On the other hand, in regard to grammatical mistakes, Parkinson (1991) gives the example of newspapers to claim that they appoint specialists in grammar whose job is to verify writings in order to ensure that they are grammatically correct.

Attempts to investigate and clearly name Arabic linguistic variations continue to emerge. In this regard, Gruyter (2014) gives three types of variations named: Literary Arabic, oral literary Arabic and Modern Written Arabic but refers to CA, MSA and Arabic vernaculars as the most common ones. On the other hand, Badawi (1973) also suggests five types of Arabic variations

which are as follows: Illiterate colloquial, educated colloquial, elevated colloquial, modern formal Arabic and classical Arabic.

3.16. Arabic Speaking Countries

The results of a study conducted by Parkinson’s (1991) revealed that there is a disagreement among Egyptians, as they are the participants of the study, on defining MSA and deciding what is Fusha and how these two are different from CA. As a result, he concluded that: “educated Egyptians, then, appear to be clearly aware that their modern formal language differs in many respects from the classical language” in other words, there exist more than one form of MSA (Parkinson, 1991, p.35).

Furthermore, Abdelali, Helmreich and Zacharski conducted several studies in order to determine whether there exist geographical variations between MSAs using the common lexicography in newspapers. These studies selected newspapers as materials from five different geographical areas including three from Africa: Egypt, Libya and Sudan, one from Asia: Syria and one from Europe: the UK as materials in order to detect the author’s country of origin. These studies revealed that there are indeed regional variations of MSA.

The following table and chart classify the Arabic vernaculars by the areas in which they are spoken and the number of speakers: there are in total twenty two countries in which Modern Standard Arabic is the official language (Al-Khatib, 2006) along with other languages in a number of cases. It is important to note that MSA is not Arabic speakers’ L1. Therefore, as of significance to tackle the dialects spoken in each geographical area, the following table will provide information on the spoken vernaculars that represent each linguistic area in the Arabic speaking world:

Dialect	Areas Spoken	Number of Speakers
Egyptian	Egypt	64,500,000
Gulf	Bahrain, Kuwait, Oman, Qatar, Saudi Arabia, UAE	36,056,000
Hassaniya	Mauritania, southern Morocco, south western Algeria, Western Sahara	8,842,800
Levantine	Lebanon, Jordan, Palestine, Syria	36,188,500
Maghrebi	Algeria, Libya, Morocco, Tunisia	32,608,700

Mesopotamian / Iraqi	Iraq, eastern Syria	15,655,900
Sudanese	Sudan, Southern Egypt	31,940,300
Yemeni	Yemen, Somalia, Djibouti, southern Saudi Arabia	14,360,000

Table 3: The major Arabic dialectal groups

Extracted from: <http://istizada.com/complete-list-of-arabic-speaking-countries-2014/> (accessed on 06 February 2021).

The above table of the spoken vernaculars representing each linguistic area in the Arabic speaking region has been converted into a chart in order to better demonstrate the number of speakers in 2014.

Overall, it is interesting to note that the number of speakers of the Egyptian dialect is the highest (64,500,000 speakers). Meanwhile, Levantine, Gulf, Maghrebi and Sudanese dialects were considerably close with 36,188,500 speakers; 36,056,000 speakers, 32,608,700 speakers and 31,940,300 speakers respectively. However, Mesopotamian / Iraqi had fewer speakers in comparison to the aforementioned dialects (15,655,900 speakers). Yemeni dialect likewise had fewer speakers (14,360,000 speakers). However, the bar chart shows that only 8,842,800 speakers use Hassaniya dialect.

To conclude, the bar chart above compares the population represented by each Arabic speaking region in 2020.

3.17. Intelligibility of Arabic Vernaculars among Arabic Speakers

Gruyter (2014) points out that Arabic speakers tend to be fluent in their vernaculars and at least another vernacular of another geographical area, however able to understand many others.

It is assumed that some Arabic vernaculars tend to be easily understood by other Arabic speakers because of their media dominance in TV channels such as their TV programmes, series and popular songs. Possibly the degree of unintelligibility is not significant since CA is a common form of language among all Arabic speakers. Furthermore, it is the language of the Islamic holy book that assumedly the majority can read except the illiterate proportion, who did not go to school and therefore did not learn the standard form of Arabic, which is acquired through formal education (Cote, 2009). Holes (2004) confirms this argument by stating that over ninety per cent of Arabs are Muslims and therefore the holy book “Qur’an” unites them. He also confirms that across the Arabic speaking world “the inhabitants of any given village or town will experience no difficulty in understanding the ordinary vernacular speech of the inhabitants of the next village or town in any direction” (Holes, 2004, p.3).

However, he adds that the possibility of intelligibility of vernaculars increases among the neighbouring Arabic speaking countries and decreases when there is considerable distance between them giving the example of an Omani nomad and Merrakeshi townsman communicating with each other in a Kuwaiti supermarket. Holes (2004) claims that cultures tend to be open to each other nowadays with the increase of travelling for education, trade etc. which is enhancing the communication among these populations.

It is to be noted that the fast development that the technology is witnessing, particularly the internet, also contributes to a wide extent in broadening one’s horizons through facilitating the contact among people all over the world, from different backgrounds and cultures; speaking different languages and dialects with no exception to the Arabic speaking region. Thus understanding other languages and dialects became easier and more accessible.

3.18. Mother Tongue, Native Language and First Language

An understanding of the concepts of native speaker, first language and mother tongue, among others, is crucial when discussing translation as a process. Since the aim of this study is to investigate the potential impact of diglossia on simultaneous interpreting (Arabic-English-

Arabic) by Arabic, I mean MSA, along with the fact that MSA is nobody’s first language, as explained before. This section will shed light on translation into a non-L1 in order to investigate whether it affects the production of a flawless translation or not. I will begin by discussing translation and then move to address simultaneous interpreting considering that the latter is an oral translation and both concepts have several common characteristics.

3.18.1. Mother Tongue vs First Language

3.18.1.1. Mother Tongue

At the outset, it is important to begin by distinguishing between the notion of mother tongue and first language (L1). In this respect, Pokorn (2005) explains that the primary meaning of mother tongue as a concept indicates the language that the mother uses as a medium to talk to her child in daily interactions assuming that the mother is the child’s first source of linguistic acquisition. However, Porkon (2005) claims that this definition is not reliable in cases where the child has a carer other than the mother, it could be family members: the father, grandparents or the nanny as Pokorn (2005) illustrates. In this case, the child acquires several mother tongues in addition to cases where the mother is bilingual or multilingual resulting in cases where “speakers can have more than one mother tongue and can even change it during their lifetime” (Pokorn, 2005, p.6). Furthermore, in the case of “linguistically mixed marriages” as suggested by Pokorn (2005, p.7), where “one of the parents uses L1 and the other L2” this results in the child’s acquisition of more than one mother tongue. Skutnabb-Kangas (1981, p.18) claims that the concept of mother tongue is defined according to several criteria explained as follows:

Criterion	Definition of “mother tongue”	Discipline
Origin	The language one learnt first (the language in which one established one’s first lasting communication relationship)	Sociology
Competence	The language one knows best	Linguistics
Function	The language one uses most	Sociolinguistics
Attitudes	The language one identifies with (internal identification)	Social psychology Psychology of the individual

	The language one is identified as a native speaker of by other people (external identification)	Social psychology Sociology
(Automacy) (World view)	(The language one counts in, thinks in, dreams in, writes a diary in, writes poetry in, etc.)	Popular conceptions

Table 4: Definitions of mother tongue

Alternatively, in order to avoid any ambiguity resulting from the abovementioned factors, the term first language is used to denote the first language that the child acquires with regard to mode of acquisition not level of competence, that is to say, “this criterion does not guarantee that native speakers are also proficient users of the language” (Pokorn, 2005, p.6). In addition to other terms such as “dominant language” with the meaning of “the language which becomes dominant in a particular environment or situation” and “home language” which signifies “the language a person uses at home when communicating with his/her family” (Pokorn, 2005, p.2). It is clear that the suggested definitions are noticeably close however in this thesis; the term first language (L1 hereafter) will be used with the meaning of the language that one learns first in order to avoid any misinterpretations of the concept.

3.18.1.2. First language

Native language is also a notion that often overlaps with mother tongue and L1. Pokorn (2005, p.6) states that native speaker as a notion has different meanings, it could mean “a person who uses his/her mother tongue, first language, but also someone who uses his/her dominant or home language, sometimes all four at once and sometimes only one of them”. In this respect, Pokorn (2005) discusses different definition of the concept of native speakers from various perspectives as follows:

The first case concerns those who were born in a family that speaks L1 so they are native speakers of L1. However, this case is defined with regard to mode of acquisition rather than level of proficiency because this case does not necessarily mean that native speakers of a language are fluent in that language.

The second definition of the concept is based on the criterion of environment, which perceives a native speaker as anyone who learnt L1 at home or through the environment. Similar to the

first definition, the second definition does not necessarily mean that these native speakers are fluent in L1.

As opposed to the previous two definitions, the third definition that Pokorn (2005, p.7) tackles, focuses on the proficient use of language, thus “a native speaker is someone who uses the language creatively” even if that language is considered as their foreign language. Davies (2003, p.1) also suggests a definition of the native-speaker concept that refers to “people who have a special control over a language, insider knowledge about ‘their’ language”. Davies (2003)’s definition is relatively close to Pokorn’s (2005), both definitions perceive creativity and language knowledge as features of a native speaker.

Further definitions of native-speaker concept will be looked at chronologically to explore how perceptions changed over time starting by Chomsky’s definition that dates back to (1965) “everyone is a native speaker of the particular language states that the person has grown in his/her mind/brain” (Chomsky, 1965) quoted in Paikeday (1985) as cited in Davies (2003, p.5).

Bloomfield (1927) notes as cited in Davies (2003, p.4)

The child growing up in the province, say, in some mountain village, learns to speak in the local dialect. In time, to be sure, this local dialect will take in more and more forms from the standard language... The child, then, does not speak the standard language as his native tongue. It is only after he reached school, long after his speech-habits are formed, that he is taught the standard language. No language is like the native language that one learned at one’s mother’s knee; no-one is ever perfectly sure in a language afterwards acquired. ‘Mistakes’ in language are simply dialect forms carried into the standard language.

Later in 1933, Bloomfield describes a native language as “the first language a human being learns to speak in his native language; he is a native speaker of this language” (Bloomfield, 1933, p.43 as cited in Davies, 2003, p.4).

Opinions over measuring one’s translation quality based on whether the translator is a native speaker of the source text (ST hereafter) or the target text (TT hereafter) are controversial. The first argument is the traditional view as Pokorn (2005) refers to it, this view asserts “translators should translate only into their mother tongue in order to create linguistically and culturally-acceptable translations” (Pokorn, 2005, p.x). Yet this view is not supported by any solid

argument that proves the preference or accuracy of the translation into one's L1 over the translation into a non-L1 (Pokorn, 2005).

Skutnabb-Kangas (1981) claims that for the majority, determining one's mother tongue is not difficult. However, in diglossic languages, it is more complex because while some perceive the H and L varieties as two different languages, because of the huge differences between them, others regard the two forms as one language.

3.19. Prospects of One Arabic Vernacular as an Alternative to MSA

In connection with the previous discussion that tackled the diglossic situation of the Arabic language and the proposal of selecting one unified spoken dialect in the entire Arabic speaking world, the following section will shed light on a study that explored Arabic speakers' views regarding this suggestion. It is to be noted that this proposal is more likely related to the discussion of language and power and the significant role that media plays in enhancing the intelligibility of a given Arabic dialect.

In a study conducted in 2009 aiming at questioning the possibility of replacing MSA by a spoken Arabic vernacular as a way of linguistic reforms, Cote (2009) states that this diglossic situation hinders communication between Arabic speakers who have different local dialects that are unintelligible to one another as discussed in section (3.17.). In many cases the choice of another third language would be the best option otherwise communication between the speakers of a diglossic language will not be possible (Cote, 2009). Suleiman (2003) also believes that Arabic speakers need "a unified language which can in turn unify them, an instrument of fusion rather than fission" (pp.142-3).

To explain further, as stated previously, CA and MSA are common languages between all Arabic speakers, however these two forms do not serve the verbal communication needs of those speakers and therefore each region has its own local dialect that may be understood by its neighbouring countries but not the very distant ones. For that reason, attempts and suggestions have been made to introduce a language that can unite all Arabic speakers and at the same time function as a medium for oral communication. The question is would it be possible to opt for one Arabic dialect that already exists and make it a common spoken variety for all Arabic speakers? Cote (2009, p.76) argues that the difficulty of applying this suggestion is that "it will be challenging to reach a consensus regarding which colloquial dialect deserves the honour", moreover upon which criteria this dialect would be chosen. Consequently, this

selection seems less feasible since every dialect represents its nation and therefore its speakers are not expected to be open to abandon their dialect and adopt another one that belongs to another nation. The second proposed option is the possibility of producing a new variety derived from a mixture of all existing varieties.

Among the biggest challenges that Arabic speakers might encounter would be the unintelligibility of some spoken Arabic dialects as stated earlier. However, CA and MSA are already common forms of language between all Arabic speakers; any attempt to suggest a new variety of language in the Arabic language may result in more fragmentation among Arabic speakers and therefore worsen the linguistic issue that this language already witnesses. Alternatively, Arabic speakers could embrace the diversity of Arabic dialects. However, it should be noted that MSA is acquired through formal education exclusively and it is the only form of Arabic taught in all stages of formal education which means that those who do not receive formal education in MSA will not be able to grasp or use this form of language (Cote, 2009). As Ferguson (1959) puts it “the actual learning of H is chiefly accomplished by the means of formal education” (p.331).

Similarly, incompetence in MSA or limited competence will prevent one from accessing media especially written media since MSA dominates media (Cote, 2009). In this sense, Newman’s (2002) argument is similar to Cote’s (2009) view: individuals in an Arabic speaking community cannot gain access to media or books without mastering the normative variety of Arabic (Newman, 2002, p.64). In this case, the chances of unintelligibility between Arabic speakers who have no competence in MSA and other Arabic speakers of another dialectal Arabic of a different Arabic speaking country may increase.

Nevertheless, Cote (2009) argues that the media in the Arabic speaking world played a significant role in the standardization of MSA. “Similar or worse problems are encountered in trying to teach adult literacy through MSA. Only where literacy is conducted in the mother tongue have there been significant results” (Abdulaziz 1989, p. 21 as cited in Cote 2009, p.80). That is to say, education in one’s non-L1 leads to less satisfactory achievements in comparison to teaching in one’s L1. Another contradictory question arises: if pupils in any Arabic speaking country receive formal education in MSA for at least eleven years, then for what reason, after finishing their studies, are pupils still lacking competence in MSA? Is it due to the absence of MSA use in daily life interactions or it is because of the complexity of MSA?

The study that Cote (2009) conducted involved participants from various regions of the Arabic speaking world in order to investigate their perceptions on the Arabic vernacular that they think is best intelligible to the majority of Arabic speakers of another dialect. They were also asked about their opinion on the Arabic vernacular that they consider less comprehensible to speakers of other dialectal Arabic. On a scale from one to five, the participants were asked to classify the vernaculars as follows, one (the most suitable dialect that can replace MSA) and five (the least dialect that could replace MSA). The list of vernaculars that the researcher proposed consisted of Egyptian, Maghreb, Levantine/Sham, Iraqi and Gulf as representatives of the five main regions of the Arabic speaking world. Each opinion was supported by an argument and the study revealed the following results: the first choice was the Saudi Arabian dialect; participants justified this choice by the connection of this dialect to religion as well as the fact that Arabic is the language of Qur'an and that Saudi Arabia was the land of Islam, which makes this dialect pure.

On the other hand, Egyptian dialect was selected as a second choice; participants related this dialect to media influence arguing that Egyptian satellite dominates the Arabic speaking world, which makes this vernacular popular and comprehensible. Concerning the less intelligible dialects, the Moroccan was chosen the first and the Algerian the second, therefore the Maghrebi vernaculars were regarded as the last choice to substitute MSA. Arguments supporting this choice included the influence of colonizer languages on Maghrebi dialects, which resulted in a hybrid language. In this light, Cote (2009) argues that if Boucherit's (1991) claim that Arabic/French language contact resulted in a new linguistic product, then "perhaps the spoken Arabic of the Maghreb should be re-classified as a Creole, similar to the division between Haitian-Creole and continental French" (2009, p.83). Regarding the replacement of MSA by a spoken dialect, suggestions were more likely based on a national pride, whereas other participants preferred their own dialects supporting their choice by stating that they are more familiar with them. Following Haeri's (2000) statement that institutions of education in Egypt "have been the major sites of the reproduction of a transformed and renovated Classical Arabic" as cited in (Cote, 2009, p.85).

Cote (2009) suggests that perhaps the Cairene Arabic became the outcome of mixture between classical Arabic, MSA and Egyptian vernacular. This discussion can lead one to question "whether or not the vernaculars should be considered Arabic at all or are simply manifestations of local national culture" (Haeri, 2000 as cited in Cote, 2009, p.75).

Among the suggestions to the existing Arabic diglossic dilemma and its impact on the educational system in the Arabic speaking area, Cote (2009, p.86) concludes by referring to Abdulaziz's (1986) suggestion that "allugha alwusta" or "Inter-Arabic" could function as the standard among Arabic speakers. Furthermore, Cote (2009) also mentions Abu-Absi's (1986) attempt to propose a solution for this dilemma, which is the use of a "Cultivated Spoken Arabic" referring to "the oral medium used among educated Arabs who come from various dialectal backgrounds and who find it cumbersome or artificial to use the literary language" (Abu-Absi, 1986, as cited in Cote, 2009, p.86). However, none of those suggestions was materialised (Cote, 2009). Yet, since it is less likely to choose one united vernacular to serve all the needs of the Arabic speaking world, alternatively "each nation should move toward developing its own form of Arabic based on its national vernacular and that best fits the educational, business and social needs of its population" (Cote, 2009, p.86).

Nevertheless, in Algeria the linguistic situation is more complex. In addition to Arabic, with its various forms, there is the Tamazight language of the indigenous people of Algeria with its numerous varieties too.

It is worth highlighting at this point, how MSA emerged as a result of modernising CA. Cote (2009) asserts that CA was the official language of all Arabic speaking countries. Cote (2009) quoted Haeri's (2000) argument that asserts "trans-forming Classical Arabic into a language for mass education to make pupils use it actively in writing and reading was considered a task of monumental magnitude given the differences between it and the spoken languages" (Cote 2009, p.78).

Cote (2009, p.78) believes that among the reasons that "may be hindering the educational development of the Arab world in general" is the fact that MSA is nobody's mother tongue. Moreover, its structure is somehow complex and this form of language is nobody's L1, Cote (2009) concludes all these facts contribute to depriving MSA of never being delegated as a language spoken for everyday use.

Abdulaziz (1986) made an argument nearly three decades ago which concerns the negative impact of the existing gap between Arabic speakers' L1 and the form used in schools, which is MSA, on the quality of the educational system in the Arabic speaking region. In fact, MSA is used exclusively in reading and writing despite the fact that it is the form that is supposed to

be used in the educational system in general due to its status as a standard form of language. As a result, two forms of language are used in parallel (Abdulaziz, 1986 as cited in Cote, 2009).

In this regard, Maamouri (1998, p.5) pinpoints:

There is a growing awareness among some Arab education specialists that the low levels of educational achievement and high illiteracy (and low literacy) rates in most Arab countries are directly related to the complexities of the standard Arabic language used in formal schooling and in non-formal education. These complexities mostly relate to the diglossic situation of the Arabic language and make reading in Arabic and overly arduous process. There are serious negative educational and social consequences related to these reading difficulties, including feelings of linguistic insecurity by large numbers of youth and young adults when it comes to common acts of social communication and personal expression.

The body of literature on the impact of Arabic diglossia on the educational system in the Arabic speaking countries has grown over the past decade, as discussed above. In Algeria in particular, there is a need for a complex study of dialects due to the existence of various spoken low varieties, such as DA and Berber, alongside other high varieties, such as MSA and French, as discussed above. This has been related to the interest in the development of the educational system in the Arabic speaking world, which has been affected by dialects and diglossic choices, which hinders education, in the Arabic speaking world in general and in Algeria in particular as the literature reveals.

This study attempts to highlight issues relating to DA, MSA and English in the context of SI and reveals the particular issues around interpreting from and into MSA, although it is used exclusively in formal education and it is not the L1 of Arabic speakers.

3.20. Interpreting Simultaneously from a non-L1 to a non-L1

In this section, I will begin by providing definitions of translation and interpreting, both concepts are “forms of linguistic mediation that involve rendering written or oral text from one language to another” (Baker and Pérez-González, 2011, p.3). In this section, I will begin by looking at each one separately including the different types of each and then discuss the similarities and differences between the two.

Wills (1982, p.3) defines translation as:

A transfer process, which aims at the transformation of a written SL text into an optimally equivalent TL text, and which requires the syntactic, the semantic and the pragmatic understanding and analytical processing of the SL.

Baker and Pérez-González (2011) explain that the equivalent in translation is similar to the meaning of synonym, while the former corresponds to items in two different languages; the latter refers to items within the same language. In this light, it is important to highlight Nida's famous differentiation between the two types of equivalence: "formal" and "dynamic" equivalences noting that there exist others in between the two (Nida, 1964, p.159). Formal equivalence translation emphasises the form and content of the message and therefore the message quality is measured by to what extent it matches the source culture. Nida (1964) argues that this form of language is similar to "gloss translation" where the translator tries to "reproduce as literary and meaningfully as possible the form and content of the original" (1964, p.159). On the other hand, dynamic equivalence translation focuses on "complete naturalness of expression... it does not insist that he *the receptor* understands the cultural patterns of the source language context in order to comprehend the message" (Nida, 1964, p.159).

Reiss (1971) perceives translation as "a bilingual mediated process of communication, which ordinarily aims at the production of a TL text that is functionally equivalent to a SL text" (As cited in Dendane, 2010, np). Both definitions agree that translation refers to the rendition of a written material in a given SL to a written material in TL. It is important to note that scholars like Nida (1964) and Nolan (2005) claim that producing a perfect translation is not possible due to the differences that exist among languages and cultures. The role of the translator is also challenging: a translator "must tackle the SL text in such a way that the TL version will correspond to the SL version... To attempt to impose the value system of the SL culture onto the TL culture is dangerous ground" (Bassnett, 1991 as cited in Dendane, 2010, np). One other challenge that the translator faces is the dilemma of form and meaning, if one is favoured over the other loss in the other may occur (Nida, 1964).

In this regard, (Nida, 1964, p.126) notes that:

Since no two languages are identical either in meanings given to corresponding symbols, or in ways in which such symbols are arranged in phrases and sentences, it stands to reason that there can be no absolute correspondence between languages . . .

no fully exact translation . . . the impact may be reasonably close to the original but no identity in detail.

On the other hand, Pökhacker (2004) grounds the definition of interpreting on Kade's (1986) characteristic "ephemeral presentation and immediate production" and defines interpreting as "a form of Translation in which a first and final rendition in another language is produced on the basis of a one-time presentation of an utterance in a source language" (p.11). Some refer to it as interpretation and perceive it as "conveying understanding" (Nolan, 2005, p.2).

However, interpreting as a task is a complex one; it requires instant decision making to convey the uttered message without making the others wait which retards communication; unlike translation, where the translator has time to consult a dictionary or use any other available materials to ensure providing the appropriate words (Nolan, 2005). Back translation is also one of the tools that only translators can use to assess the quality and accuracy of their translation.

Nolan (2005) argues "some experience as a translator provides a good foundation for becoming an interpreter" (2005, p.3) however both Nolan (2005) and Gile (2005) agree that some are able to do both tasks while others prefer one over the other due to personal reasons such as personality and skills. This leads to the discussion of whether interpreting courses should include translation and then interpreting or both should be taught in parallel. In this respect, Gile (2005) writes, due to the common challenges and difficulties that translation and interpreting share, some programs begin by teaching translation basics or translation and liaison interpreting and then specialise in the type of translation or interpreting targeted.

In this sense, Gile (2005) continues with explaining the importance of the preparatory stage that translation and interpreting teaching and learning processes undergo for a syllabus of four years beginning at the first year of undergraduate level. First, this stage prepares students to comprehend that translation is not just a transformation of ideas from one language into the other but rather understanding then reformulating while learning translation skills. The second stage allows students to build knowledge in decision-making and the selection of the right choice of words that certainly enhances and improves the quality of the translation without going through the mental demands, or 'cognitive load' as Gile (2005, p.129) describes it, that interpreting requires. Another benefit of the preparatory stage that Gile (2005) highlights is that it helps students of interpreting become ready for professional translation and not only interpreting.

3.21. Simultaneous Interpreting, Consecutive Interpreting and Liaison Interpreting

Interpreting with all its different types plays a crucial role in a multilingual world such as the one we are living in at the present time. The following section will provide definitions of the interpreting types and their fundamental features, with special reference to simultaneous interpreting since it is the core of this study. However, the difference between interpreting and interpretation should first be highlighted in order to demonstrate how these two notions will be used in this thesis. Riccardi (2002) argues “from interpretation as the activity of interpreting we can distinguish interpretation as a finished object resulting from the interpreting activity” (p.58). Therefore, interpretation refers to the final product whereas interpreting denotes the process.

3.21.1. Simultaneous Interpreting

Simultaneous interpreting is a type of interpreting where the interpreter is “usually sitting in a soundproof booth, listens to the speaker through earphones and, speaking into a microphone, reproduces the speech in the target language as it is being delivered in the source language” (Nolan, 2005, p.3).

It is also considered as:

One of the most common kinds of interpreting, but also the most difficult one. Very few translators (who are used to getting the time to really think about their translations) can do it, and not even all interpreters can do it well (Chen and Dong, 2010, p.716).

As a result, interpreters encounter many constraints; no pauses or hesitations are permitted and messages need to be conveyed faithfully with no time to polish the language or consult a dictionary, that is to say multitasking in a very limited time “seconds or milliseconds” (Gile, 2005, p.129). Gile (2005, p.130) describes the process of SI as “several parallel operations” along with the requirements of knowledge of terminology in a various domains.

In addition to that, the speed and articulation of the speaker should be also taken into consideration as one of the most important challenges that interpreters are likely to encounter:

It is really a very complex process to interpret simultaneously, one that only very few interpreters can handle well. A speaker is speaking, and that speaker does not stop or pause. He keeps talking. Therefore the interpreter must do the following while the speaker is talking: listen to what the speaker is saying; translate it in his mind; render

the translation in his microphone; and (and this is the most difficult part) at the same time listen to what is being said while he is speaking himself. (Chen and Dong, 2010, p.714)

Among the hardships “in the simultaneous mode, speeches are often fast, technical, linguistically more complex” (Gile, 2005, pp.129-130). In this regard, Nolan (2005) also argues that simultaneous interpreting is a challenging task and in view of that, attempts are made to reduce the stress involved in this process and help interpreters. Suggestions include “developed standards governing workload, team strength, and equipment, based on medical studies, which are intended to keep the workload and cumulative stress within reasonable limits” (Nolan, 2005, p.7).

3.21.2. Consecutive Interpreting

Nolan (2005) argues that consecutive interpreting involves listening to a speech delivered in the SL, then taking notes and finally delivering the speech in the TL. To these stages Riccardi (2002) adds analysing the message, memorising it before taking notes.

This process could be divided in parts or delivered all at once while the speaker finishes talking. Memory plays a crucial role in consecutive interpreting along with note-taking (Nolan, 2005). Furthermore, this mode of interpreting is characterized by a longer time lag in comparison to SI and tends to be used for interpreting spontaneous discourses; commercial and technical topics; political speeches; and multilateral negotiations (Riccardi, 2002).

3.21.3. Liaison Interpreting

Liaison interpreting differs from consecutive interpreting in a number of aspects, in the latter interpreters are required to work in only one direction, that is to say, one language and starts interpreting after hearing the entire speech or parts of it (Sandrelli, 2001). On the other hand, in liaison interpreting, “interpreters work in two language directions with a text that is developing ‘in real time’. However, the technique used by the liaison interpreter to interpret each part of the exchange is consecutive interpreting” (Sandrelli, 2001, p.177). Unlike in the two modes discussed above, among the distinguishing features of liaison interpreting, the segments are short and the communication type is face-to-face communication, consequently the interpreter does not need to take notes or use technical devices (Riccardi, 2002). It is important to note that liaison interpreting is the most natural mode of interpreting and

“clarification, explanations, and interruptions are often necessary steps in fulfilling the objective of effective communication” (Riccardi, 2002, p.75).

3.22. Translation and Interpreting: Similarities and Differences

The following section will discuss the fundamental similarities and differences between translation and interpreting while focusing on SI because it is the focal point of the proposed study. Pedagogically speaking, Gile (2005) tackles some key elements that training in conference interpreting lack. First, there is no universal agreement on what works best in such trainings. Second, there are various factors in the interpreting training settings that should be taken into consideration, to mention but a few: student’s previous background, the number of students in each class, their age, their competence in the languages involved and the trainer’s qualifications. Therefore, it would be more effective to take all these criteria into consideration when designing the course rather than following a standard paradigm (Gile, 2005).

In Algeria, classes of interpreting in general including (sight interpreting, consecutive interpreting and simultaneous interpreting), pay less attention to those factors and courses are planned on national bases. Nolan (2005) claims that the translator’s role lies in the reproduction of a text written in the SL in a text written in the TL. On the other hand, the interpreter’s role consists of the listening to an uttered message and then the rendition of that message orally (Nolan, 2005). Nolan (2005) highlights the importance of having a full mastery of the TL along with good command and understanding of the SL in both translation and interpreting tasks. Nolan (2005, p.3) argues that “for most interpreters, the target language will be his or her native tongue”. It is important to note that in the case of Algeria, students of Arabic-English-Arabic SI are asked to interpret from a non-L1 into a non-L1, that is to say, neither MSA nor English are Algerian students’ first languages.

Gile (2005) explains the differences between translation and interpreting which are as follows:

- a) While proficiency in the TL in translation relies on reading, in interpreting it relies mainly on listening involving familiarity with different accents and speech articulations that becomes easier in situations where the conversation held is face-to-face which enables the interpreter to request more explanations when necessary. The latter is acquired through listening practice.
- b) Gile (2005) suggests that translators and interpreters are translating/interpreting from A-language (the native language or passive language) into B-language (active foreign

languages). Translators could assess their translation quality through proof reading and back translation, therefore grammatical mistakes or poor language styles are less likely to occur which means such mistakes are not acceptable. In contrast, in interpreting, such mistakes are not as important as in translation; however, interpreters are still required to produce meaningful utterances with no possibility to verify them once they are said.

- c) Required cognitive skills differ in translation, liaison interpreting and conference interpreting. Translation and liaison interpreting need less cognitive skills in comparison to conference interpreting since it involves multi-tasking in a very limited time.

Nolan (2005) suggests also speaking as one of the important skills embodied in interpreting. Therefore, students of interpreting should have and develop proficiency in two languages; however, this is not enough if not supported by good public speaking skills (Nolan, 2005).

Students of interpreting also learn sight translation that can be defined as “reading aloud a source-language text in the target language” (Gile, 2005, p.134). Gile (2005) suggests teaching consecutive interpreting at the onset and mastering it, then teaching sight translation and simultaneous interpreting in parallel because in sight translation the students are more likely to be translating word-for-word while reading the text written in the SL, as opposed to the approach they learnt before which is “comprehension reformulation approach” (Gile, 2005, p.135). Gile (2005) claims that a possible way to avoid this issue could be giving the students the text beforehand to prepare it and then asking them to translate it quickly.

Dendane (2010, np) concludes:

But an interpreter whose mother tongue is one of the many dialectal forms of Arabic, and not the formal variety called Modern Standard Arabic (MSA), will find difficulties not only in speaking that H variety in a spontaneous manner which the conference or the event normally requires, but also to convey equivalent meanings and expressions of the SL, in particular on cultural and pragmatic dimensions. Only a fully-competent interpreter at all levels in MSA will convey the TL expressions and meanings in a quite successful manner.

From the aforementioned quotation and according to the existing literature that is previously reviewed, it can be argued that Arabic diglossia has a negative impact on the educational system

in the Arabic speaking countries. Therefore, the aim of this research is to investigate its impact on my participants' perceptions of the pedagogy of simultaneous interpreting in Algeria.

3.23. Definition and Challenges of SI

In comparison to other types of interpreting, SI is “the least time-consuming mode of interpreting” (Russo, 2010, p.333). “SI is a complex cognitive ability used to serve communication between speakers from different linguistic and cultural backgrounds. It entails the oral transposition of a message from a source language (SL) into a target language (TL) while the message is being delivered (see Interpreting*). The interpreter therefore has to listen to the speaker and produce her/his own speech at the same time” (Russo, 2010, p.333).

Riccardi (2002) points out that SI is used in international conferences and institutions where the interpreter hears the speaker and communicates with the recipients through technical devices that are used as mediators; also, any kind of subjects is expected to be discussed in those settings. Riccardi (2002) defines SI by referring to cognitive psychology as “a complex human information-processing activity composed of a series of interdependent skills, of which the most striking for the lay person is the capacity of listening to a speech segment in a source language while simultaneously expressing in the target language what has been said in the previous segment” (p.76). In addition to the multitasking imposed in this mode of interpreting, a number of challenges are embodied in that task such as time pressure; high demand for successful linguistic communication; the necessity to handle the speaker's articulation; the possibility of technical flaws; and no chance for corrections to be made once the interpretation is delivered (Riccardi, 2002).

Al-Salman and Al-Khanji (2002, p.608) cite a number of challenges that simultaneous interpreters may face when interpreting, which include: the task requires various types of both linguistic and non-linguistic skills, mastery of the active language, solid background of general knowledge, some personal qualities like the faculty of analysis and synthesis. To these they add: the ability to intuit meaning, the capacity to adapt immediately to change in subject matter and different speakers and situations, the need to have good short and long-term memory, the ability to concentrate, a gift for public speaking, and physical endurance and good nerves (p. 608).

Given the challenges embodied in the task, in order to be able to perform better, Russo (2010, p.333) emphasizes that one has to have “good general knowledge, excellent comprehension

and production of one or more foreign languages, in addition to one's mother tongue". In addition to that, the interpreter needs other interpreting skills which tend to improve through training, for example managing listening and speaking concurrently (Russo, 2010). Excellent comprehension and production of one's L1 are two crucial requirements in SI and seem to be as important as excellent comprehension and production of the other working languages. Conversely, in the Algerian context students of SI's L1 is one of the spoken dialects and not MSA that is one of the working languages in the module of SI at university alongside English, which has the status of a foreign language.

Russo (2010) refers to Seleskovitch and Lederer (2002) to explain that SI is not a task that entails rendering a message from one language into the other (one-to-one equivalence) but rather before this phase takes place, the interpreter has to analyse and comprehend the message, highlighting that occasionally translation of words takes place before the meaning of the message is clear. The importance of the comprehension phase makes the task of SI "meaning-based activity" (Russo, 2010, p.333).

3.24. Directionality in Translation and Interpreting

Research on directionality in interpreting has intensified over the past decade. Arguments over translating and interpreting into one's L1 only or from one's L1 into another language and the quality of the translation and interpretation along with the difficulties involved in each direction are controversial. This section will discuss the various points of view and highlight the results of the main studies in this field that have investigated directionality in translation and interpreting. The focus will be on interpreting in general and SI in particular since it is the core of this study and because of the cognitive constraints incorporated mainly in this task. Interpreting studies emerged in the 1950s where a number of studies attempted to analyse and explain oral translation (Pöchhacker, 2016). Directionality on the other hand was a subject of interest in the first decade of the twenty-first century and continues to be (Bartłomiejczyk, 2015), yet despite the attempts undertaken to explore this topic in the past decades, further studies need to be conducted to investigate directionality in SI (Bartłomiejczyk, 2004).

To begin with, the International Association of Conference Interpreters (Association Internationale des Interprètes de Conférence – AIIC) distinguishes between three categories of working languages in interpreting, and defines them as follows:

- The “A” language, the interpreter’s L1 which is considered as an active language, since the interpreter speaks it fluently and finds no difficulties in expressing even complicated thoughts in that language. Interpreters work from the other languages into the A language in the two modes of interpreting: consecutive and simultaneous.
- A “B” language is a language that the interpreter speaks fluently and therefore is an active language. Interpreters can work into B language but in comparison to SI, they tend to prefer working into B in consecutive interpreting as this mode of interpreting is not as fast as the former.
- A “C” language is a passive language as interpreters understand perfectly and interpret from it into another active language but are not able to work into that language (AIIC, 2012).

According to AIIC, for interpreters, fluency and ease of expression are not equal in all languages involved in interpreting, therefore active languages refer to languages they speak fluently whereas passive languages denote languages which interpreters comprehend perfectly yet do not speak fluently (AIIC, 2012).

However, despite the fact that the aforementioned classifications and definitions that the AIIC suggests are clear, it is difficult to some extent to decide the status of each working language (Gile, 2009). This involves cases such as interpreters whose L1 is one of the vernacular languages whereas their official 'A' language is not acquired at early childhood, as is the case in Africa (Gile, 2009). Gile (2009) is among the few scholars who tackled this situation and this highlights a clear gap in literature, which this study aims to fill. The Algerian context is a prototype of this situation: students of SI' L1 is one of the spoken varieties, dialectal Arabic, while MSA is the A official language of the country, which students learn when they reach school, that is to say, at a later age. Problematic cases that the abovementioned classification does not clearly cover also involve interpreters who live in their B language speaking country (Gile, 2009) in this case a confusion may occur between the status of A and B languages.

According to the above explanation, when applying this to SI in the Algerian context, we can conclude the following: SI students' L1 in Algeria is one of the spoken dialects, so the “A” language is dialectal Arabic or Berber for some students. English on the other hand can be considered as a “B” language, as students speak it fluently and understand it. However, MSA is a language that, presumably, students understand perfectly but do not speak fluently which makes it hold a “C” language status or a passive language. In SI modules in Algeria, students

are expected to work in both directions where the L1 or the “A” language is not involved in any of them, that is from English into MSA (from B into C) and from MSA into English (from C into B). Gile (2009, p.236) observes “many translators and interpreters have excellent passive knowledge of their C languages, including passive knowledge of a rich set of words and idioms, but are not fluent in them”.

Consequently, MSA can be recognised as a C language, which in return contributes to the constraints that students of SI may experience when interpreting from B into C and vice versa. Gile (2009, p.238) outlines “in interpreting, assuming that overall availability is lower in a B language than in an A language and that it is even lower in a C language, working from a C into B entails higher risks of saturation and is avoided”. Availability indicates the time and amount of processing capacity that the interpreter takes to turn a text or a speech into a language element as well as the time needed to access linguistic structures from long-term memory (Gile, 2009).

The AIIC argues “as well as speaking their mother tongue perfectly, conference interpreters perfectly understand one or more other languages and the culture that lies behind them. They may not speak all of those languages equally well” (AIIC, 2012). From this, we can understand the importance of perfectly speaking L1 for conference interpreters while having an adequate understanding of another language and culture. This argument justifies Seleskovitch’s point of view that claims “only in the A language will the speech production be spontaneous and idiomatic” (Seleskovitch, 1968 as cited in Gumul, 2017, p.221).

A number of studies investigated directionality in translation and interpreting; and how do translation and interpreting performance differ when working from one’s L1 (A) into B or from B into A. By directionality, we refer to the direction of interpreting, whether translators and interpreters work from a foreign language into their L1 or from their L1 into a foreign language (Pavlović 2007; Tang 2018). The latter is referred to as “retour” which is a French term for interpreting from A into B (Page, 2006 as cited in Tang, 2018, p.27; AIIC, 2015). “Retour interpreting” is also known as “into-B interpreting” (Bartłomiejczyk, 2015, p.109) or “active interpreting” (Bartłomiejczyk, 2004, p.239) which is said to be more challenging (Gumul, 2017) whereas “passive interpreting” refers to interpreting from B into A (Bartłomiejczyk, 2004, p.239).

In order to check the validity of the claim that interpreters perform better when interpreting into their L1 in an Arabic/English simultaneous interpreting context, in 2002 Al-Salman and Al-Khanji conducted a study. As research instruments, the researchers used questionnaires and audio-recordings of professional interpreters' real performance in both interpreting directions, the latter were analysed in terms of linguistic adequacy, strategic competence and communication strategies. The results of the questionnaires showed that interpreters prefer interpreting from Arabic into English, thus the results of their study were in favour of retour interpreting. This might be attributed to the diglossic nature of one of the working languages involved in the study, which is Arabic, consequently, simultaneous interpreters comprehend the speech uttered in Arabic but feel more comfortable rendering it in English than in Arabic.

In this regard, Al-Salman and Al-Khanji (2002, p.621) confirm that "oral production of colloquial language is in a sense 'more automatic' and more natural than oral production of a 'standard' variety". Furthermore, when they face difficulties in interpreting into CA, interpreters resort to "the implicit knowledge which consists of the unconscious competence they have as a result of acquiring, through natural processes of social interaction since infancy, the ability to speak and understand Arabic, and with which they have better fluency and facility in communication" (Al-Salman and Al-Khanji, 2002, p.623). Al-Salman and Al-Khanji (2002) claim that the difficulty of interpreting into CA increases when the speaker's speed of delivery rate is high, thus they do not have time to recall their knowledge of CA.

Accordingly, following this argument, if we are to apply this in interpreting from English into MSA, simultaneous interpreters equally find it more challenging to find the right equivalent instantly in comparison to translation task where translators have time to think and recall. Attributable to the fact that MSA is not used in daily life settings, "encoding (production) in a dominant language such as Arabic may not be as easy as decoding in it (comprehension)" (Al-Salman and Al-Khanji, 2002, p.608). Moreover, "their knowledge [Arab interpreters] of this form [colloquial Arabic] is both automatic and spontaneous, and switching to it in interpretation requires much less awareness of language use than is the case when employing classical Arabic" (Al-Salman and Al-Khanji, 2002, p.623). Therefore, in the case of the Arabic language in particular, retour interpreting seems to be easier than interpreting into A, since the A language in this case is not MSA but one of the various Arabic vernaculars.

It is important to note that Al-Salman and Al-Khanji (2002) refer to standard and colloquial as languages, registers and varieties of language (pp. 621-2) rather than two varieties belonging

the same language, however there is a clear-cut differentiation between standard with dialects and diglossia (Ferguson, 1959).

When they refer to Arabic in SI settings, Al-Salman and Al-Khanji (2002) do not clearly specify which form of Arabic was concerned in SI, MSA or CA. Yet it is evident from the following statement that both forms were involved, as Al-Salman and Al-Khanji (2002) note that respondents showed deficiencies in classical Arabic; likewise, in situations where they encountered communicative issues, they switched to colloquial Arabic in cases where MSA was to be used.

It is to be noted that when mentioning the notion of 'native language', in their study, Al-Salman and Al-Khanji (2002) refer to it as Arabic without precisising which form of Arabic is in question “control for native language dominance has not always yielded better results. We have noticed that interpretation from English into Arabic presents special problems for interpreters [...] especially in terms of decoding messages” (p.608). They also highlight that in the case of the Arabic language, the production might be harder than comprehension (as the findings of their study revealed).

When analysing the data, Al-Salman and Al-Khanji (2002) found eight frequently used strategies that interpreters choose when interpreting in both directions, which are skipping, anticipation, summarizing, approximation, code-switching, literal interpretation, incomplete sentence strategy, and message abandonment (p, 617). Concerning code-switching, which is a one of the reduction strategies, noticeably the use of this strategy when interpreting into Arabic was higher than when interpreting into English. Al-Salman and Al-Khanji (2002, p.619) explain that interpreters chose code-switching because it is “an easy way out to use the informal form of Arabic instead of the demanding standard Arabic”. Al-Salman and Al-Khanji (2002) note that interpreters used this strategy due to the constraints of the standard form of Arabic, which they describe as “demanding”, as well as the linguistic deficiency in their Arabic language competence, which makes interpreting into Arabic “more problematic” (p.620). However, quality of performance in Arabic varied when the context changed; higher quality performance was noticed in religious text interpretation, as interpreters were familiar with the subject yet the quality decreased when political or economic topics were discussed (Al-Salman and Al-Khanji, 2002).

The two opposite arguments over directionality are presented by two different camps: the Western European camp who rejects interpreting into B and the Eastern European camp who favours into-B interpreting (Page, 2006 as cited in Tang, 2018, pp. 27-8; Gumul, 2017).

- The Western European Camp, Paris School (into A interpreting)

Seleskovitch (1968), who is one of the proponents of the Paris school, argues “only in the A language will the speech production be spontaneous and idiomatic” (as cited in Gumul, 2017, p.221). Scholars favouring into A interpreting base their view on the belief that interpreting into a foreign language entails higher mental load (Bartłomiejczyk, 2015; Gumul, 2017) and interpreters are more likely to commit errors as they are not as confident as interpreting into their A language (Gumul, 2017). Seleskovitch (1978a) does not disapprove interpreting consecutively into-B as opposite to SI settings where she thinks that interpreters should not be working into-B and it should not even be taught at all excluding from her argument interpreting technical materials in which literally translation is more likely to occur (Bartłomiejczyk, 2015). Seleskovitch justifies her standpoint by claiming that speaking a B language fluently does not prevent language interference when interpreting, disregarding listening to a speech in the A language as a facilitator factor for comprehension because the interpreter is already supposed to have a good command of B language (Bartłomiejczyk, 2015). Language interference or linguistic interference as the term suggests denotes interference between two languages where language transfer and code switching tend to occur (Thiery, 2013).

This argument is consistent with the standpoint of Déjean Le Féal (1982) who claims that in cases where the interpreter interprets into a non-L1 “the standard of language and oratory quality can hardly be met. Perhaps even more frequently, we do not have enough background knowledge – even though we may have prepared carefully for the conference – to live up to the standards of clear and precise re-expression of the original cognitive content ...” (as cited in Déjean Le Féal, 1990). Pavlović (2007, p.79) also argues “in traditional, prescriptive approaches, work into one’s second language (L2) is regarded as inferior to work into L1, as evidenced by terms such as “inverse” or “reverse” translation”. Furthermore, Déjean le Féal (2005) pinpoints the inferiority of interpreting into a foreign language by stating that “performance in a learned language is always shakier and less assured than in the mother tongue” (as cited in Tang, 2018, p.28). Furthermore, scholars who perceive retour interpreting inferior than into A, argue that

In the non-dominant language, the level of receptive skills and knowledge will always be higher than the level of productive skills. Accurate comprehension in the non-dominant B language will be achieved with a greater likelihood than its accurate production, and it is thus advantageous to have the B-language text as the source text to be understood, and have the message formulation stage take place in the dominant language (Tommola and Helevä, 2016, p178).

In other words, when interpreting into A, the interpreter is able to fulfil the task successfully in terms of both meaning and style (Tommola and Helevä, 2016).

- The Eastern European camp, the Soviet Union (into-B interpreting)

On the other hand, the contrasting standpoint proclaimed by the Eastern European group held by the Soviet Union upholds that interpreting from one's L1 displays higher level of comprehension in comparison to foreign languages even if the bilingual shows a good command of both languages (Tommola and Helevä, 2016; Gumul, 2017). In this respect, Denissenko (1989) writes "a full or near full message gotten across even if in a somewhat stiff, less idiomatic or slightly accented language serves the purpose much better than an elegantly-worded and an impeccably pronounced half message or less" (Gumul, 2017, p. 222). Thus, Denissenko prioritises comprehension over style; if the interpreter understands accurately the speech delivered in their A language, given the demanding interpreting requirements such as speech rate and heavy accent, the style of rendition becomes of less importance (Bartłomiejczyk, 2015). Furthermore, pioneers of this view believe that when interpreters are interpreting a speech into their non-L1, the number of options used to convey the message is limited which in turn smooths the process and contributes to quick decision-making (Bartłomiejczyk, 2015; Fernandez 2005, cited in Gumul, 2017, p.222).

Moreover, among the reasons of favouring retour interpreting, is that in some circumstances and with regard to market needs, into-B interpreting becomes a necessity in conference interpreting settings (Bartłomiejczyk, 2015).

It is to be noted that political and social contexts contributed to considering only local interpreters as reliable (Brander de la Iglesia and Opdenhoff, 2014 as cited in Gumul 2017, p. 222). This led the Paris school views to move from totally excluding into-B interpreting to tolerating it when necessary emphasising the importance of ensuring the students' mastery of into A before teaching into-B (Bartłomiejczyk, 2015).

3.24.1. The Interpretive Theory of Translation

The French theorist Seleskovitch was the first to perceive translation as a cognitive activity (Gile, 2009). In 1975, Seleskovitch published her doctoral thesis (Gile, 2009) and later developed what is known as “The Theory of Sense” or “The Interpretive Theory of Translation” (hereafter ITT) (Alves and Albir, 2010) in collaboration with other colleagues mainly Lederer. Thus, the ITT until the present time has a vital role in the field of interpreting studies and is a useful model to interpreting trainers (Gile, 2009; Petrescu, 2014).

The ITT theory postulates “interpreters and translators use their knowledge of languages as well as extralinguistic knowledge

- 1) to extract the meaning or 'sense' from the Source Text,
- 2) that is followed by a 'deverbalization' stage in which the Translator forgets the linguistic form in which the 'sense' was conveyed in the Source Text,
- 3) and then by the third and final stage, namely reformulation in the target language from the 'sense” (Gile, 2009, p. 252)

At first, the theory was mainly concerned with cognitive aspects of interpreting; by 1980s, studies began to consider written translation as well (Alves and Albir, 2010).

Seleskovitch considered her own experience with interpreting to understand what is involved in the process “the mental mechanisms of interpreting, mostly through introspection and field observations” (Gile, 2009, p.252). Lederer (2010) adds, “her experience as an interpreter and translator had convinced her that the brain did not build sense by first grasping the meaning of separate words, then putting them together, but rather worked top-down” (p.173). According to the above quotation, she was concerned with the language and mind connection.

Lederer (2010, p.173) defines the ITT as “a coherent construct with high explanatory power, based on practical experience of both interpreting and translation. It was built up little by little, starting from the middle of the 1960s, both to answer the need to know more about the translation process (oral and written) and to meet the requirements of teaching the skills of T&I”.

According to this theory, translation and interpreting activities are not merely linguistic transcoding from one language into another but also complex cognitive activities perceived from a cognitive approach to translation (Petrescu, 2014). As a result of this argument, “one

has to take into consideration the mental processes involved in the course of a translation task as well as the capacities translators/interpreters are required to possess in order to do it adequately (translation competence)” (Alves and Albir, 2009, p.54). As opposed to cognitive approaches to translation, linguistic approaches to translation are merely concerned with the working languages entailed in the activity and therefore view translation as a rendition of a source text (ST) into the target language (TL) (Petrescu, 2015).

The ITT emphasises the importance of the comprehension phase, according to the ITT, translation and interpreting mental process undergoes three stages explained as follows:

1. Understanding: this theory proposes that in translation/interpreting, language competence should be accompanied with cognitive inputs, including encyclopaedic knowledge and contextual knowledge, this link results in the generation of sense, which is the product of understanding. Furthermore, in this phase, memory has a fundamental role, which in return is divided into two types: immediate memory where utterances are stored for a limited time only and cognitive memory where everything that a person knows is stored.
2. Deverbalization: in this phase, the translator or the interpreter focuses on deverbalizing the meaning rather than language structure in order to prepare for the next phase.
3. Re-expression: for ITT, this stage involves the rendition of the message in the target language, thus “from the sender’s intended meaning to its linguistic formulation. Intended meaning is the preverbal origin of linguistic form and, therefore, of sense” (Alves and Albir, 2009, p.55).

In this respect, Lederer (2010, p.175) explains that “sense is made of linguistic meanings plus the relevant extra-linguistic knowledge supplied by hearers/readers”.

Seleskovitch (1989, p.72) remarks:

There would be no need for cognitive complements if translating languages resulted in readable texts or intelligible oral renderings. But on the one hand words are so abundantly polysemic and sentences so unexpectedly ambiguous that pure language translating would result in a chain of lexical entries embedded in awkward grammar.

In the ITT, translation and interpreting activities are similar to monolingual communication where the speakers express their ideas through words and the parties involved in the conversation grasp the message without the need for direct translation; translators and

interpreters understand the meaning and then express the ideas as if they are theirs (Lederer, 2010). Taking into account the time constraints embodied in the task of interpreting, where interpreters are supposed to instantly understand what the speaker uttered, puts a great emphasis on the comprehension phase (Lederer, 2010). However, the participants felt that they have not been equipped to do this. Algeria is a prime example of a functioning multilingual society and this creates challenges for students within a traditional monolingual. That is to say, if the interpreter lacks competence in the source language then the understanding phase would be challenging and accordingly the translation/interpreting will not be similar to monolingual communication. Thus, this study challenges the monolingual model when the interpreter lacks competence in the source language.

3.25. Summary

This chapter provided a profound understanding of the linguistic phenomenon, diglossia, with special reference to Arabic diglossia, in the Algerian context. The literature shows that Arabic diglossia has a negative impact on the educational system in the Arabic speaking world. This review of literature allowed me to establish the contribution of this study, and identify the research gap that this study aims to fill. This research explores the impact of Arabic diglossia on my participants' perceptions of the pedagogy of SI in Algeria.

Chapter 4: Methodology Chapter

4.1. Introduction

In the previous chapter, I reviewed the literature in order to generate an idea about the studies that have been undertaken in this field of research and concluded it by identifying the research gap, which led to these research questions. Accordingly, this chapter will introduce the methodology used in this study in order to find answers to the proposed research questions, introduce the sampling design and explain how the data is going to be collected and analysed. This study is based upon the proposition that Arabic diglossia has a negative impact on the educational system in the Arabic speaking world and teaching Arabic as a foreign language as well. As shown in the literature (among many others, Abdulaziz, 1986; Maamouri, 1998; Haeri, 2000; Cote, 2009; Dendane, 2015) and therefore hypothesises that it has an impact on the pedagogy of SI in Algeria.

4.2. Research Questions

The following questions were designed after reviewing and analysing the existing literature. Thus, they govern the choice of the research methodology, design and approach used in this research. This study aims to investigate the potential implications of Arabic diglossia on my participants' perceptions of the pedagogy of simultaneous interpreting studies at university level in Algeria, in order to explore the difficulties that students of SI may experience when interpreting simultaneously from a non-L1 to a non-L1, that is to say MSA-English-MSA. Furthermore, the study seeks to answer the following research questions:

- What are the potential implications of Arabic diglossia on the teaching methods of simultaneous interpreting from Arabic into English and vice versa to Master's students of SI at the University of Ouargla?

This question aims to investigate whether diglossia has an impact on my participants' perceptions of the pedagogy of SI, and to explore the nature of this impact, if there is any, is it positive or negative. The answer to this question provides primary understanding that will be expended further in the following research questions.

- What are SI learners' attitudes towards interpreting from and into MSA even if it is not their first language (L1)?

The main reason for this question is to investigate the challenges that learners of SI may experience when interpreting from and into MSA with limited use of MSA in daily life interactions. Meanwhile, teachers assume that learners have a certain degree of competence in MSA, because they studied MSA for a minimum of twelve years before reaching higher education, which enables them to perform the task of SI smoothly.

- To what extent are postgraduate learners of SI aware of Arabic diglossia?

This question tends to explore the students' awareness of Arabic diglossia in the educational system in Algeria. The results of this general question leads to further detailed discussion of the implications of diglossia on SI as will be tackled in the following question.

- To what extent would a proposed ESA, as a mixture between Literary and Colloquial Arabic, help reduce the impact of diglossia in the field of teaching SI?

As highlighted earlier in the literature review, ESA is proposed as medium form of Arabic that is neither purely standard nor purely colloquial. This research question is designed to examine the possibility of using this form in the field of teaching and learning SI in Algeria.

- What is the students' experience of the SI classes:
 - What impact did their perceived level of English have on their performance in SI classes?
 - What did the students consider to be positive about the class?
 - What recommendations would the students make for improvement?

I will begin by providing a definition of research, Kothari (2004, pp. 1-2) points out that research is “the systematic method consisting of enunciating the problem, formulating a hypothesis, collecting the facts or data, analysing the facts and reaching certain conclusions either in the form of solutions(s) towards the concerned problem or in certain generalisations for some theoretical formulation”. The reason for conducting a research is to contribute to the existing knowledge by discovering a truth that has not been discovered yet (Kothari, 2004).

Ontology according to Hughes (1995) as cited in Cohin, Manion and Morrison (2018, p.3) is “assumptions about the nature of reality and the nature of things”, whereas epistemology refers to “ways of researching and enquiring into the nature of reality and the nature of things” (Hughes, 1995, as cited in Cohin, Manion and Morrison, 2018, p.3). That is to say, epistemology is how knowledge is acquired.

4.3. Theoretical Framework

The literature review revealed that Arabic diglossia has a negative impact on the educational system in the Arabic-speaking countries and research on Arabic diglossia has intensified over the last decade. Nevertheless, the implications of the latter on the pedagogy of SI in Algeria has not yet captured sufficient attention by researchers. Therefore, my study explores the implications of Arabic diglossia on my participants’ perceptions of the pedagogy of SI in Algeria.

Cohen, Manion and Morrison (2018) postulate that theoretical frameworks “are based on the accumulated wisdom of multiple tests and research; they are the general ideas which underpin the conceptual relationships, and are not specific to the study in question” (p.69). Furthermore, a theory is “based on and bounded by researchers’ assumptions about the subject matter in question” (Alvesson and Sandberg, 2011, p.253), thus, a theoretical framework relates to and helps focus a thesis.

Accordingly, I decided to use the work of Gile (2009) as a theoretical framework as it underpins and informs this study and because it is a suitable framework to explore the constraints that SI students in Algeria encounter when interpreting simultaneously from and into MSA.

One of the popular models is based on the work of Gile (2009) who considers the cognitive constraints among the most dominant limitations affecting interpreting performance (Gile, 2008). Speech production constraints in interpreting are dissimilar to speaking, unlike speaking, when interpreting, speakers have the freedom to rephrase or restructure sentences in order to overcome possible shortages, whereas interpreters are required to follow the speaker (Gile, 2009). In addition to the mental load of SI, from a linguistic perspective, speaking a foreign language fluently does not necessarily enable the speaker to interpret from and into that language smoothly. In the Algerian context, the fact that SI students studied both MSA and

English for a period of twelve years and eleven years respectively does not necessarily allow them to engage in SI without training or a preparatory phase.

In this regard, after experiments and observations in the field of interpreting, Gile (2009) explained the difficulties inherited in interpreting and suggested the Effort Models for simultaneous interpreting, consecutive interpreting and sight translation. Gile (2009) refers to these components as “Efforts” in order to highlight “their effortful nature, as they include deliberate action which requires decisions and recourses” (p.160). Interpreting involves cognitive capacity or ‘mental energy’ as Gile (2009) refers to it, which is “only available in limited supply” (p.159).

Gile (2009) highlights that problems arise in situations where there is a processing capacity deficit, that is to say, the processing capacity of one of the efforts is not sufficient for the required task. Gile (2009) explains that shortages in interpreting are inevitable despite the interpreter’s preparation and experience, yet, even when these deficiencies are not present, “cognitive load-related factors made critical by the Tightrope situation led to numerous errors” (p.191). The Tightrope hypothesis is suggested by Gile (2009) to elucidate that, as opposite to the mainstream idea that, interpreting deficiencies are attributed to insufficient linguistic or extralinguistic knowledge, they occur in fact due to “chronic cognitive tension between processing capacity supply and demand” (p.182). Therefore, a Tightrope situation refers to situations in which interpreters “work close to their maximum capacity” (p.183). In light of the above explanation, in the context of my study, interpreting from and into MSA, which is not the students’ L1, entails enormous cognitive load. In other words, it is incredibly difficult to deal with cognitive load and insufficient knowledge in the two working languages in parallel. Some professionals regard interpreting as constant “crisis management” as cited in Gile (2009, p. 191).

Gile (2009, pp. 167-8) argues that SI consists of three fundamental efforts known as “the Effort Model of Simultaneous Interpreting” in addition to the Coordination Effort referring to resources that coordinate the three main efforts as explained below:

$$SI = L + M + P + C$$

L: the Listening and Analysis Effort

M: the Short-term Memory Effort

P: the Speech Production Effort

C: the Coordination Effort

Gile (2009) proceeds to explain that the suggested model represents SI as “a process which involves a set of operations on successive speech segments. Each of them is heard and analysed (L), then stored in memory for a short while (M), and finally reformulated in the target language (P)” (p.168).

Issues may occur in cases where the available processing capacity is not distributed properly between the Efforts, that is to say, “inappropriate management of processing capacity” (Gile, 2009, p.170). To illustrate, if the interpreter is focusing on the production effort, trying to produce elegant segments, limited capacity would be left for listening to the next discourse (Gile, 2009). Consequently, in this case “the interpreter has not allocated enough resources to the Listening and Analysis Effort and cannot complete the listening and comprehension task successfully; again, this results in his/her inability to render the information in the target speech” (p.172). It is Important to note that in some cases, interpreters do not face difficulties understanding or translating under normal circumstances, however, issues are more likely to occur when insufficient capacity is allocated to the appropriate effort (Gile, 2009). Consequently, interpreters are concerned with managing the cognitive processes.

According to the above discussion, when interpreting from a B language into A, the emphasis is on the listening effort at the expense of the production effort, on the contrary when interpreting from an A language into B, the attention would be given to the production effort since the interpreter is speaking a non-native language (Nigro, 2015). In the context of the current study, students of SI encounter difficulties at both levels, listening as well as production since they interpret from a non-L1 into a non-L1.

However, there seems to be a higher cognitive pressure when interpreting from a non-L1 to a non-L1. In respect of the processing capacity that Gile (2009) addresses, interpreting from and into two non-native languages necessitates more mental energy. In other words, listening and analysing the speech uttered in the source language (a non-L1) and reformulating that speech

in the target language (a non-L1) can be very complex, as both efforts consume mental energy and require more processing capacity, which is already limited.

Gile's thinking was particularly relevant to the context of this study because he focuses on the cognitive aspects of SI and the Model he suggested, aims to explain interpreting difficulties, which are explored in this thesis. A deep consideration of Gile's work helped me to focus my thoughts, and - see below - to ask the questions, which will focus my participants to get the responses, which will accordingly help me to analyse the data and answer the proposed research questions.

4.4. Sampling Techniques

Choosing the sample of a given study could be challenging with the extensive available options that might be convenient to answer the proposed research questions. Yet, the participants in this research are chosen according to various criteria as will be explained below.

Many qualitative researchers often wonder about the size of their samples, whether there is an optimum number of participants or parameters to follow (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018). Although this question is commonly asked in the field of research, there is no 'clear-cut' answer to it (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018, p.203). Consistent with Cohen, Manion and Morrison's (2018) argument, Morse (2000) states that each study is different from the other, consequently it is challenging to provide guidelines for sample size to apply to every study as there are various aspects to consider when deciding the sample size.

Furthermore, the researcher has to be cautious when taking such decision, Mason (2010) explains that participants perceive the world differently, thus the researcher has to strike a balance; the sample has to be large enough to ensure that the diverse viewpoints are tackled while not having a very large sample that generates repetitive and unnecessary data. Mason (2010) claims that one of the key criteria of the decision of the sample size is the concept of saturation. Saturation refers to cases "when the collection of new data does not shed any further light on the issue under investigation" (Mason, 2010, para.2). On the other hand, Cohen, Manion and Morrison (2018) claim that whether it is qualitative or quantitative research, "the essential requirement is that the sample is representative of the population from which it is drawn" (p.209).

In general, the sample size in quantitative research is often larger than the one in qualitative research (Manson, 2010; Dworkin, 2012). In quantitative research, it is advised to have a larger sample as this increases the reliability (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018).

Moreover, the fact that qualitative research requires fewer participants is because qualitative research methods seek to answer 'how' and 'why' questions, which generates in-depth data that help understand the phenomenon under study (Dworkin, 2012). In this regard, Dworkin (2012) continues to explain "in-depth interview work is not as concerned with making generalizations to a larger population of interest and does not tend to rely on hypothesis testing but rather is more inductive and emergent in its process" (p.131). As opposed to quantitative research, qualitative research is not concerned about frequencies "as one occurrence of the data is potentially as useful as many in understanding the process behind a topic" (Mason, 2010, para.1). To this argument, Mason (2010) adds that large sample analysis in qualitative research might be infeasible and hard to achieve due to time constraints.

Morse (2000, pp. 3-4) suggests five elements to consider when deciding the sample size:

- The scope of the study: if the scope of the study is very broad, the researcher will need more data, however too much data do not necessarily ensure the richness of a study. Furthermore, the more the scope of study is broad, the longer it take saturation to be reached.
- The nature of the topic: the topic of the study determines the sample size. That is to say, if the topic is less complicated, straightforward and the data are easily collected from interviews, then the researcher needs less participants.
- Quality of data: this point depends largely on the quality of the data gathered from the interviews. Some participants engage well in the interview due to various reasons including their availability, experience in the topic or openness to share their insights with the researcher, which provides rich data. In such cases, less participants are needed to reach saturation.
- Study design: "some study designs produce more interviews per participant (and therefore more data) than others". Longitudinal interviews "in which the family or group is the unit of analysis (rather than the individual), all produce more data than the single interview per participant design".

- The use of shadowed data: in addition to the participants' own experiences, individuals refer to others' experiences that are similar to or different from theirs. "Using shadowed data provides direction for theoretical sampling, and the clues that it provides in turn enhances the analysis. It simply moves analysis along more quickly".

In other words, the qualitative researcher will need fewer participants when each interview provides a large amount of useful data (Morse, 2000). Morse (2000) proceeds to explain that the number of participants and the method used to obtain data are interrelated. Giving the example of semi-structured interviews, Morse (2000, p.4) asserts "if, when using semistructured interviews, one obtains a small amount of data per interview question (i.e., relatively shallow data), then to obtain the richness of data required for qualitative analysis, one needs a large number of participants (at least 30 to 60)".

Based on the above discussion, it can be concluded that the sample size in qualitative research can hardly be estimated or pre-determined; rather it depends largely on the quality of data. On the one hand, one can interview a large number of participants but obtain poor quality data, whereas on the other hand, one can interview a relatively small number of participants but can get rich and in-depth data. Sim et al. (2018) discuss sampling decisions and refer to Fugard and Potts's paper (2015a), in which they attempted to suggest a calculation of sample size for qualitative research. Sim et al. (2018) claim that, the most dominant critique of this attempt was that "determining sample size a priori is inherently problematic in qualitative research, given that sample size is often adaptive and emergent" (p.620).

The sample taking part in this study involved alumni Algerian students of SI who graduated in 2016 from the University of Ouargla in Algeria with an MA degree in Translation and Translation Studies. As a brief background of the sample taking part in this study, it involved participants of both genders, aged above twenty-five to 30 and coming from different home areas. All participants studied SI, and were required to interpret from English into Arabic (MSA) and vice versa, as an MA module along with other forms of interpreting such as consecutive interpreting as parts of their course. I interviewed two females and three males.

The two-year course included other modules that required translation from and into MSA as well. It is to be noted that the students did not take any prior language test neither in English nor in MSA before studying this course, yet applications were accepted based on the overall score achieved in the BA degree. Furthermore, twenty-one participants completed the

questionnaires whereas the participants who took part in the Skype interviews were five in-depth case studies.

As a researcher, I approached my participants by contacting them via Facebook. As chosen tools to obtain data, questionnaires were distributed to 25-30 participants. As a prior selection tool for the interviews; five students were selected depending on their answers to the first questions in the questionnaire (L1 and current job) and on their answer to question 7: 'Please select among the following options the one you found most challenging in your SI classes: your level of English language, your level of MSA, classroom use of MSA and not dialectal Arabic'. It is to be noted that only respondents who expressed their willingness to participate in the interviews, through providing their details at the end of the questionnaire as requested, were interviewed. Data for in-depth case studies were then-collected using skype interviews. As a plan B, if the response rate was not sufficient, I was planning to expand my sample to 2017 cohort who graduated from the same university as well. However, this was not needed.

Interviews were recorded after getting the interviewees' permission. This sample in particular was chosen because the participants graduated from university, which presumably makes the data they provide richer than students who are currently studying there and gives them more freedom to express their thoughts. Data collection procedures will be discussed further in the following sections. Nevertheless, despite the aforementioned argument that justifies the choice of this sample, it is important to address the main limitation that may be as follows: the students left university three years ago, which may result in inadequacy of the obtained data due to the difficulties to remember a past experience as such. The impact of this issue was reduced by providing the participants with a clear introduction to the research project and through question wording that stimulated their memories and therefore helped them recall their experience as SI students.

As a sampling technique, there are two main types: probability and non-probability sampling (Merriam, 2009; Robson and McCartan, 2016). Probability sampling is used in quantitative studies and tends to generalise the results through the selected representative sample (Clark and Creswell, 2008), which is not the aim of the qualitative research (Merriam, 2009). Therefore, non-probability, purposive sampling are the preferred types for the majority of qualitative researchers (Merriam, 2009, Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018). Probability sampling has six categories: simple random sampling; systematic sampling; random stratified sampling; cluster sampling; stage sampling and multi-phase sampling (Cohen, Manion and

Morrison, 2018, p.214). Merriam (2009) argues that simple random sampling is the most famous type of probability sampling.

On the contrast, non-probability sampling does not aim at generalising the results but rather aims at focusing on a particular unit that belongs to a wider population, yet this type of sampling is more likely to be biased in comparison with the first type (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018). Also this type of sampling falls into seven categories: convenience sampling, quota sampling, purposive sampling, dimensional sampling, snowball sampling, volunteer sampling and theoretical sampling (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018, p.218).

Purposive sampling or purposeful sampling is the most popular type of non-probability sampling, as the name suggests the sample is selected intentionally for a particular purpose, which helps the researcher gain a better understanding of the phenomenon under investigation (Merriam, 2009; Creswell and Plano Clark, 2011; Robson and McCartan, 2016). Purposive sampling tends to be used in qualitative studies (Clark and Creswell, 2008).

It is to be noted that there are various types of purposive sampling, which are typical, unique, maximum variation, convenience, and snowball or chain sampling (Merriam, 2009, p.78). The most popular type of purposive sampling is snowball sampling, which is also known as chain sampling or network sampling (Merriam, 2009) or chain-referral methods (Cohen, Manion and Morrison 2018). Snowball sampling denotes cases where the researcher knows a few participants while it is difficult to reach the rest in this case; the people that the researcher knows connect them with their acquaintances using social networks and personal contacts (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018). However, this type of sampling was not used in this research because I know the participants since we were former colleagues.

Teddlie and Yu (2007) argue that mixed methods research implies the use of the two types of sampling: probability sampling and purposive sampling in order to “increase transferability” (p. 78) highlighting that purposive sampling is also known as purposeful sampling, non-probability sampling, or qualitative sampling. One of the main features that distinguishes the two types of sampling is that purposive sampling is designated to focus on a few cases that will provide in-depth data, while probability sampling focuses on a larger number of cases representing a certain population that will in turn offer larger amount of data (Teddlie and Yu, 2007)

However, although in general most mixed methods studies use both sampling types: purposive and probability, in some cases only one type is appropriate in terms of addressing the research questions and therefore one of them could be used (Teddlie and Yu, 2007). Teddlie and Yu (2007) continue to explain that even if the researcher is using a mixed methods research, it is common that one of the approaches predominates, for instance if the focus of the study is on quantitative approach, probability sampling is more likely to be used. Conversely, if the importance is given to qualitative approach, purposive and non-probability sampling are more likely to be chosen.

According to the above discussion, the purposive sampling strategy was used in this study because, as mentioned earlier, it focuses on a few cases that will provide in-depth data. Moreover, the sample was selected on purpose in order to provide the information needed to answer the proposed research questions while taking into consideration that qualitative data is the focus of this research. Furthermore, through the lens of mixed methods, data was collected using online surveys and Skype semi-structured interviews.

4.5. Definitions of Terms

It is important at this stage to provide initial definitions of terms that will be used throughout this chapter and which will be discussed in further details in each section, terms include methodology, method, research design and paradigm. Methodology refers to “the theory (or set of ideas about the relationship between phenomena) of how researchers gain knowledge in research contexts and why” (Scott and Morrison 2006, p.153). Furthermore, Taylor, Bogdan, and DeVault (2015) explain that the methodology chosen is determined by various factors such as the purpose of the study, the research interests and the assumptions we make. Therefore, methodology as a term denotes “the way in which we approach problems and seek answers” (Taylor, Bogdan, and DeVault, p.3, 2015).

Research design on the other hand is “a procedure for collecting, analysing and reporting research such as that found in the time-honored designs of quantitative experiments and surveys and in the qualitative approaches of ethnographies, grounded theory studies, and case studies” (Creswell, et al, 2003, p.163). Paradigm, according to Bassey (2007, p.42), is “a network of coherent ideas about the nature of the world and the function of researchers which, adhered to by a group of researchers, conditions the patterns of their thinking and underpins their research actions”.

4.6. Research Approach: Positivism vs Interpretivism

In the light of the elements addressed in the literature review chapter, including the impact of diglossia on the educational system in the Arabic speaking countries, this study will shed light on the pedagogy of SI in Algeria and the perceptions of learners of SI towards the impact of diglossia on this pedagogy. Taylor, Bogdan, and DeVault (2015) state that in social sciences there are two fundamental theoretical perspectives, which are positivism and phenomenologist perspective, also commonly referred as interpretivist, each perspective tackles different types of problems, looks for different types of answers and consequently uses different methodologies. The two approaches are discussed below.

4.6.1. Interpretivism

Interpretivists on the other hand aim to obtain an understanding of social phenomena through individual's own perceptions using qualitative methods such as participant observation and in-depth interviewing, claiming that the reality is defined by people's perceptions and therefore gathering descriptive data (Taylor, Bogdan, and DeVault, 2015). Descriptive data refers to the "people's own written or spoken words and observable behaviour" (Taylor, Bogdan, and DeVault, 2015, p. 7).

Based on the above discussion, an interpretivist research approach is adopted for this study since this research aims at gathering descriptive data, in this case the perceptions of Algerian students of SI on the impact of Arabic diglossia on the pedagogy of SI through mixed methods. The tools used to collect data are questionnaires and semi-structured interviews. Questionnaires are considered as the first source of data that help selecting interviewees to take part in in-depth interviewing based on the answers obtained from the questionnaires.

The questionnaires were my first data collection tool, followed by semi-structured Skype interviews. The questionnaires were used to obtain data that helped refine and reframe the interview schedule. For instance, it can be seen in appendix E on page 231-3 question 15 which is "in your opinion what impact did your level of English have on your performance in SI classes?" was added to the interview questions as a result of the questionnaire responses as follows.

In this study, the questionnaires were used to get an overview of the participants' perceptions of their MSA oral and written levels, how they perceive the SI classes at their university and

what was the most challenging element in the SI classes. In this respect, twenty-one respondents completed the online survey.

The data was collected and analysed sequentially, quantitative data collection and analysis preceded the qualitative data collection and analysis. After analysing the survey data, the results highlighted some relevant data that had to be discussed in more depth in the interviews as explained earlier.

4.7. Research Design

4.7.1. Mixed Methods Research

First, I will begin by defining research design as a term. A research design refers to all the issues present when undertaking a research from the start (pinpointing the problem) to the end (publishing the results) (Punch, 2013).

Moreover, moving to a more detailed definition, it connotes “the overall strategy that you choose to integrate the different components of the study in a coherent and logical way, thereby, ensuring you will effectively address the research problem; it constitutes the blueprint for the collection, measurement, and analysis of data” (Labaree, 2013, p.1).

The research design used in this research is a mixed methods research. In general, mixed methods as a concept denotes mixing distinct methods (Creswell, Gutmann, and Hanson, 2003).

Mixed methods research design involves:

The collection or analysis of both quantitative and/or qualitative data in a single study in which the data are collected concurrently or sequentially, are given a priority, and involve the integration of the data at one or more stages in the process of research (Creswell, et al, 2003, p.156).

The aforementioned definition views the design in terms of the importance given to each method in order to collect data along with the nature of data collection whether it is acquired simultaneously or successively (Creswell, et al, 2003).

Later, the definition evolved and Creswell (2006) defines the concept as:

Mixed methods research is a research design with philosophical assumptions as well as methods of inquiry. As a methodology, it involves philosophical assumptions that guide the direction of the collection and analysis of data and the mixture of qualitative and quantitative approaches in many phases in the research process. As a method, it focuses on collecting, analyzing, and mixing both quantitative and qualitative data in a single study or series of studies. Its central premise is that the use of quantitative and qualitative approaches in combination provides a better understanding of research problems than either approach alone (p.5).

Overall, among the advantages of mixed methods research design integrating both quantitative and qualitative methods is that both research designs are used in investigating problems related to social sciences, mixing the two “can neutralize or cancel out some of the disadvantages of certain methods” (Creswell et al, 2003, p.211). Furthermore, due to the complexity existing in social sciences, the use of multiple methods results in broader understanding of the phenomenon (Greene and Caracelli, 1997 cited in Creswell et al, 2003). The idea of mixed methods research is that there are multiple ways of perceiving the world and it is not only concerned with data collection but it embodies data analysis and combining both quantitative and qualitative data in the same study (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018).

The purpose of choosing a mixed methods research design in this study is determined by the nature of the research questions and research aims as Labaree (2013) highlights, the research design is determined by the research problem. Consistent with Labaree’s view, Creswell and Plano Clark (2011) assert that research problems and questions justify the choice of mixed methods study. Moreover, by using mixed methods the researcher benefits from the strengths of both qualitative and quantitative methods and therefore the weaknesses of both are minimised (Tashakkori and Teddlie, 2003, p.211; Creswell and Plano Clark, 2011; Denscombe, 2014; Scott, 2017). Creswell and Plano Clark (2011) continue to emphasise that the research problem needs to be studied through more than one type of methods and with the use of various data sources in order to enhance the understanding of the phenomenon under study and best address the research problems. In addition to that, Scott (2017) argues that the two methods complete each other leading to obtaining more objective data. Consistent with Scott’s view, Cohen, Manion and Morrison (2018, p.32) assert, “the use of quantitative and qualitative approaches, in combination, provides a better understanding of research problems

and questions than either approach on its own”. In the light of the aforementioned advantages of mixing quantitative and qualitative approaches, mixed methods research was used in this study.

Denscombe (2014, p.160) gives four advantages of using mixed methods approach which are as follows. First, it enhances the comprehension of the phenomenon under study. Second, it is “a practical, problem-driven approach to research”, which “gives voice to the general practice of a large proportion of social researchers”. Third, it allows the researcher to clearly demonstrate how and why alternative methods are complementary and lastly, mixed methods approach helps balance the advantages and the disadvantages of methods in a way that enables the researcher to benefit from the advantages of each one without being criticised for its weaknesses.

However, mixed methods approach has also disadvantages, in this light, Denscombe (2014, p.161) points out five limitations. The first limitation concerns time and costs. However, in this research, both qualitative and quantitative data collection took place online, which eliminated the limitation of costs.

The second limitation regards the need of developing an expertise in each approach when using mixed methods, which therefore requires more efforts and skills (Dencombe, 2014). As a researcher, I did an extensive reading about the use of mixed methods before applying it.

The third constraint involves the possibility of having to extend the research if the data derived from both methods cannot be integrated. Nevertheless, I did not encounter this limitation in my research.

Furthermore, Denscombe (2014) adds another shortcoming of integrating qualitative and quantitative approaches, which is “when making the QUAL/QUAN distinction mixed methods researchers need to be aware that the clarity and simplicity of the terms mask a more complicated reality” (p.161).

The final limitation of combining these approaches is that “the underlying philosophy of the mixed methods approach –pragmatism- is open to misinterpretation” (p.161).

4.7.1.1. Qualitative Research (Limitations and Ethics)

The recognition and use of qualitative methods in social sciences date back to the 19th century (Taylor, Bogdan, and DeVault, 2015). Qualitative research can be defined as:

A form of social inquiry that tends to adopt a flexible and data-driven research design, to use relatively unstructured data, to emphasize the essential role of subjectivity in the research process, to study a number of naturally occurring cases in detail, and to use verbal rather than statistical forms of approach. (Hammersley, 2013 as cited in Cohen, Manion and Morrison 2018, p.287).

In this regard, qualitative researchers aim at “understanding how people interpret their experiences, how they construct their worlds, and what meaning they attribute to their experiences” (Merriam, 2009, p.5). Moreover, qualitative researchers give importance to generating a deep understanding about situations and people rather than averages and numbers (Rubin and Rubin, 2011).

Given the preceding arguments, as a researcher I used qualitative approach as a main method of data collection preceded by quantitative research in order to obtain an overview of how students of SI initially regard Arabic diglossia and the pedagogy of SI. The qualitative research provided more detailed and in-depth understanding of the phenomenon under investigation, and by combining the two research methods, I benefited from the strengths of both.

Cohen, Manion and Morrison (2018) highlight the discussion of whether or not to start the qualitative research with an initial hypothesis and in this regard, two points of view emerged. The first argument claims that the nature of positivist approach is based on testing a predetermined hypothesis unlike in qualitative approaches where the nature of research is more open and emergent. The second point of view tends to support the argument that claims “researchers should deliberately free themselves from all prior knowledge” (Glaser and Strauss 1967 as cited in Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018, p.291), adding that “theory is the end point of the research, not its starting point” (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018, p.291). As a suggestion to this debate, eliminating the commencement of qualitative research with a hypothesis and the fact that every research starts with a previous knowledge or theory, which contribute to undertaking the research, a number of solutions is proposed (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018). This includes:

1. An openness to data;
2. A preparedness to modify one’s initial pre-suppositions and position;
3. A declaration of the extent to which the researcher’s prior knowledge may be influencing the research (i.e. reflexivity);

4. A recognition of the tentative nature of one's hypothesis;
5. A willingness to use the research to generate a hypothesis; and
6. An acknowledgment that having a hypothesis may be just as much a part of qualitative research as it is of quantitative research (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018, p.291).

In this light, Merriam (2009) asserts that qualitative research does not aim at testing hypotheses or theories but rather tends to build theories inductively.

Cope (2014) refers to Lincoln and Guba (1985) who propose the key trustworthiness criteria used to evaluate qualitative research as discussed below.

Credibility, which denotes the truth-value, is concerned with the researcher's ability to demonstrate confidence in their findings (Anney, 2014).

The second criterion is dependability, it is concerned with consistency, in other words, "how can one know if the findings would be repeated consistently with the similar (same) participants in the same context?" (Anney, 2014, p.6).

Furthermore, the third criterion is confirmability, which can be achieved through the use of the participants' own words in order to prove that the data is derived from their perspectives and not the researcher's (Cope, 2014).

Transferability on the other hand is a key criterion of qualitative data evaluation, which refers to applicability (Anney, 2014) and is achieved when "the results have meaning to individuals not involved in the study and readers can associate the results with their own experiences" (Cope, 2014, p.89).

To these four criteria, later in 1994, Guba and Lincoln added authenticity.

Authenticity refers to faithfulness in reporting data, which can be exhibited in the participants' voices in their own words (Cope, 2014).

4.8. Research Tools

Since the study used mixed methods research, questionnaires and interviews were selected as research tools to help answering the proposed research questions. The reason of choosing these two tools over the others is because they match better the selected sample and the research questions. For instance, it is not possible to choose participant observation, field notes, focus

groups, experiments or artefact analysis as data sources since the participants graduated from university and SI modules were based on verbal practice in the classroom instead of written documents. Accordingly, I conducted semi-structured interviews and surveys since they were the most convenient methods of data collection to provide answers to the research questions.

Adam and Cox (2008) argue that questionnaires can take the form of paper or online questionnaires in which a series of questions is given and participants are required to answer all of them. This enables the questionnaires to reach a large sample with minimum effort, yet it is important to note that this also means receiving a considerable amount of data to code and analyse (Adams and Cox, 2008). On the other hand, concerning interviews, the most common type of interviews is one-to-one interviewing which despite its various advantages could be time consuming and similar to questionnaires, transcribing and coding the data is time consuming (Adams and Cox, 2008). Each method will be discussed in details in the following sections with justifying the preference of selecting it over the other existing methods.

4.8.1. Questionnaires

Questionnaires were the first method of data collection in this study and were administrated electronically in order to obtain preliminary data that would be useful for framing the interview questions. Unlike other methods of data collection that might be costly, complicated or time consuming, questionnaires on the contrast are a good method if the researcher intends to get responses from a large sample, they are cheap, reliable and straightforward (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018). The main purposes of using questionnaires in this research are first to explore in general students' awareness of Arabic diglossia, and second to investigate how they perceive its impact on their performance in SI. Obtaining numerical data from questionnaires provided an overview of how students perceive Arabic diglossia and were supported later with interviews to get qualitative data that in return allowed the former students to discuss in depth their own insights, provide their personal opinions on the pedagogy of SI and therefore helped answering the proposed research questions. As Adams and Cox (2008) put it, with regard to what the researcher aims to find, it is convenient to begin the data collection with questionnaires to get preliminary data and then use experiments or interviews to get a better understanding of the phenomenon under investigation. The questionnaires were completed by a group of twenty-one alumni students of SI who studied at the University of Ouargla in Algeria.

4.8.1.1. Types of Questionnaires

Among the various types of questionnaires, the broad classification incorporates structured, semi-structured and unstructured questionnaires, if the sample is very large, structured, closed and numerical questionnaires are more likely to be used whereas if the sample is small, it is better to use structured and open questionnaires (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018). Unstructured questionnaires refer to the type of questionnaires in which the questions used invite the respondents to write their own answers while structured questionnaires are completely closed. However, semi-structured questionnaires, fall between the two types mentioned above denoting the case where “a series of questions, statements or items are presented and the respondents are asked to answer, respond to or comment on them as they wish” (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018, p.475). In this type, the questionnaire still follows a certain protocol yet the use of open-ended questions provides the respondents with more freedom and flexibility to express their insights.

Furthermore, the type of questions asked in the questionnaire also can vary and falls into two broad categories as Cohen, Manion and Morrison (2018) explain:

- Open-ended questions: are a useful option to use when looking for personal information and when used in accordance with ticking boxes, a space or a line is often provided to give the respondent the chance to write comments. This type of questions is suitable for smaller scale research. At the same time, they give the respondent a hint about what information is needed which results in generating rich, deep and honest responses. However, open-ended questions can be time consuming for both parts, the participant and the researcher. For the participants, they can be time consuming in terms of taking the time to think and write an answer and the possibility of providing irrelevant data whereas for the researcher by finding it difficult to code the data, thus they will be “quantitizing qualitative data” (p.475).
- Closed questions: provide an array of options and the respondent is required to choose the most suitable option among them. In contrast to open-ended questions, closed questions are easy to code, they do not require much time to complete but their high structure restricts the respondents and do not give them the opportunity to add their own notes.

Gibbs (2012) gives a more detailed explanation of the differences between the two types that is displayed on the table below:

Open questions	Close questions
More representative of respondent's true opinions	Very easy to score and analyse
Less open to researcher's bias	Give predictable outcomes
Useful to indicate points of interest or weaknesses	Useful for statistical illustrations or summaries

Table 5: Open or closed questions? (Gibbs, 2012, 26:37)

However, Cohen, Manion and Morrison (2018, p.475) highlight six further types of questionnaire questions: dichotomous questions; multiple-choice questions; rating scales; constant sum questions; ratio data; and open-ended questions.

Semi-structured questionnaires were used in this study incorporating a mixture of open-ended and close-ended questions to generate data about the participants' experience in the field of SI (see appendix D on page 229).

4.8.1.2. Strengths and Weaknesses of Questionnaires

4.8.1.2.1. Strengths of Questionnaires

Robson and McCartan (2016) highlight some advantages of questionnaire-based surveys classified into three main categories depending on the survey type: surveys using respondents; postal, internet and self-administrated surveys; and internet surveys as will be explained below.

The strengths of the first type are general and valid for all surveys using respondents. They encompass offering a better understanding when studying attitudes, beliefs, values and motives; data obtained from them can be generalizable and can be gained through any proportion from the society; and information gained from questionnaire-based surveys can be standardized (Robson and McCartan, 2016, p.248).

However, the focus will be on the strengths related to internet surveys since they are the type of surveys used in this study. In this respect, Mertens (2005) suggest five advantages of using internet surveys:

1. In terms of expenses, internet surveys are very low in cost and when participants are scattered across different geographical areas, this will not be a setback to take into consideration.
2. Internet surveys are a fast method of data collection.
3. Surveys completed through websites reduce the confusion occurring in paper-based questionnaires.
4. Website based surveys can offer a wide range of visual aids.
5. People with disabilities are able to complete internet surveys due to the technological advancement that website based surveys are witnessing (as cited in Robson and McCartan, 2016, pp.255-256)

4.8.1.2.2. Weaknesses of Questionnaires

Robson and McCartan (2016) give general disadvantages occurring in all surveys using respondents: the data retrieved depends to a wide extent on the personal features of the respondents such as their own experiences, motivation, personality etc. Furthermore, information gained from questionnaire-based surveys may not necessarily be accurate as people are more likely to hide their weaknesses (Robson and McCartan, 2016).

Internet surveys more specifically have seven weaknesses as Robson and McCartan (2016) pinpoint:

1. When using internet surveys, people who do not have access to the internet may not be reached. Hence, internet surveys are restricted to the population who has access to the internet.
2. The second disadvantage also concerns people lacking technology skills or advanced devices resulting in increasing response bias rates.
3. The researcher may encounter setbacks related to sampling as probability sampling can only be used where there are adequate lists.
4. Unlike paper-based questionnaires, in which people receive the same printed-paper, in online questionnaires, many factors can make the questionnaires look different from one another such as the screen size, the browser, internet speed etc.
5. The longer the questionnaires are the more non-responses and non-completion will occur. Thus, they need to be as short as possible.

6. In questionnaires, there is no chance for the researcher to interfere when necessary to provide further explanations and clarifications. Yet, the researcher can overcome this issue by providing an email or links to be used whenever required.
7. The researcher cannot govern the way in which the questionnaires are completed in terms of following the question order and the place, nor can they know if the questionnaire is completed by the respondent per se or by a group.

However, in order to mitigate these weaknesses, I tried to make the survey questions as straightforward as possible and I avoided designing a long survey in order to ensure a high response rate. Furthermore, I avoided asking complex questions to avoid ambiguity. The surveys were not the main data collection method; they were followed up by in-depth interviews to gain a detailed understanding. I used questionnaires because first, I was hoping to get some general information and second because I was hoping to get answers that would help me develop the interview questions.

4.8.2. Interviews

Interviews are among the foremost vital and commonly used tools to obtain case study data and can take the form of directed discussions instead of controlled questions (Yin, 2014).

Denscombe (2014, p.186) highlights that in contexts of low-budget small-scale research the time and effort saved when using interviews are worth it especially when the area under investigation is complex and the researcher is looking for opinions, feelings, emotions and experiences, privileged information and dealing with complex issues. This study aims to explore the attitudes of SI students in-depth according to their own experiences in a field as complex as SI and accordingly get a detailed understanding of the phenomenon under investigation. Therefore, interviews were used to get qualitative data.

Yin (2014) points out three types of case study interviews: prolonged interviews, shorter interviews, and survey interviews. Prolonged case study interviews, as the name suggests, could last for two hours or more and consequently it is possible to split the interview into more than one setting. The second type is shorter interviews that in general may take approximately an hour, still involving an open-ended type of questions yet following to some extent the procedure of the case study. Survey interviews is the third type that Yin (2014) suggests referring to the use of a structured questionnaire, which will provide quantitative data.

The traditional type of interview denotes a situation in which the interviewer sits in front of the interviewee, in the case of individual interviewing, or facing a group of respondents in the case of group interviewing (King, Horrocks, and Brooks, 2018). However, interview types moved from this narrowed traditional definition to encompass cases where the parts of the interview do not necessarily have to be in the same location during the interview as will be discussed below.

Remote interviewing consists of telephone interviewing and online interviewing and it is used to obtain two distinct types of data: written or spoken data (King, Horrocks, and Brooks, 2018). Furthermore, time scale characterizes the type of remote interviewing as well, splitting it into two categories: synchronous, in which interaction takes place instantly such as telephone interviews, and non-synchronous or asynchronous like email interviews where no instant exchange occurs (King, Horrocks, and Brooks, 2018). In this respect, and in terms of depth and reflexivity, Hewson (2007) writes “a further possible advantage of online interviews, particularly in asynchronous contexts, is the scope for eliciting deeper, more reflective, detailed and accurate responses” (p.411). However, in this study I used synchronous remote interviewing in order to allow the interviewees to request clarifications when needed and therefore get the data that answers my research questions. Furthermore, since the interviews took place online, it was better to use synchronous interviewing to ease interaction and communication. Another reason for choosing synchronous interviewing is that it enables the researcher to ask follow-up questions especially when I used semi-structured interviews.

4.8.2.1. Types of Interviews

Interviews can be classified according to various criteria. The core classification, which is frequently used, is based on the interview structure: fully structured interviews, semi-structured interviews and unstructured interviews (Robson and McCarter, 2016, pp.285-6). The three types are explained in the table below:

Highly Standardized	Structured/	Semi-structured	Unstructured/ Informal
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<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wording of questions is predetermined • Order of questions is predetermined • Interview is oral form of a written survey • In qualitative studies, usually used to obtain demographic data (age, gender, ethnicity, education, etc.) • Examples: U.S. Census Bureau survey, marketing surveys. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interview guide includes a mix of more and less structured interview questions • All questions used flexibly • Usually specific data required from all respondents • Largest part of interview guided by list of questions or issues to be explored • No predetermined wording or order 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open-ended questions • Flexible, exploratory • More like a conversation • Used when researcher does not know enough about phenomenon to ask relevant questions • Goal is learning from this interview to formulate questions for later interviews • Used primarily in ethnography, participant observation, and case study
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Table 6: Interview structure continuum (Merriam, 2009 p.89)

Rubin and Rubin (2011) explain further that “in the semi-structured interview, the researcher has a specific topic to learn about, prepares a limited number of questions in advance, and plans to ask follow-up questions” (p.31). On the other hand, in unstructured interviews, the interview can take the form of an informal conversation (Robson and McCarter, 2016). Semi-structured and unstructured interviews can also be called qualitative interviews, depth interviews or in-depth interviews, and focused interviews (Robson and McCarter, 2016, p.286).

In addition to the three types that Merriam (2009) enumerates, Cohen, Manion, and Morrison (2018) add two more types: the non-directive interview and the focused interview. In the non-directive interview, the interviewer does not control the interviewee, which consequently results in more freedom of expression given to the latter. In this type of interviews, the interviewer interferes when necessary to rephrase, summarise or to make sure they clearly understood what the interviewee stated. The second type of interviews is characterized by pre-interview analysis done by the interviewer in which the interviewee is exposed to a familiar situation and then asked to provide subjective responses.

Furthermore, Denscombe (2014) explains a crucial feature of semi-structured interviews, which is despite the fact that the interviewer prepares the interview questions beforehand, there is always an extent of flexibility that allows the interviewer to reorder the topics which in turn enables the interviewees to express their thoughts widely. In addition to that, in semi-structured interviews, the interviewer can make some changes at the level of the interview and develop it based on the information obtained from the previous interviews (Denscombe, 2014).

The main research tool used in this study is semi-structured interviews following Yin's view (2003) claiming that it fits better in the exploratory case study.

King, Horrocks, and Brooks (2018, p117) argue that "whatever interview approach is selected will depend upon what is best suited to the particular research project". (Denscombe, 2014) emphasises that "the use of interviews in small-scale research tends to involve the use of semi-structured interviews to investigate attitudes and issues in detail, and is generally used as part of qualitative research", p.186).

Furthermore, I aim to gather in depth data and meanwhile allowing the interviewees to express their thoughts more freely benefiting from the various advantages of semi-structured interviews. It is to be noted that questionnaires were used as a research instrument prior to conducting interviews in order to guide me when selecting the interviewees depending on the data the informants provided in the questionnaires.

4.8.2.2. Strengths and Weaknesses of Interviews

4.8.2.2.1. Strengths of Interviews

Denscombe (2014) highlights eight advantages of using interviews, which could be classified as follows:

1. Interviews allow the researcher to gain in-depth data that the topic under investigation requires.
2. The researcher can benefit from the participant's knowledge and insights gained from the in-depth data.
3. In terms of equipment, no sophisticated equipment is needed, only a digital recorder, computer and internet connection.

4. Unlike other methods of research, the flow of thoughts present in the interviews allows the informants to express themselves broadly.
5. In the two types of interviewing: structured and semi-structured interviews, there is a degree of flexibility that enables adjustments and changes to be made throughout the interview resulting in spontaneity of the process.
6. Given the fact that the place and the time where the interview is going to take place are planned beforehand, increases the high response rate.
7. Whether it is a face-to-face or a Skype interview, the personal contact between the two parts of the interview that is audio recorded, decreases the possibility of mishearing what has been uttered and therefore eliminates any kind of misinterpretations.
8. Interviews are considered therapeutic in the sense that they provide the respondents with the chance to sit and discuss their thoughts and perceptions with a person who is interested in and actively listening to what they are saying without being judged (Denscombe, 2014, pp. 201-2).

To these advantages, Oppenheim (2000) adds that interviewers “can give a prepared explanation of the purpose of the study more convincingly than a covering letter can; will more easily reach less well-educated respondents; help the ones with reading difficulties; offer standardized explanations to certain problems that arise... ” (pp. 81-82). In addition to that, Yin (2014, p.106) enumerates two further reasons to choose interviews as a qualitative research tool, which are: a) targeted, interviews shed light mainly on case study topics under investigation; and b) insightful, that is to say they supply the researcher with people’s personal attitudes, views and perceptions. Interviews are appropriate as a data collection instrument for this specific topic because they provide in-depth data on the perceptions and attitudes of the participants of this study.

4.8.2.2.2. Weaknesses of Interviews

Despite the advantages of interviews that are cited above, interviews have also disadvantages that need to be addressed. Among the disadvantages of interviews Denscombe (2014) pinpoints:

1. There might not be a match between people’s way of thinking; what they say and how they behave, which results in a degree of inaccuracy in their responses.

2. The background of the interviewer may have an impact on the respondents, yet this disadvantage may be reduced in online interviewing.
3. In structured and semi-structured interviews where the researcher is flexible in terms of question order and other factors, there might not be a consistency among all the interviews, thus the information may depend more or less on the context and the individual.
4. Another disadvantage concerns the data obtained from structured and semi-structured interviews, which has an open format resulting in making transcribing and coding time consuming.
5. The fifth drawback lies in travel costs and the time that the researcher wastes in face-to-face interviewing that increases in cases where the participants are in different geographical areas and the researcher has to travel in order to interview them.
6. Also in face-to-face interviews, the fact that the recording equipment is right in front of the respondent may act like an inhibition even though once the interview starts, the respondents may forget about this device. This issue concerns only this type of interviewing excluding online interviews.
7. Finally yet importantly, in cases where the interviewer shows a lack of interviewing skills and does not carefully choose the right words, informants may feel uncomfortable and may perceive the interview as an invasion to their privacy (pp. 202-3).

In this respect, Yin (2014, p.106) also proposes four weaknesses of using interviews that are: a) bias resulting from the lack of good question utterance, b) bias when responding, c) mistakes caused by poor recall and d) informants oriented to and say what they think the interviewer wants to hear. In this study, these were the anticipated weaknesses of using interviews. However, as a researcher I made sure they were mitigated by choosing the right wording of the interview questions to avoid any possible bias and it was made clear to the interviewees that there are no right or wrong answers, they were rather encouraged to express themselves freely and ask for clarifications whenever needed.

4.8.2.3. Remote Interviewing

There are various forms of remote interviewing; King, Horrocks and Brooks (2018, p.115) mention four major forms: telephone, remote video (video-conferencing and webcams), emails and instant messaging.

Online interviewing as (Cohen, Manion and Morrison 2018) refer to it could take the form of

- Text-based only like emails, chat rooms, blogs etc.
- A combination of text and visuals like instant messaging
- Audio only e.g. WhatsApp
- Both audio and visual interviews like Skype (Cohen, Manion, and Morrison, 2018, p.538).

All the aforementioned types of online interviewing require special requirements that vary according to the kind of interviewing chosen such as internet access, smartphone or relevant equipment or hardware and competence in using the appropriate software (Cohen, Manion, and Morrison, 2018).

King, Horrocks, and Brooks (2018) highlight three major reasons for using remote interviewing: a) physical distance from participants; b) availability of participants; and c) the nature of the interview topic (p.115). It is clear that all of the three features are encountered in this study, among others, therefore remote interviewing was selected as a data collection method in this study.

4.8.2.3.1. The Advantages of Online Interviewing

Among the various advantages of online interviewing, time and location of the interview are not problem to consider, as there is flexibility of agreement concerning when and where the interview is going to be conducted (Cohen, Manion, and Morrison, 2018). In addition to that, in situations where the participants are hard to reach due to either geographical restrictions or availability purposes, remote interviewing helps to minimise travel expenses and time consumption (King, Horrocks, and Brooks, 2018). Hewson (2007) comments on these advantages by stating that they facilitate participation “from, and interaction amongst, respondents across different geographical regions and time zones” (p.413).

4.8.2.3.2. The Disadvantages of Online Interviewing

One of the major problems that researchers using online interviewing might encounter is technological problems: slow internet connection or unstable connectivity. However all these possible problems that might occur should be checked before the start of the interview (Cohen, Manion, and Morrison, 2018).

4.8.2.4. Skype Interviewing

Skype interviewing is “an instant, face-to-face audio-visual method” (Cohen, Manion, and Morrison, 2018, p.540). Cohen, Manion, and Morrison (2018) note that the advantages and disadvantages of Skype interviewing are the same as the advantages and disadvantages of face-to-face interviewing in terms of deciding the time of the interview and the difficulty to know if there are any other parties present in the location other than the interviewer and the interviewee. Denscombe (2014) shares the same argument and adds that costs and difficulties of travelling are associated only with face-to-face interviewing.

Consequently, for the stated reasons, and many others, and due to the constraints that prevent the researcher from conducting face-to-face interviews with the participants, such as the availability of the interviewees; geographical dispersion, as the participants are scattered all around the country; and the difficulties to reach the participants, Skype one-to-one semi-structured interviews were used in this study.

4.8.2.4.1. Advantages of Skype Interviewing

Furthermore, Seitz (2015) highlights another advantage of Skype interviews, which makes them “more beneficial to participants who are shy or introverted, allowing them to feel more comfortable opening up in front of a screen” (as cited in Lo Iacono, Symonds and Brown, 2016, p.11). This is also applied to researchers who are shy, introvert, and may not feel at ease when interviewing people with whom they have a limited relationship. Novick (2008) also emphasises that “researchers may feel awkward when interacting with participants in person...interviewers need to develop strategies to feel comfortable, put participants at ease, and develop rapport” (as cited in Lo Iacono, Symonds and Brown, 2016, p.11).

The point that Seitz (2015) discusses contributes to encouraging the participants to take part in the study especially when they are given the opportunity to choose the time of the interview that suits them best, which is clearly highlighted in the participant information sheet sent to them beforehand.

In comparison to face-to-face interviews, Skype interviews involving “video footage of both the interviewer and the participant can be recorded very easily, (...) without the need to set up additional cameras (...). This way, the body language and interactions can also be analysed during annotation” (Lo Iacono, Symonds and Brown, 2016, pp.13-14). Moreover, the researchers claim “Skype allows people not to look at someone in the eye during an interview,

might actually be an advantage in helping shy people to open up” (Lo Iacono, Symonds and Brown, 2016, p.12).

4.8.2.4.2. Disadvantages of Skype interviewing

Skype interviewing has a number of disadvantages despite its fast widespread nowadays. In this regard, Lo Iacono, Symonds and Brown (2016) assert that not everybody has access to the internet, and able to use technology especially elderly, however in this study the participants were young graduate students who are familiar with technology.

Another limitation of using Skype online interviews is the difficulty of rapport building (Lo Iacono, Symonds and Brown, 2016). Rapport refers to “trust – enabling the participant to feel comfortable in opening up to you” (King, Horrocks, and Brooks, 2018, p.77). They highlight that building rapport leads to a successful interviewing. However, in Skype interviewing it may not be easily achieved. Nevertheless, in this study, the fact that the participants are my former colleagues increased the chance of building rapport over Skype.

Furthermore, Seitz (2016, pp.230-4) argues that various obstacles may arise during Skype interviews as listed below:

The first limitation is dropped calls and pauses, technical problems may happen at any time throughout the call and cause interruption, which affects the interview flow. As a suggestion to avoid this issue, technological preparation done by the interviewer as well as the participants could be helpful. Checking the internet connection before the interview takes place and ensuring the device is fully charged are also useful strategies.

The second limitation involves inaudible segments, sometimes the interviewer may experience difficulties hearing the participant, and thus, participants are encouraged to choose an appropriate and a quiet location and if necessary, the interviewer can ask the participants to slow down and speak clearly.

The third disadvantage is the inability to read body language and nonverbal cues even when the cameras are on.

The last limitation discusses the loss of intimacy compared to traditional in-person interviews. Highlighting that “the quality of a Skype interview is indeed affected by the research topic, aim, and interview questions. More personal questions may pose more difficulty over Skype due to the loss of personal connection and intimacy compared to in-person interviews.” (2016,

p.332) rather than the nature of the interview. However, in the course of this research, I did not encounter this issue as both the topic of the research and the interview questions were not sensitive. The ethical consideration of internet mediated research are discussed further in section 4.14.4.

4.9. Procedures

Creswell (2017) proposes four features manipulating the design of procedures of mixed methods that are explained as follows:

Timing: as mentioned in the definition of mixed methods proposed by Creswell et al (2003), the timing and phases of data collection are important. In this respect, similarly Creswell (2017) pinpoints two different types of data collection: either quantitative and qualitative are collected in parallel or one collected before the other. Thus, the data is collected concurrently or sequentially respectively. In the first type, some situations urge the researcher to visit the field to collect the data simultaneously. However, in the second type, if qualitative data is collected first, the researcher investigates the topic in the field with the participants and then uses quantitative method to widen the sample (Creswell, 2017). In this research, quantitative data was collected first, thus questionnaires were distributed to a larger group in order to obtain preliminary data and then interviews were conducted with a smaller number of participants.

Weighting: Creswell (2017) discusses weight or priority given to quantitative or qualitative method whether it is equal or one is given more importance in terms of design of procedures in mixed method data collection. In this study, the emphasis was on the qualitative method as it provides in-depth data whereas the quantitative method was used to obtain initial data to help frame the interview questions.

Mixing, as a third factor, Creswell (2017) tackles mixing with its three cases: connecting, integrating and embedding. Connecting in this context denotes “a mixing of the quantitative and qualitative research are connected between a data analysis of the first phase of research and the data collection of the second phase of research” (Creswell, 2017, p.208). That is to say, there is a connection between the two phases of data collection although they are separate for instance the results of one method collected in one stage helps in deciding the participants and the process of the next stage of data collection. On the other hand, integrating occurs when the two data are collected in parallel and integrated. The third case is embedding, this occurs when

the researcher uses one method as complementary to the other. In this situation the “researcher is embedding a secondary form of data within a larger study having a different form of data as the primary database. The secondary database provides a supporting role in the study” (Creswell, 2017, p.208).

Theorizing: Creswell (2017) writes in this regard “in mixed methods studies, the theories are found typically in the beginning sections as an orienting lens that shapes the types of questions asked, who participates in the study, how data are collected, and the implications made from the study (typically for change and advocacy)” (p.208).

4.10. Case Study

This section provides definitions of case studies although definitions are controversial and changing considerably over time. Then I will address the different types of case studies along with the strengths and weaknesses of this research strategy including validity, reliability, and ethics. I will conclude by stating when it is appropriate to use this strategy.

Yin (2014, p.4) states that case studies enable “investigators to focus on a case and retain a holistic and real-world perspective such as in studying individual cycles, small group behaviour, organizational and managerial processes, neighbourhood change, school performance, international relations and the maturation of industries”.

It is important to mention that case studies are used across various disciplines such as psychology, sociology, political science, anthropology, social work, business, education, nursing and community planning (Yin, 2014). Before diving into precised definition of case studies, Cohen, Manion and Morrison (2018) claim that any study conducted in the field of social science is a case study. Yet many attempts have been made in the past to provide an insight to case study, to mention but a few, Merriam (2009) notes that in the 1980’s some scholars referred to case study as a methodology such as Stake (1988), Yin (1984) and Merriam (1988). However, twelve years later Wolcott (1992) perceived case study as “an end-product of field-oriented research” (as cited in Merriam, 2009, p.40).

On the other hand, (Robson, 1993, p.146) asserts that case study is “a strategy for doing research which involves an empirical investigation of a particular contemporary phenomenon within its real life context using multiple sources of evidence”. Nevertheless, Graham R Gibbs (2012) comments on this definition by claiming that in some cases, case study does not involve

one particular case, it could be several cases and phenomenon can be a person or social phenomena such as places, events, organisations, etc. Graham R Gibbs (2012) continues to explain Robson's definition, by contemporary we mean it is not a historical approach and it is happening in real life not in the lab, as contrast to experiments where the researcher brings people as volunteers to participate in their experiment. Case studies are very common in the qualitative field, linked mainly with various qualitative approaches such as interviews and observations whereas it can be other sources as well like documents for instance (Graham R Gibbs, 2012). Yin (2008, p.18) shares Robson's view and envisages case study as an empirical enquiry that explores a contemporary phenomenon and adds "especially when the boundaries between phenomenon and context are not clearly evident".

Later, Yin (2009, p.13) suggests a more enlightening definition of case study and perceives it as "a research strategy comprises an all-encompassing method-with the logic of design incorporating specific approaches to data collection and to data analysis". However, it is remarkable that in Yin's later publications the definition of case study changed considerably from referring to it as strategy to a method stating that "as a research method, the case study is used in many situations, to contribute to our knowledge of individual, group, organizational, social political and related phenomena" (Yin, 2014, p.4). Conversely, Thomas (2021, p.9) has an opposite point of view claiming that "the case study is not a method in itself". Others perceive case study as an approach "qualitative case study is an approach to research that facilitates exploration of a phenomenon within its context using a variety of data sources" (Baxter and Jack, 2008, p.544).

On the other hand, Denscombe (2014) perceives case study as an approach that enables the use of a variety of methods dictated by the situation. Furthermore, Denscombe (2014) goes on to affirm that in order for a study to be classified as case study, it has to have an end-point, outside and limits otherwise it would fit in any other social phenomena and therefore will not be a case.

4.10.1. When to Use Case Studies?

Denscombe (2014, p.56) claims that case study approach provides rich data by enabling the researcher to "delve deep into the intricacies of the situation".

Yin (2014) points out that research questions monitor the choice of the method used, thus if the investigator attempts to answer contemporary questions like how and why related to social phenomenon, requiring in-depth description, case study method is a good choice. In addition

to that, the choice of the method is determined by “the extent of control a researcher has over actual behavioural events” and “the degree of focus on contemporary as opposed to entirely historical events” (Yin, 2014, p.9).

Following these arguments, it is appropriate to use a mixed methods approach in this research since it aims to investigate how Arabic diglossia affects my participants’ perceptions of the pedagogy of SI in Algeria, which entails the need for in-depth data.

Method	(1) Form of Research Question	(2) Requires Control of Behavioural Events?	(3) Focuses on Contemporary Events?
Experiment	How, why?	Yes	Yes
Survey	Who, what, where, how many, how much?	No	Yes
Archival Analysis	Who, what, where, how many, how much?	No	Yes/ no
History	How, why?	No	No
Case Study	How, why?	No	Yes

Table 7: Relevant situations for different research methods (Yin, 2014, p. 9)

The reason for favouring the use of case study method over other methods such as experiment, survey archival analysis or history is determined by the focus of the study, although either of the abovementioned methods can fit in the exploratory research, and the type of research questions that do not include how and why questions (Yin, 2014). Furthermore, the questions of this research focus mainly on “what” questions; this classifies the research into two categories as Yin (2014) claims, either exploratory, or “how many”, or “how much” line of enquiry. The first classification implies the use of exploratory research, which tends to develop pertinent hypotheses and propositions for further research to be undertaken. On the other hand, the second classification suggests the use of surveys or archival methods that tend to be more convenient than other methods (Yin, 2014). In spite of the claim that Yin (2014, p.11) makes emphasizing that “the form of the question can provide an important clue regarding the appropriate research method to be used”, Yin (2014) also notes that in some cases the decision of the research method could be made without being governed by the research question.

Consequently, as this study is exploratory by nature, and since case study is more suitable for an exploratory type of research and “what” questions, I used case study method in this study.

As Yin (2014, p.11) puts it “what questions may either be exploratory (in which case, any of the methods could be used) or about prevalence (in which surveys or the analysis of archival records could be favoured”.

The second and the third criteria, that Yin (2014) suggests, provide guidance on how to select the relevant method, besides the type of research questions asked, are concerned with the distinction between a history, case study and experiment. The history method tends to be used when it is impossible for direct observations to take place and the only available source of evidence is primary, secondary documents, cultural and physical artefacts. On the other hand, in contrast to historical studies, the case study implies the examination of present events where there is no manipulation of events as the above table shows. In addition to the techniques used in historical studies, case studies have the advantage of using direct observations and interviews. Experiments generally take place in labs, which allows the investigator to manipulate behaviours. However, there are cases where the investigator cannot control behaviours, which are known as quasi-experimental situations or observational studies (Yin, 2014).

4.10.2. Types of Case Studies

Types of case studies could involve individual case study, set of individual case studies, community studies, social group studies, studies of organisations and institutions, studies of events and roles and relationships. Dawson and Algozzine (2011) note three main types of case study research designs: exploratory, explanatory and descriptive.

4.10.3. Strengths and weaknesses of Case Studies

4.10.3.1. Strengths of Case Studies

Among the strengths of case studies, “the flexibility to incorporate multiple perspectives, data collection tools, and interpretive strategies” (Marshall and Rossman, 2014, p. 19).

Denscombe (2014, p.63) lists five advantages of using case studies. First, case studies are convenient for small-scale research. Second, they allow the researcher to take a holistic view, which, in return provides an in depth understanding of complex social phenomena. Third, case study approach facilitates the integration of multiple methods because it seizes complex areas. Furthermore, in situations where the research does not necessitate the researcher’s control of the variables, case study approach is convenient as it fits into naturally occurring settings. The

fifth advantage is that case study is a flexible approach as “theory-building and theory-testing research can both use the case study approach to good effect” (p.63).

4.10.3.2. Weaknesses of Case Studies

Yin (2009) notes three main prejudices surrounding case studies including: a) bias in case study strategy; b) the difficulty of providing generalization and c) the length of time in case studies. These prejudices are explained in more details below.

Concerning the first point, bias is not likely to occur only in case studies, other research strategies like experiments, questionnaire and surveys can also be subjected to bias. To avoid this, the investigator should ensure that data is reported fairly (Yin, 2009). The second issue arising from using a case study strategy lies in whether it is possible to generalise the findings, in this respect Yin (2009, p.10) compares between case studies and experiments and writes

Case studies, like experiments, are generalizable to theoretical propositions and not to populations or universes. In this sense, the case study, like the experiment, does not represent a "sample," and the investigator's goal is to expand and generalize theories (analytic generalization) and not to enumerate frequencies (statistical generalization).

Finally yet importantly, Yin (2009, p.11) adds “case studies are a form of inquiry that does not depend solely on ethnographic or participant-observer data. One could even do a valid and high-quality case study without leaving the library and the telephone, depending upon the topic being studied”. In other words, time is not a setback when using a case study strategy as it is when choosing other methods of data collection (Yin, 2009). Consistent with Yin’s point of view, Qi (2010) mentions the lack of generality and reliability of results and bias due to investigator’s high exposure to the research as weaknesses of case studies. Similarly, Thomas (2015) pinpoints the lack of generality when using case studies supporting his argument by claiming that case studies are concerned with the particular instead of the general.

In accordance to the above discussion, Denscombe (2014) also agrees that case study approach is mostly criticised for the credibility of generalisations, and to this limitation, he adds that it is difficult to determine the boundaries to the case, which makes the decision-making of the sources of data incorporated in the case study hard. Another limitation is related to gaining access to case study settings, which can be challenging. The last weakness of using case studies is that “case studies are sometimes regarded as acceptable in terms of providing descriptive accounts of the situation but rather ill-suited to analyses or evaluations” (p.64).

However, the results of this study cannot be over-generalised and they need to be used with care as I have done in my conclusion and summary. Following this, I strived to ensure that the data has been reported fairly. I was not trying to generalise this to the entire Arabic speaking world, I was referring to the Algerian context and to one cohort.

4.11. Data Analysis

This study aims to explore the potential implications of Arabic diglossia on my participants' perceptions of the pedagogy of simultaneous interpreting (SI); in particular, the difficulties that students of SI may experience when interpreting simultaneously from a non-L1 to a non-L1, that is to say MSA-English-MSA.

This research project adopted mixed methods for data collection in order to increase the validity of the findings. By using mixed methods the researcher benefits from the strengths of both qualitative and quantitative methods and therefore the weaknesses of both are minimised (Denscombe, 2014).

Overall, in this study, quantitative methodology was used as a complementary method, as the emphasis is on the qualitative methodology. Therefore, data collection underwent two phases.

The first phase involved an administrated online survey in January, in which twenty-one participants took part. The questionnaire had nine close-ended questions and one sub open-ended question, at the end of the questionnaire, the respondents were invited to participate in a Skype interview and were asked to provide their contact details if they wish to take part. Sixteen respondents out of twenty-one agreed to participate. However, when those who showed willingness to take part in the online interview were contacted, only five of them (three males and two females) were still interested and therefore participated in the online semi-structured interviews. The five interview participants were given the names IP1, IP2, IP3, IP4 and IP5. IP1 and IP3 are both females and they work as teachers of English whereas the other three participants are males. IP3 works as a tramway senior manager, IP4 works as a teacher of English and IP5 is a chef personnel.

Braun and Clarke's (2006) six stages to conducting thematic analysis were used in the qualitative interview analysis, thus the analysis underwent six phases: familiarizing yourself with your data, generating initial codes, searching for themes, reviewing themes, defining and naming themes and producing the report (Braun and Clarke, 2006, p.87). In chapter 5, extracts from the participants are quoted, deliberately unedited in order to maintain their voices and to

provide a precise and accurate presentation of their perceptions of the phenomenon under investigation.

Creswell and Plano Clark (2011) emphasise that the research problem needs to be studied through more than one type of method and with the use of various data sources in order to enhance the understanding of the phenomenon under study and best address the research problems. In this study, collecting data through questionnaires provided an overview of the participants' attitudes towards the topic under investigation and helped in building up and editing the interviews. Furthermore, the use of mixed methods "answers complex research questions more meaningfully" (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018, p.33). Linguistic deficiencies in both languages involved in a task as complex as SI could be very problematic, thus combining quantitative and qualitative data helps gain insight into the participants' experiences.

Qualitative data analysis implies describing, understanding, explaining and interpreting the data obtained from participants and making sense of it, it is "an ongoing process that takes place during the research as well as at the end of it" (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018, p.644). It is to be noted that qualitative data analysis is not subjected to only one way of analysis, yet it is open to various interpretations, furthermore among the fundamental features of qualitative data analysis, is the possibility of stages overlap: analysis and interpretation which is more likely to happen (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018). Gibbs (2018) highlights the advantages of merging data collection and data analysis, when doing so, the researcher can benefit from the analysis of the preliminary data to improve the research questions and take into consideration new issues that may arise throughout the process.

As opposite to quantitative data that entails numbers and statistics, qualitative data incorporates a wide range of human communication to mention but a few: interviews and their transcripts, participant observation, emails and online conversations, diaries, films, websites etc. (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018; Gibbs, 2018).

Qualitative data analysis incorporates various phases: data reduction (to minimise voluminous data); data display; data analysis and interpretation; drawing and verifying conclusions; and reporting the analysis and findings (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018, p.643). They continue to explain that data reduction does not entail eliminating data but rather focusing on the key elements (Gläser and Laudel, 2013, as cited in Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018, p.643). As

opposite to this argument, Gibbs (2018, no pagination) points out that what characterizes qualitative data analysis is “expanding the volume of data not reducing it”; moreover, “qualitative analysis usually seeks to enhance the data, to increase its bulk, density and complexity”.

Gibbs (2018) explains that qualitative data analysis may aim at:

- In-depth description of social phenomena: in this case, the researcher is exploring an under-researched phenomenon.
- Develop and refine hypotheses: this approach tends to occur in mixed methods research where a qualitative research precedes quantitative research, yet this does not necessarily have to be the case but it is important to note that in this case, qualitative analysis lacks numeric estimates of frequency.
- Create a model that explains the determinants of the research phenomenon: this approach is used in cases where the research is “addressing some policy or practice needs or even is aimed at evaluating some programme of activity”
- Develop a theory: a developed theory that can be based on a small-scale phenomenon under investigation usually it is the choice of researchers preferring grounded theory.

Robson and McCarter (2016, p.461) name three main approaches to qualitative analysis given as follows with their characteristics:

Quasi-statistical Approach

- Relies mainly on word or phrase frequencies and inter-correlations to identify the main terms.
- Characterized by content analysis.

Thematic Coding Approach

- A general approach that does not necessarily match a given theoretical perspective.
- All or some parts of the data are coded and labelled.
- Themes are formed through classifying codes that have an identical label.
- Codes and themes generated from data can be either determined inductively and/or in line with the research questions, previous studies or theoretical considerations.

- The themes generated are considered as a foundation for further data analysis and interpretation.
- This approach uses summaries of themes considerably accompanied with matrices, network maps, flow charts and diagrams.
- It fits in descriptive or exploratory research or within various theoretical frameworks.

Grounded Theory Approach

- It is a version of the previous approach in which codes are generated from interaction with data.
- The researcher's interpretation of the meaning emerged from textual data, determines the codes.
- Used when generating a theory "grounded" in the data.
- The researcher can opt for it following approach founders' rules or as a generic analysis using specialised terminology.

4.11.1. Thematic Coding Analysis

Gibbs (2018, no pagination) explains that coding is "a way of indexing or categorizing the text in order to establish a framework of thematic ideas about it". Furthermore, coding is "followed by grouping the initial codes into a smaller number of codes" (Robson and McCartan 2016, p.468).

Thematic coding analysis was used in this research following Robson and McCartan's (2016) argument, claiming that it can fit in purely descriptive or exploratory studies and in wide range of theoretical frameworks, thus it is not tied to a given theoretical framework. Furthermore, Braun et al. (2019) claim that accessibility and flexibility are two crucial reasons for using thematic analysis. Given that thematic analysis is not an approach to conducting qualitative research but rather a method of data analysis reinforces both its accessibility and flexibility (Braun et al., 2019). Moreover, in the sense of accessibility, thematic analysis provides researchers with little or no experience of qualitative research with guidance on how to code and analyse qualitative data, which therefore reduces the complexity of data analysis (Braun et al., 2019).

Braun and Clarke (2006) suggest advantages and disadvantages of using thematic coding analysis as cited in Robson and McCartan (2016, p.470), which are as follows:

4.11.1.1. Advantages of Thematic Coding Analysis

1. It can fit in practically any type of qualitative data.
2. In terms of use, as an approach to qualitative data analysis, it is known for its simplicity and swiftness.
3. Qualitative researchers do not necessarily need to have prior experience in order to use this approach.
4. The analysis results are comprehensible to practitioners, policy-makers and educated people.
5. It is a good choice in researches where participants collaborate in the research and in the analysis of findings.
6. It allows voluminous qualitative data to be summarised providing significant features.
7. Studies in various fields and disciplines can use thematic coding analysis.

4.11.1.2. Disadvantages of Thematic Coding Analysis

1. Despite considering the flexibility of this type of analysis as a strength, it can also be a weakness in terms of making it hard on the researcher to choose the key aspects to emphasize.
2. Thematic coding analysis is not commonly used in interpretation, as it is more likely to be linked to description or exploration.
3. Lack of information about the procedure is frequently associated with this type of analysis.
4. In comparison to other approaches to qualitative analysis, this approach is perceived as general which makes it less kudos as an analytic method than the others.

Therefore, thematic coding analysis was used in this research. As opposite to the other methods of analysis, thematic analysis is characterised by its flexibility (Braun and Clarke, 2006). Furthermore, “it is the first qualitative method of analysis that researchers should learn, as it provides core skills” (Braun and Clarke, 2006, p.78). Consequently, it is a good choice for novice researchers.

4.12. Questionnaire Database

The data was collected over a two-month period through the use of mixed methods. This procedure underwent two phases. The first phase (January 2020) was devoted to the questionnaires. Before distributing questionnaires to the participants, an informal message was

sent to them via Facebook to introduce them to the questionnaire. Following this, a participant information sheet was sent to each participant in order to give them more details about the research, why they were chosen, what are they expected to do and also informing them of their rights mainly confidentiality and anonymity. Twenty-one questionnaires were submitted online via Survey Monkey. Considering the fact that the questionnaires were to be completed anonymously, the participants did not need to sign a consent form. Consequently, the first page of the questionnaire contained a brief summary of the main points in the participant information sheet for the questionnaires, and a statement to ensure that the participants consent for their data to be used in this study. Moreover, since the questionnaires were anonymous, it was made clear that the participants would not be able to withdraw their data after they submitted their response due to the fact that it would not be possible to identify their data, because all responses were anonymous. The questionnaires contained nine questions; the first two questions were about the respondents' details, whereas the rest included seven close-ended questions with one open-ended sub question at the end. The aim of using questionnaires is to obtain an overview and straightforward data to help shape the subsequent interview questions and select participants to be interviewed based on their willingness to take part in the interviews as well as their answers to a few questions in the questionnaires.

The second phase (February 2020) focused on semi-structured interviews. The participants were invited in the questionnaires to take part in the interviews. Accordingly, at the end of the questionnaires, there was a note stating that the researcher was also conducting interviews in this research and those who are interested in being interviewed can provide their contact details in the space provided. The participants were given several choices for giving their contact details: phone number, email, Facebook username, Skype username, if the participant prefers to remain anonymous, they can just provide their phone numbers. This way it will not be possible to link the interviewee with their response to the questionnaire and this will ensure complete anonymity. However, a separate sheet could have been used to give the contact details to ensure more anonymity but this way the researcher cannot select the interviewees based on the answers to some specific questions as discussed earlier. It is to be noted that all the questionnaires and interviews were in English to ensure consistency among all the participants. All the participants had a certain level of English, as they had degrees in English, consequently all the questionnaires and the interviews were conducted in English. No Arabic was used to ensure consistency. Neither the questionnaires nor the interviews were in Arabic because it would have been uncomfortable to communicate in MSA, despite the fact that we were

interpreting into and from MSA during our MA degree. It was not possible to use DA as well since it is an informal variety of language and it would have been hard and time-consuming to transcribe the interviews and translate them into English. This is consistent with the findings of this research that show that the vernaculars cannot be used to discuss academic subjects. Furthermore, it is difficult for the participants and I to express thoughts successfully using MSA especially in the oral form. However, I am aware that when an interview takes place in English this could affect the level of expression for certain participants and their views.

4.13. Qualitative Data Analysis

This study adopted a sequential explanatory strategy. According to Creswell and Plano Clark (2011, p, 211) this design is:

Characterized by the collection and analysis of quantitative data in a first phase of research followed by the collection and analysis of qualitative data in a second phase that builds on the results of the initial quantitative results.

Thus, in this research, the phase of quantitative data collection and analysis preceded the qualitative data collection and analysis. The questionnaires were used to get an overall idea about the students' attitudes towards their experience in SI but they did not provide in depth data, thus they were followed up by semi-structured interviews in order to get a detailed understanding of the phenomenon under study.

The questionnaire results helped largely in building up and editing the interview questions. The online survey involved ten questions. The first two questions were general questions about the participants' L1 and job title.

On the other hand, four questions aimed to explore the participants' attitudes towards the SI module; in terms of the teaching materials, the facilities, the assignments and the effectiveness of the module. The following two questions focused on the graduates' MSA writing and oral language proficiency. Furthermore, the remaining question was the only open-ended question in the survey in which the graduates' were asked to choose from three options (your level of English language, your level of MSA, and classroom use of MSA and not dialectal Arabic) the most challenging element in their SI classes and justify their choice. Lastly, in the questionnaire, the respondents were invited to participate in a Skype interview and were asked

to provide contact details of their choice to be approached later if they are interested in taking part. As abovementioned, the questionnaire results helped in building up the interview questions. Earlier in the literature review, studies revealed that Arabic diglossia has a negative impact on the educational system in the Arabic speaking countries. Therefore, the survey questions were based on this proposition, as shown in the literature (among many others, Abdulaziz, 1986; Maamouri, 1998; Haeri, 2000; Cote, 2009; Dendane, 2015), and hence hypothesises that Arabic diglossia has an impact on the pedagogy of SI in Algeria. However, in general, participants seem to have a good MSA oral and written language proficiency according to their answers: when asked about their MSA oral language proficiency, over half of the participants chose excellent and good. These themes re-emerged in the follow-up interviews as will be discussed below in the following sections.

In other words, the focus of the survey questions in terms of language proficiency was exclusively on the Arabic language, whereas the graduates' level of English was not mentioned anywhere in the questionnaire.

A number of themes emerged from the online survey. A fundamental finding from the questionnaire is that the level of the English language was chosen as the biggest challenge that SI students encountered in their SI classes which is a key finding. In this respect, most participants (seventeen out of twenty-one) claimed that the difficulties they faced were attributed to the level of language required in SI classes in general and to their lack of terminology in English in specific as they highlighted later in the interviews, which made the SI tasks more challenging. In this light, Gile (2009, p.9) emphasises that “interpreters and translators need to have good command of their active working languages”. In the context of this study, English is an active language in interpreting, a ‘B’ language, or the interpreters’ foreign language. Gile (2009) explains “this requirement is set at a very demanding standard (...). This requirement goes much beyond the ‘natural’ command one acquires over childhood and adolescence in one’s native language” (p.9). In other words, according to Gile (2009) having a good command of the active working languages is requisite. However, as reported by the participants in the online survey and the interviews, they were encountering difficulties in both working languages. In English because it is their foreign language and they did not feel that their level was good enough to enable them to interpret from and into that language, and in MSA because it is not a form of language they are exposed to in their daily life interactions.

Consequently, based on the questionnaire results, the interview questions were reviewed, and included questions related to the difficulties the graduates faced when interpreting because of their English language incompetence. For instance, it can be seen in the appendix E on page 231-3 question 15 which is “in your opinion what impact did your level of English have on your performance in SI classes?” was added to the interview questions. This question directly relates to the issue of the students’ English level since the majority of the questionnaire respondents claimed that the difficulties they faced in SI classes are traceable to their lack of an adequate English vocabulary in different contexts. Furthermore, two questions in the questionnaire asked the respondents to define their MSA written and oral language proficiency. After analysing the quantitative data and figuring out that the English language was a key problem, I proposed to add the following question to the interview questions, “How would you define your written and oral English Language level? However, the aim of the in-depth interviews is to provide rich data rather than brief answers, that is why this question was eliminated and question 15 was asked instead. On the other hand, when I delved deeper into the interviews, MSA appeared to be challenging as well due to diglossia, in other words not only the graduates’ English language was considered a challenge but also MSA.

One example of how the questionnaire contributed to refining the interview questions is where the first question which is “what is your L1?” was removed. It is to be noted that this question was already asked in the questionnaire but was deliberately supposed to be asked again in the interview in order to precede questions related to L1 definition and if the graduates consider MSA as an L1. Nevertheless, in order to narrow the interview protocol, and since a question related to the English level was added, this question had to be removed; (see my interview schedule on page 231).

4.14. Ethical Considerations

As part of the qualitative research, and well before the stage of data analysis, a consent form was sent to the participants to highlight all aspects of this research including what are they supposed to do and what are their rights (Gibbs, 2018). Nevertheless, among the ethical issues that qualitative researchers face is the identification of participants, that is to say the data provided is very personal and there is a high possibility of identification of individuals if for instance the researcher uses direct quotations, this is why anonymization of transcripts is very crucial throughout the stage of data analysis (Gibbs, 2018).

Consistent with Gibbs's (2018) argument, Cohen, Manion and Morrison (2018) also emphasise on confidentiality due to the nature of qualitative data that tends to be more sensitive and personal in comparison to quantitative data, which in return increases the researcher's responsibility of being aware of all ethical issues embedded in their study. Additionally, the researcher should ensure that their research would not harm or cause discomfort to the participants in any way even before reaching the stage of data analysis (Gibbs, 2018).

4.14.1. Researcher Positionality

Discussions over the pitfalls of interviewing people with whom the researcher has a relationship and cases in which the researcher belongs to the population under study are controversial. In this section, I will tackle the implications of recruiting people you know in qualitative research along with the issues of validity, limitations and bias resulting from the latter. In the literature, this case is referred to as "Insider-Outsider" (Dwyer and Buckle, 2009, p.54). Recruitment refers to when "researchers ask people to participate in interviews for the purpose of research" (Roulston, 2010, p.98).

While the researcher as an insider denotes "sharing the characteristic, role, or experience under study with the participants", the outsider on the other hand refers to cases where the researcher is "an outsider to the commonality shared by participants" (Dwyer and Buckle, 2009, p.55). Following the above definitions, in this research, as a researcher I am an insider because I have a shared experience with the participants, in addition to that, I belong to the population under study. Dwyer and Buckle (2009) highlight that what is more important in a researcher role is not an insider or an outsider, rather authenticity; honesty; openness; interest and accuracy in representing the participants' experiences.

4.14.2. Limitations and Benefits of Being an Insider Researcher

McEvoy (2001) highlights key drawbacks of being an insider researcher, this includes assuming that the aspects of the social world to which the researcher belongs are taken for granted; questions discussing grounded social norms may not be welcomed and participants might not be as open as tackling sensitive topics with an outsider. To this McEvoy (2001) refers to Stephenson and Greer (1981) to add that the insider lacks the objective standpoint due to his/her emergence in the population he/she belongs to which may result in narrowed and imbalanced opinions. In my view, having a mutual lived experience with the participants under

study does not necessarily entail being aware of the entire image as each individual experience is unique, therefore the influence of the insider researcher may not be considered as a drawback.

Additionally, when the researcher is an insider, the participants may not provide full details of their experience assuming that the researcher is already aware of the entire image and this does not genuinely help the understanding of the phenomenon under study. McEvoy (2001) supports this argument by stating “I have found that colleagues have tended to avoid stating the obvious” (p.53). Roulston (2010) also agrees that when both the researcher and the participant have a mutual experience, they rely on their understanding and therefore it makes it hard to tackle research topics and ask questions as will be discussed further in the next section. Yet in this case, the researcher can ask further questions to request more clarification and details. Roulston (2010) quotes Bourdieu et al (1999) to address this situation

Every investigation is therefore situated between two extremes doubtless never completely attained: total overlap between investigator and respondent, where nothing can be said because, since nothing can be questioned, everything goes without saying; and total divergence, where understanding and trust would become impossible (as cited in Roulston, 2010, p.99).

On the other hand, Dwyer and Buckle (2009) assert that being an insider provides easy access to the participants that might be difficult if the researcher is an outsider. Furthermore, considering the fact that the researcher is part of the same population as the participants allows them to be more open assuming that there is a high level of understanding of their mutual experiences (Dwyer and Buckle, 2009). In this light, “shared experience may act as a catalyst that helps to generate new avenues of inquiry by opening up and extending the depth of a discussion” (McEvoy, 2001, p.52). According to Roulston (2010, p.98) “for researchers using personal connections to informants as a means to recruit participants, relative intimacy and rapport with participants may enhance the generation of data in interview settings in ways not possible for 'outsider' researchers”.

4.14.3. Ethical Considerations of Interviewing Colleagues

Among the ethical considerations that one should take into account when interviewing colleagues is that this kind of relationship the researcher has with his/her fellows may make

them feel they are implicitly obliged to take part in the research and therefore have to make this decision (McEvoy, 2001). As a result, McEvoy (2001) continues to explain “this could infringe my ethical duty to respect their autonomy” (p.55). In order to reduce the impact of the participation in research on the researcher/participant relationship, the participants were clearly informed from the beginning (in the participant information sheet) that their participation in the research is totally voluntary and any incapability to take part will not affect the researcher/participant relationship in any way. Therefore, interviewing former colleagues is regarded as an advantage rather than a drawback. However, this could be challenging as it is harder than it seems for the reasons abovementioned.

4.14.4. Ethical Considerations of Internet Mediated Research

Internet Mediated Research, hereafter ‘IMR’, covers “any research involving the remote acquisition of data from or about human participants using the internet and its associated technologies” (bps.org.uk, 2017).

4.14.4.1. Building Rapport over Skype Interviews

Among the drawbacks of using Skype interviews is the lack of the advantages present in face-to-face interactions in comparison to online interactions and building rapport with the participants is one of them. King and Horrocks (2010) explain that “rapport is ... about trust – enabling the participant to feel comfortable in opening up to you” (p.48). It is hard to build rapport over Skype if you do not previously know the participants, and therefore this may be considered as a drawback. However, in this study because the participants are my former classmates, this issue is less likely to be encountered.

4.14.4.2. Issues Related to Skype Interviews

Technical issues may affect the flow of Skype interviews, such as cases where the interviewee is fully engaged in the interview and then an interruption occurs due to the loss of connection (Seitz, 2015 as cited in Lo Iacono, Symonds and Brown, 2016, p.10). This issue can be reduced in the context of this research because I know most of the participants in person, as they were my former classmates and the interview questions are not too personal and do not tackle sensitive topics, consequently resuming the call in cases of poor connection will presumably not affect the flow of the interview. It is to be noted that technology is constantly and rapidly

developing, therefore technical issues may be less likely to occur in the future (Lo Iacono, Symonds and Brown, 2016).

Moreover, arguing that face-to-face interviews offer richer data in comparison to online interviews is not always true as this depends to a great extent on “the topic of the research and on the personality of the participant and interviewer” (Lo Iacono, Symonds and Brown, 2016, p.11). Body language, especially eye contact in Skype interviews cannot be as present as in face-to-face interviews, in the research that Lo Iacono, Symonds and Brown (2016) conducted, in which the researchers gathered data from the feedback of their participants in Skype interviews, the results revealed that the lack of eye contact was not considered as a drawback.

4.14.4.2.1. Ethical Considerations of Skype Interviews

Lo Iacono, Symonds and Brown (2016) note that in addition to the ethical considerations present in every research project that involve human participations when collecting data, namely:

- The researcher’s responsibility to ensure that the participants understand their right to withdraw at any time;
- Giving the participants a consent form;
- Informing them that the interview will be recorded;
- Giving them the opportunity to choose the location and time of the interview according to their preferences and availability;
- Confirming the confidentiality of the meeting and;
- Reassuring the participants that the data will be stored in a password protected USB and only accessed by the researcher and the supervisory team.

Skype interviews incorporate further ethical considerations that the researcher has to be aware of, in this regard, Lo Iacono, Symonds and Brown (2016) note three key elements:

- 1) Electronic Data and Big Brother: Skype video calls risk to be monitored “it is therefore important, from an ethical stand-point, to remind participants that their discussions online may be accessed and stored by governments agencies or corporations” (p.16). However, this is more applied to topics that tend to be sensitive.

- 2) **Verification of Identity:** it may be hard to ensure the identity of the interviewees online, as a suggestion, checking their online social media accounts can give the researcher an overview of who they are.
- 3) **Interview Environment and Video Recording:** since the participants have the right to choose the location in which they sit and use Skype interviews, they are advised beforehand to select appropriate places in order to avoid any risk of accidentally showing private things they do not want others to see.

Nevertheless, “researchers need to be aware that it is impossible to maintain absolute confidentiality of participants’ personal information gathered online because the networks are not in the control of the researcher” (bps.org.uk, 2017, p.10).

Concerning the second point, which highlights the issue of identity verification, interviewing people you know, as is the case of this research can eliminate the latter. In relation to the third point, which tackles the interview environment, the interviewee is able to view the screen that the interviewer sees including the background and therefore can change the setting if he/she thinks is not suitable for the interview. However, what should be taken into consideration to assure confidentiality in Skype interviews is ensuring there is no third party in each of the locations. This may be hard to identify online as the camera does not show the whole location, yet it can be overcome if both (the researcher and the participant) use headphones to make sure that only the two parties can hear what is being said.

Furthermore, because Skype video calls are to be recorded, the participants should be informed when the recording starts, pauses and stops as well as being offered the chance to “listen to a copy of the video/audio recording of the interview” (Lo Iacono, Symonds and Brown, 2016, p.18).

4.15. Summary

In conclusion as I have justified above, I used mixed methods involving questionnaires and semi-structured Skype interviews. I also justified the sample selection, which involved graduate students of the University of Ouargla in Algeria, the research design, theoretical framework, data collection, tools and procedures, data analysis, and ethical considerations.

Chapter 5: Findings

5.1. Questionnaire Data Analysis

Question 1:

The first question referred to the participants' first language. As is tabulated below, all the respondents answered "Arabic" when asked about their L1.

Number of participants	First language
21	Arabic

Table 8: Number of respondents according to their first language

Question 2:

This item asked the participants to give their current job title. The following table shows the distribution of respondents according to their current jobs. As shown below, most participants are teachers of English whereas the second most common response shows that five participants are currently unemployed. The rest of the answers included a variety of other jobs.

Job title	Number of participants
Teacher of English	7
Unemployed	5
Teacher of remedial English courses	1
Translator	1
Interpreter	1
Translator/interpreter and English language teacher	1
Assistant	1
Admin and commercial coordinator	1
IT (Computer and Network) Technician	1
Tramway senior manager	1
Chef Personnel	1

Table 9: Distribution of respondents according to their job title

Name of the participant	Job title
QP1	Teacher
QP2	Teacher

QP3	Teacher
QP4	Interpreter
QP5	Teacher
QP6	Translator
QP7	Unemployed
QP8	Assistant
QP9	Unemployed
QP10	Unemployed
QP11	Teacher
QP12	Tramway senior manager
QP13	Teacher
QP14	Admin and Commercial Coordinator
QP15	Unemployed
QP16	Teacher
QP17	Translator/Interpreter/teacher
QP18	IT Computer Technician
QP19	Unemployed
QP20	Chef Personnel
QP21	Teacher

Table 10: Names of the participants and their jobs

Question 3:

This question aimed to ask the participants about the effectiveness of the methods of SI. The table below shows that the majority were satisfied with the SI teaching methods.

Effectiveness of SI teaching methods	Number of participants
Extremely effective	0
Effective	4
Satisfactory	12
Somewhat ineffective	4
Ineffective	1

Table 11: Likert scaling of the teaching methods of SI

Question 4:

This question seeks to explore the extent of helpfulness of the classroom assignments during the SI course to the development of the students' interpreting skills. Almost half of the participants claim that they were helpful.

Helpfulness of classroom assignments	Number of participants
Extremely helpful	2
Helpful	10
Satisfactory	6
Somewhat unhelpful	3
Not helpful at all	0

Table 12: Helpfulness of classroom assignments Likert scaling

Question 5:

This item was about rating the quality of SI teaching materials at university in the second year of the MA degree. The majority of the respondents think they were poor.

Quality of SI teaching materials	Number of participants
Excellent	2
Good	2
Satisfactory	4
Poor	11
Very poor	2

Table 13: Quality of SI teaching materials

Question 6:

This question was about rating the facilities in their university and their role in developing their SI skills. Over half of the participants assert that the facilities were poor.

University facility rating	Number of participants
Excellent	0
Good	1
Satisfactory	2
Poor	16
Very poor	2

Table 14: University facility rating

Question 7:

This question aims to explore participants' perceived MSA oral language proficiency. The table shows that most respondents claim that they have 'good' to 'excellent' MSA oral command.

MSA oral language proficiency	Number of participants
Excellent	8
Good	9
Satisfactory	4
Poor	0
Very poor	0

Table 15: MSA oral language proficiency rating

Question 8:

This table shows how respondents rated their perceived MSA writing language proficiency. The majority selected 'Excellent' and 'Good'.

MSA writing language proficiency	Number of participants
Excellent	10
Good	7
Satisfactory	3
Poor	1
Very poor	0

Table 16: MSA writing language proficiency rating

Question 9:

The following table shows evidence that the majority of the participants think that their English language level was the most challenging element in their SI classes. However, concerning the second two options, the MSA level and the classroom use of MSA and not dialectal Arabic, the respondents gave equal percentages.

Options	Number of participants
Your level of English language	15

Your level of MSA	3
Classroom use of MSA and not dialectal Arabic	3

Table 17: Distribution of participants according to their choice of the most challenging element in SI classes

There was a sub open-ended question in which the participants were asked to explain their response in relation to this question in a few words. In total, 18 out of 21 participants responded to this question, accordingly the answers were varied as will be demonstrated below.

Among the 15 respondents who chose “your level of English language”, 13 provided a justification for their choice. After reviewing the answers of the open-ended questions, I can conclude that three themes emerged.

The first theme is the unfamiliarity with the English language terminology in different contexts. The majority of the respondents, who chose “your level of English language”, (seven respondents) agreed on this point. QP3 and QP16 who both work as teachers of English agreed that the challenge they were facing when interpreting lies in their English vocabulary, they stated respectively that “*maybe because of the lack of English specialized terms like the legal and medical terms*” and “*the lack of advanced vocabulary*”. Furthermore, the level of English that the task of SI requires seems to be challenging to the students. In this regard, QP6 who works as a translator stated “*my level in English was good but in interpretation should be excellent*”, whereas QP7 who is currently unemployed did not give much details and said “*level of English used*”. It can be understood from their answers that in SI classes, a certain level (high level) of English language was requisite. On the other hand, QP8 who works as an assistant, and QP20 who is a “chef personnel”, both agreed that the process of interpreting contributed to enriching their vocabulary in both languages. QP8 stated “*it was really helpful to discover new terminologies and to learn the difficulties that encounter the interpreter during the process of interpreting*”, whereas QP20 said “*because it’s all about knowledge and gaining more vocabulary that helps in multi-fields and the lack of that could cause to a disruption*”. QP20’s answer shows that the practice of SI depends on the interpreter’s knowledge and vocabulary, which both improve with practice when the interpreter deals with different contexts. QP12, who works as a “tramway senior manager”, claims that “*English is changing rapidly and being out of date may cause misleading*”. This answer also shows that the English

language vocabulary is a challenging element in SI classes as it plays a vital role in the practice of interpreting, therefore interpreters have to update themselves as individuals on the new terminology that emerges.

The second most common theme that the respondents' highlighted is the fact that English is neither their L1, nor even their second language, which made their level of English language a challenging element in their SI classes. In this respect, QP1 who works as a teacher said "*it was a bit challenging comparing to the level of my Arabic Language*". Moreover, QP18 who is a computer and network technician stated that "*English language is neither my native nor second language*".

QP2 who works as a teacher and QP15 who is currently unemployed, referred to the direction of interpreting (into B interpreting). When asked to explain why English was the challenging element in SI classes, QP2 said "*because you have to master the target language (English) very well to convey the essence of the message you want to transmit*". That is to say, according to QP2's response, it was challenging to them to interpret from MSA into English as they referred to English as the target language. However, QP15 said "*personally, mastering the target language facilitates all the obstacles*". Nevertheless, QP15 did not specify what language they are referring to by '*the target language*', whether it is English or Arabic. However, what is inferred is that they were referring to the English language.

Following the definition of the AIIC (Association Internationale des Interprètes de Conférence), a "B" language is a language that the interpreter speaks fluently and therefore is an active language. Interpreters can work into B language but in comparison to consecutive interpreting, they tend to prefer working into B in consecutive interpreting as this mode of interpreting is not as fast as SI. In other words, according to the two respondents' answers, interpreting simultaneously into an active language, in this case into English, seems to be challenging. The participants think that they were not equipped linguistically for this course in either languages.

The third and the last area that came out from the answers of the participants who chose the level of English language as the most challenging element in SI classes is multi-tasking: speaking and listening to what have been said while they were speaking. QP9 and QP10, who are both currently unemployed, referred the mental load embedded in SI. QP9 provided a description of the SI process "*the biggest challenge I have is speaking: find equivalent word*

in English (foreign language), while listening to Arabic speech. Indeed, I'm always facing this problem while interpreting whatever the interpretation is into or from English. So I must enhance the skill of speaking while listening". On the other hand, QP10 said *"My mental process was very slow. I could not do two things at the same time (multitasking)".* It is important to highlight, that SI is a mentally exhausting task even when interpreters are competent in both working languages. However, it would be hugely difficult to deal with multi-tasking and linguistic shortcomings at the same time.

The other option among the available options in the open-ended question, which asks the respondents to select the most challenging element in SI classes, is "your level of MSA". Among the three respondents who selected this option, two provided explanations to their selection. QP5 who is a teacher said *"because we neglect parsing as well as we are thinking in Arabic (mother language)",* whereas QP17 who works as a teacher as well as translator/interpreter said *"I found a difficulty in standard modern Arabic because it's rarely spoken".* It should be noted that QP5 added an emphasis (*mother language*) after mentioning 'Arabic' although he/she argued that their level of MSA is the most challenging element in SI classes, it could mean that their L1 affected his/her level of MSA. However, the participant's answer is not precise, by 'Arabic', he/she could be referring to MSA or to dialectal Arabic, and accordingly this point was followed up in the interview.

On the other hand, the three respondents who chose "classroom use of MSA and not dialectal Arabic" gave varied reasons for their choices. QP11 and QP13 who are both teachers said respectively *"Modern standard Arabic is rarely used to communicate unlike dialectical Arabic"* and *"the use of Modern Standard Arabic in class instead of the dialectical one wasn't that simple because of first my poor level (yeah, I have very low proficiency in it) and also out of habit! I've never totally engaged to speak it".* However, although QP4 chose "classroom use of MSA and not dialectal Arabic" when asked to select among the three given options the one that is the most challenging element in SI classes, he/she said *"we can say in this case just some subtle differences".* The explanation contradicts the choice he/she made; if there are only subtle differences between MSA and dialectal Arabic, then why would the classroom use of MSA and not dialectal Arabic be challenging? Therefore, this point is followed up in the interview.

At the end of the survey, participants were invited to take part in Skype interviews. Sixteen respondents out of twenty-one expressed their willingness to participate and provided the

contact methods in which they preferred to be approached. In this light, the respondents were asked a follow up question.

After analysing the questionnaire data, I realised that the open-ended questionnaire question number nine, in which the respondents were asked to select one most challenging element in their SI classes among three options, was not thoughtful. That is to say, the majority of the respondents chose “your level of English” as the most challenging element, yet it was not clear in which interpreting direction they encountered more difficulties in their level of English. In this light, I asked the respondents a follow up question to get more details regarding the most challenging element they faced in SI classes and its impact on the direction of interpreting. Five respondents showed willingness to share their experience and provided more details. The question was more like a discussion than a formal question and it was as follows: I was reviewing my questionnaire questions and I figured out that one of them was a bit unclear. When I asked you what was the most challenging element in simultaneous interpreting classes, you answered by (your level of English language). What was more challenging, interpreting from English into Arabic or from Arabic into English?

The five respondents, who replied to this question, chose “your level of English” earlier in the questionnaire.

QP1 and QP16 said that it was more challenging to interpret from English into Arabic. QP1 added “*well, concerning from Arabic into English I used to face the lack of English vocabulary, which caused wasting time while looking for the right term that may serve the situation. On other hand, concerning from English into Arabic sometimes I was not able even to understand the meaning of some words. Therefore, I think that my main problem was the vocabulary*”. According to QP1’s response, it seems that English vocabulary was the main difficulty when interpreting in both directions. On the other hand, QP16 said “*so, for me the most challenging is from English into Arabic because many difficulties can appear like new vocabulary, structure of the sentence etc.*” Vocabulary occurs one more time and to it, QP16 added morphology.

The three other respondents said it was harder for them to interpret from Arabic into English.

QP12 said “*The difficulty was mainly in complex texts in Arabic. As an example, literary texts, which contain vocabulary and expressions that are not widely used nowadays, or specialized texts that often contain a lot of terms that are interrelated*”. In this respect, Al-Salman and Al-

Khanji (2002) note that “written texts tend to use more sophisticated vocabulary, more complex syntax, and more complex semantic and pragmatic implicatures than even rather formal oral discussions, including those conducted in “standard language in formal settings”, therefore “most of the code shifts occur when the speaker was reading from a written text” (p.621). In this regard, when the speaker is reading from a paper, the style tends to be more formal in comparison with speaking spontaneously, therefore, in that case, it would be more difficult for the students to interpret from MSA.

I proceeded to ask the participant, if they thought that the challenge lies in the nature of the Arabic texts, which made it harder to interpret from Arabic into English, then why did they choose ‘your level of English language’ as the most challenging element. The participant said “*I meant that my English is not rich enough to handle the majority of texts*”. It can be understood from QP12’s explanation that both languages involved in the interpreting process affect each other: if the student of interpreting faces difficulties in the language they are interpreting from (in this case Arabic), it affects their understanding and therefore affects their interpretation in the language they are interpreting into (English). Furthermore, QP12 said that the vocabulary used in Arabic literary texts is not widely used nowadays; this could mean that because the form of Arabic used in daily life interactions is dialectal Arabic and not MSA, that is why he/she was not familiar with its terminology unless QP12 was referring to Classical Arabic. This point will be elaborated in the interview.

QP16 claims that it was harder to interpret from Arabic into English because of the “*specialised terms in English such as legal and political terms etc.*” In other words, in SI there it is requisite to have a rich broad vocabulary according to the specific context especially in the language you are interpreting into, which in this case is English (a foreign language). Therefore, a number of respondents agreed that it was harder for them to interpret into a language that is neither their L1 nor their second language.

QP2 also said it is more difficult to interpret from Arabic into English because:

From English into Arabic we have a rich vocabulary in Arabic, it is our mother tongue, and it is not as difficult as interpreting into a foreign language. From English into Arabic, once you understand the context you have the vocabulary to interpret into Arabic, it is our mother tongue, we have rich vocabulary and we are also familiar with the culture.

When referring to MSA, the only form of Arabic used in SI classes, QP2 addressed it as a '*mother tongue*', this could mean that he/she considers MSA as a mother tongue or he/she was referring to the Arabic language in general including its both forms MSA and dialectal Arabic. This point will be discussed further in the interviews.

From the above discussion, we can understand that the English language vocabulary was the common point among the five respondents' answers. Whether they were interpreting from English into Arabic or from Arabic into English, vocabulary was a significant challenge. In other words, regardless of the direction of interpreting, when one does not have a rich vocabulary in one of the languages involved in the interpreting process, this affects ones' understanding (if they are interpreting from that language) or the product of interpreting (if they are interpreting into that language).

To conclude, the data collected from the online survey administrated to the alumni of the Translation and Translation Studies master's students at the University of Ouargla shows that all participants answered "Arabic" when asked about their L1. This answer provides consistency among the participants and it shows that since Arabic is their L1 they are familiar with the Arabic language and its use both in daily life interactions and in academic settings; therefore they can provide rich data in the interviews. However, the participants' answers were general; none of them specified which form of language is their L1, whether it is one of the various spoken dialects or MSA. This underlines the issues between MSA and DA, as the word "Arabic" is often used to refer to both forms although they are hugely different. This point will be discussed further in the interviews.

Overall, the respondents were satisfied with the teaching methods that used to deliver SI in their university and stated that the classroom assignments were helpful to their interpreting skill development. However, they argue that the quality of SI teaching materials and the facilities at their university were in their opinion poor and this perhaps accounts for their lack of vocabulary in English.

In general, participants seem to have a good MSA oral and written language proficiency according to their answers; however, this is their perceived language level, which may vary from their actual level. On the one hand, when asked about their MSA oral language proficiency, over half of the participants chose excellent and good to describe their proficiency. On the other hand, when asked to rate their MSA writing language proficiency, excellent and

good were the most common answers. These findings contradict Dendane's (2015) argument, which states that interpreters whose L1 is not MSA will encounter difficulties speaking and conveying meanings in that form of language. Furthermore, Cote (2009) claims that the complexity of MSA along with the fact that it is nobody's L1, contribute to the hindrance of the development of the educational system in the Arabic speaking world. This research endorses the fact that MSA in nobody's L1 results in making the pedagogy of SI more challenging, as the participants explained later in the interviews. However, the two arguments that Cote (2009) and Dendane (2015) made demonstrate that Arabic diglossia has a negative impact on the educational system in the Arab world. In SI on the other hand, the linguistic issue is very fundamental, as neither MSA nor English are the students' L1. Furthermore, the majority of the participants rated their oral and written MSA levels as good and excellent, however, writing and speaking a language is very different from interpreting from and into that language.

Furthermore, another fundamental finding from this survey is that the majority chose the level of English language as the most challenging element that SI students encountered in their SI classes. In this respect, most participants claimed that the difficulties they faced were attributed to their lack of knowledge of the terminology in English, which made the SI tasks more challenging. In their study, Al-Salman and Al-Khanji's (2002) findings showed that the field and the context of interpreting might largely affect the performance of the interpreter; this point is consistent with the findings of this questionnaire. When asked to provide some details about why their level of English language was the most challenging element in their SI classes, many respondents stated that it was because of their lack of knowledge of the vocabulary in the English language in the various contexts.

The second most common area that the respondents highlighted is that of interpreting from/into a foreign language. Four participants referred to this area with two of them clearly highlighting the fact that English is neither their L1 nor even their second language, which contributed to making their level of English language a challenging element in their SI classes. It is evident from the participants' answers that they do not feel that their English language level prepare them adequately for this role.

The third most common answer to this question is that of multi-tasking, as students said it was hard to listen and speak simultaneously, which is the main SI feature and requirement. In this

regard, Dailidėnaitė and Volyneć (2013) assert that SI “is agreed to be an extremely complex activity, as listening and speaking at the same time is a very demanding task” (p.34).

Furthermore, Al-Salman and Al-Khanji (2002) also mentioned the need to be focused when interpreting, to have physical endurance and most importantly to have a good short and long-term memory. These points are to some extent consistent with the findings of this questionnaire. Only two participants referred to the mental load embedded in the task of SI, explaining that it was challenging to them to listen and speak at the same time. In other words, they think that they have been inadequately prepared for this training by their university course.

On the other hand, the number of the respondents who chose “your level of MSA” and “the classroom use of MSA and not dialectal Arabic” as challenging elements in SI classes is equal.

5.1.1. The Direction of Interpreting

The questionnaire results show that the participants, SI students, argue that they perform differently depending on the direction of interpreting whether it is from MSA into English or from English into MSA. While some prefer interpreting in the first language direction, others favour the latter. In fact, “many interpreting scholars and the professional interpreter community regard directionality of SI as one of the factors which is directly related to the quality of SI” (Dailidėnaitė and Volyneć, 2013, p.34).

In the context of SI, and through the lens of a questionnaire survey, Bartłomiejczyk (2004) attempts to explore to what extent does the direction of interpreting affect the performance of interpreting students and professional interpreters. According to the findings of this study, the two points of view regard this matter in a significantly different way due to several reasons. Bartłomiejczyk’s (2004) study is among the very few studies in which interpreters and students of interpreting were asked about their perceptions and attitudes on directionality and how does it affect their performance, which is an area that should be investigated further incorporating several working languages. In this respect, Bartłomiejczyk (2004) makes a very important note by stating that “it is often difficult to determine whether the influence of interpreting direction (into or out of one’s native tongue) or the language specificity plays the greater role in interpreters’ performance” (pp.246-7). Bartłomiejczyk (2004) continues to explain that some factors “may sway interpreters’ opinions and preferences regarding the language combinations they work in quite independently of the given languages being native or non-native for them” (p.247). Accordingly, directionality and the L1 notion are not the only factors that affect

interpreters' performance; language combination (the involved working languages in interpreting), also plays a vital role. Therefore, suggestions for further research, as above, in the impact of working languages on the interpreters' preferred interpreting direction is needed.

The findings of Bartłomiejczyk's (2004) study revealed that "students were in favour of A-B interpreting much more often" (p.246). This could be due to various reasons. Bartłomiejczyk (2004) assumes that students of interpreting may be feeling more confident at the understanding phase, which is in the A language, and might be unaware of the errors they make when interpreting into B as they do when they interpret into their A (their L1), which makes them assume they have a very good command in B language. The more their B language level improves the more they will be aware of the errors they make; also, another reason for favouring A-B interpreting could be associated with students' improved into-B performance as the interpreting course proceeds (Bartłomiejczyk, 2004). Concerning the results of this questionnaire, the number of students favouring into-B is equal to the number of students favouring into-A interpreting, however, students' choices and attitudes will be discussed further in the interviews.

A discussion of perceptions of the relationship between the direction of interpreting, in both SI and consecutive interpreting, and the interpreter's performance can be controversial. While some scholars strictly believe that in the two modes of interpreting, consecutive and SI, interpretation should be only done in one's L1, others on the other hand consider that this depends largely on the mode of interpreting itself (Bartłomiejczyk, 2004). Seleskovitch (1978) is convinced that SI will only be successful if the interpretation is done into the interpreter's L1; in contrast, consecutive interpreting could be done into-B (as cited in Bartłomiejczyk, 2004, p.240). With regard to interpreting into-B, Seleskovitch argues that "once he finds himself in the shoes of an interpreter, [...] his native-like fluency disappears. His words no longer flow easily and naturally, and his pronunciation and vocabulary reflect the influence of his native language" (as cited in Bartłomiejczyk, 2004, p.240). This argument is consistent with the results of the questionnaire for this study as the second most common theme that emerged shows that whether it is from B or into B, students of SI found it difficult to interpret. In other words, the majority of the respondents argued that the complexity of B, the English language in this case, in both directions of interpreting, from B or into B, contributed to a great extent to making the SI task more challenging in comparison to their level of A language, MSA, which the majority regards it as an L1.

It is to be noted that the majority of the respondents consider that the complexities and the challenges they encountered in the classroom when interpreting are attributable to linguistic factors, mainly their English language vocabulary, which they think was not rich enough to fulfil the SI tasks in various and different contexts. Furthermore, Bartłomiejczyk (2004) uses Jones' (1998) argument to illustrate the viewpoints supporting into-B interpreting as Jones (1998) believes that it is easier to interpret into A, in comparison to interpreting into B advising interpreters to be "modest in the style they adopt" (as cited in Bartłomiejczyk, 2004, p.240). Bartłomiejczyk (2004, p.240) also refers to Kurz's (1992) experiment that shows that it is harder and more exhausting for interpreters to work into a non-L1.

On the other hand, despite the assumption made by scholars favouring into A interpreting and regarding its quality as "superior" (Bartłomiejczyk, 2004, p.239), scholars favouring 'retour interpreting' also have strong arguments. From a cognitive standpoint, Denissenko (1989) for instance believes that comprehension is the key element in the process of SI, which is enhanced when the language the interpreter listens to is his/her L1; additionally Denissenko (1989) argues that the available possibilities in the B language are limited, which facilitates the instant decision making (Bartłomiejczyk, 2004). In line with the last viewpoint of Denissenko (1989), the results of this research questionnaire show that the respondents consider the limited vocabulary in their B language as an obstacle rather than an advantage even when interpreting from A into B. Furthermore, when analysing the interpretation of professional interpreters, Al-Salman and Al-Khanji (2002) found that interpreters used some strategies such as anticipation and approximation when interpreting from English into Arabic (from B into A), "they succeeded in anticipating particularly culture-specific expressions by actually saying them before speakers had uttered the corresponding expressions" (2002, p.618). Strategies as such are more likely to be used when interpreting into an A language. However, given that the Arabic language is characterised by diglossia, this makes the situation more complex, as there is no clear-cut classification of MSA: while some do not consider it as an L1, it still cannot be clearly considered as a 'C' language. Therefore, interpreting into A is not always easier in comparison to retour interpreting. The findings of the study that Al-Salman and Al-Khanji (2002) conducted show that "it may not always be the case that people generally perform the same task (in speaking or in interpreting) less well in a second language than in a first" (p.624). In other words, conclusions generated from studies dealing with non-diglossic languages might not be applicable to diglossic languages as the complexity in the latter increases.

Although some strategies the interpreters in their study employed when interpreting into Arabic seemed to be helpful “achievement strategies”, as anticipation and approximation, they also used “reduction strategies” such as message abandonment, literal interpretation, incomplete sentences and code switching (Al-Salman and Al-Khanji, 2002, pp.618-9). In their study, interpreters resorted to some interpreting strategies when they failed or struggled to produce an MSA interpretation, “summarizing in informal Arabic, as we have pointed out, seems to have freed the interpreters from the linguistic constraints and the conscious monitoring of standard Arabic which can be quite demanding” (Al-Salman and Al-Khanji, 2002, pp. 619-620).

On the other hand, when analysing the interpretation from Arabic into English, interpreters were less likely to use reduction strategies; in contrast they used more achievement strategies such as approximation, skipping and summarizing. However, “omissions that occurred in skipping, were not due to great information load, time pressure or inability to process information quickly. It was perhaps due to the redundant use of lexical Arabic items or synonyms, a linguistic feature of Arabic style” (Al-Salman and Al-Khanji, 2002, p.620).

Al-Salman and Al-Khanji (2002) conclude that “strategy difference, therefore, provides another piece of evidence that interpretation from English to Arabic is more problematic according to the data analyzed in this study” (p.620). Furthermore, Al-Salman and Al-Khanji (2002) highlighted that the level of interpreters’ MSA “showed poor performance due to various factors such as familiarity with the subject matter, speaker’s speed, skill, etc. [...] Consequently, oral production of colloquial language is in a sense “more automatic” and more natural than oral production of a “standard” variety” (p.621). This is inconsistent with this study as the respondents claimed that they encountered these problems in the English language, with the majority describing their MSA written and oral levels as ‘excellent’ and ‘good’.

In this respect, in the study conducted by Bartłomiejczyk (2004), as I discussed above, the students of SI and the professional interpreters were given a list of options and were asked to classify the problems they encountered when interpreting from B into A and from A into B from a scale of never to always. Vocabulary was among the given problems. On the one hand, students think that vocabulary was a problem when interpreting from B into A more than it was when interpreting from A into B. In contrast, professional interpreters perceive vocabulary as a problem when interpreting from A into B more than it was when the interpretation is done from B into A. According to the findings of Bartłomiejczyk (2004), students of interpreting and professional interpreters’ viewpoints regarding the problems encountered when

interpreting in each direction differ considerably. Therefore, interpreters and interpreting students should be observed separately.

It is important to note that the issue of context appeared more frequently when the respondents in this research questionnaire were asked about the challenges they faced when interpreting. In this regard Al-Salman and Al-Khanji (2002) observe “the background of the interpreter vis-à-vis the subject matter of the presentation being interpreted is another important variable”. That is to say, as discussed earlier, directionality, L1 notion as well as language combination are not the only criteria to take into consideration when investigating interpreting studies, the context and the interpreter’s background can all affect the interpretation.

It is to be noted that twenty-one participants filled in the questionnaire and sixteen respondents out of twenty-one expressed their willingness to participate in the Skype interviews and provided the contact methods in which they prefer to be approached.

The participants were previously asked in the online survey about their current job title and the majority of the participants who took part in the Skype interviews work as teachers of English (IP1, IP2 and IP4), whereas IP3 is a tramway senior manager, and IP5 works as “chef personnel”. Moreover, Arabic is all the survey respondents’ L1.

Thus, from the participants’ answers to the open-ended question concerning the most challenging element in SI classes, various themes emerged. Accordingly, the majority of the participants, 15 participants, think their English language level was on top of the list of the most challenging elements in their SI classes. However, the other two options, the MSA level and the classroom use of MSA instead of dialectal Arabic were given equal percentages as demonstrated in the following chart.

Chart 1: Distribution of participants according to their choice of the most challenging element in SI classes

Three main themes emerged from the respondents' answers who chose "your level of English language". The first theme is their lack of the knowledge of the English language terminology in different contexts as highlighted by the majority of the respondents (seven respondents). It can be understood from their answers that in SI classes, a certain level (high level) of English language was requisite, yet they do not consider their English level as high as the task requires. They also pinpointed that the English language vocabulary is a challenging element in SI classes as it plays a vital role; therefore, interpreters have to update themselves of the new terminology that emerges.

The second most common theme that the respondents' highlighted (four respondents) is the fact that English is neither their L1, nor even their second language, which made their level of English language a challenging element in their SI classes. Two respondents referred to the direction of interpreting (into B interpreting) when asked to explain why English was the challenging element in SI classes. They stated that it was challenging to them to interpret from MSA into English as they referred to English as the target language. In other words, according to the two respondent's answers, interpreting into an active language, in this case into English, seems to be challenging.

The third and the last area that arose from the answers of two respondents who explained why their level of English language as the most challenging element in SI classes is multi-tasking, speaking and listening to what have been said while they were speaking.

Concerning the two remaining options of the open-ended question, students' level of MSA did not seem to be as challenging as their level of English according to the survey results. Furthermore, classroom use of MSA instead of dialectal Arabic also was not considered a constraint in comparison to their English language proficiency.

It is important to highlight that all the five participants in the Skype interviews are among the fifteen respondents who previously stated in the online survey that their level of English language was the most challenging element in their SI classes. This could be considered as one of the limitations as the other opinions were not discussed. The four other respondents among the six who chose the other two options (your MSA level and classroom use of MSA instead of DA) were not available when they were approached and asked to participate in the interviews. Concerning the other two, one of them did not leave any contact details when asked in the questionnaire, whereas I interviewed other one but the data they provided was irrelevant and therefore could not be used, thus I had to replace it with another interview.

As discussed above, the survey data show that the lack of L2 proficiency proved to be a major challenge in SI classes. However, that raises an interesting question; the graduates have studied English for four years at middle school, three years at high school and three years as a speciality at university before being enrolled in the two-year Translation and Translation Studies MA degree, yet they still find it hard to interpret simultaneously from and into English. Is this issue related to the quality of the learning of English or does the module have to focus more on L2 language instruction? In this light, Shaw, Grbic, and Franklin (2004, p.70) refer to the phase between L2 learning and interpreting pedagogy as the "transition phase". This phase can be defined as "that period during which students begin to apply language learning to interpretation" (Shaw, Grbic, and Franklin, 2004, p.70).

The transition phase may be critical as SI students may experience self-doubt once they find themselves indulged in the interpreting process with the presumption of the two working languages' mastery (Shaw, Grbic, and Franklin, 2004). Consequently, Shaw, Grbic, and Franklin (2004) strongly encourage a shift to a learner-centred pedagogy in which educators consider students' feedback to prepare them for a smooth transition. Bartłomiejczyk (2009) argues that beginners at their interpreting early stage need to be aware that they are expected to listen to the source text, analyse the message and render it in the target language rather than transcoding words.

Furthermore, Shaw, Grbic, and Franklin (2004, p.70) argue “many interpreting instructors face similar problems of students who start their interpretation classes with an insufficient command of their working languages (including their mother tongue)”. The context of this study is a prototype of this argument as both the survey and the interview data show that the graduates had a shortage in English as well as MSA, that is to say, they faced a dual problem. The participants emphasized the importance of practice and training in improving their SI skills but at the same time considered their lack of English language terminology as the main challenge of SI. However, the question is whether this kind of shortage is teachable and would trainings and classroom practice help resolve the language deficiencies the students face?

Shaw, Grbic, and Franklin (2004, p.74) note that “it is surprising that remedial activities developed to meet the student’s inadequate language competence are often seen as lying beyond the realm of the interpretation classroom. Rather, remediation is assumed to belong in the area of foreign language pedagogy”. As reported by the participants, most of the challenges they faced in interpreting are attributed to their linguistic deficiencies in both working languages, consequently a significant improvement could be observed if educators and curriculum designers would consider including language instruction in interpreting programs.

The table below illustrates the participants’ perceived MSA writing and oral language proficiencies according to their answers when they were asked to choose between five options: excellent, good, satisfactory, poor and very poor.

The participants	MSA writing proficiency	MSA oral proficiency
IP1	Excellent	Excellent
IP2	Good	Good
IP3	Satisfactory	Satisfactory
IP4	Good	Good
IP5	Excellent	Excellent

Table 18: The participants’ MSA writing and oral language proficiencies

Overall, the participants’ responses showed that they believed they had a very good command of MSA. However, when they were asked in the interviews about the impact of Arabic diglossia on their SI practice, the common answer was that the absence of MSA in daily life interactions made it harder to interpret from and into MSA. Although most of the participants in the survey found that English was the key problem they also found that, the second huge problem is MSA

when delved deeper into the interviews. This creates an extremely big problem, as each way is problematic.

In other words, the infrequent use of MSA in daily life interactions results in the lack of spontaneous use of MSA when interpreting simultaneously, and given the time constraints embodied in this mode of interpreting, the interpreter needs more time to think about grammar and vocabulary, which is particularly difficult in SI. The participants may think they have a good level of MSA in general but the MSA used in SI could be more formal or the vocabulary used might be specialised depending on the subject being interpreted. Another point that is worth highlighting is that one's linguistic competence in natural and spontaneous real-life settings, where no mental load is imposed, might differ from interpreting, as the interpreter is listening in a source language, translating in their mind and then speaking in the target language while listening to what have been said when they were speaking. It is incredibly difficult as it is hard to increase their English language levels. In other words, language instruction does not precede SI and it is not part of the SI programmes, thus the students need to make personal effort to increase their English language levels outside the classroom.

As Fraihat et al (2013, p.185) assert “simultaneous interpreting requires pacing all the effort listening, comprehending and coordinating, and finally TL oral production opportunely with no intervals”. That is why SI “requires a high level of proficiency in the working languages” (Fraihat et al, 2013, p.176) so that the interpreter has to deal with other SI constraints rather than struggling with linguistic ones. In other words, SI is an instant oral translation and interpreters are required to cope with the cognitive load that SI involves, which means linguistic deficiencies in either languages could be problematic. However, to have even small linguistic deficiencies in both languages is even more problematic. That is to say, if the students have linguistic deficiencies in both working languages, SI would be extremely hard as they would struggle with both comprehension and production phases.

In addition to that, if the students have an exceptional English level, MSA would be less of a problem, unlike facing linguistic difficulties in both working languages. Nevertheless, competence as a term is controversial; it is somehow hard to provide an accurate answer to questions related to defining one's competence in a given language and the answer is more likely to be subjective. This point will be discussed further in this chapter. That is a key finding, as English was considered an issue in the questionnaire and MSA as an issue as well in the interviews.

A follow up question was asked after analysing the questionnaire data as I realised that the open-ended questionnaire question, in which the respondents were asked to select one most challenging element in their SI classes among three options, was not precise. That is to say, the majority of the respondents chose “your level of English” as the most challenging element, yet it was not clear in which interpreting direction they encountered more difficulties in their level of English. In this light, the respondents were asked a follow up question to get more details regarding the most challenging element they faced in SI classes and its impact on the direction of interpreting. Five respondents showed willingness to share their experience and provided more details. It has to be pointed out that the five respondents, who replied to this question, chose “your level of English” earlier in the questionnaire.

According to the respondents’ answers it can be concluded that the vocabulary is more important than the direction of interpreting, that is to say, interpreters are required to have a rich vocabulary in both the source and the target languages.

According to the survey results, it can be understood that the English language vocabulary was the common point among the five respondents’ justifications when they were asked what interpreting direction was more challenging. Whether they were interpreting from English into Arabic or from Arabic into English, the specific vocabulary was a significant challenge. In other words, regardless of the direction of interpreting, when one does not have a rich vocabulary in one of the languages involved in the interpreting process, this affects either their understanding (if they are interpreting from that language) or the product of interpreting (if they are interpreting into that language). As stated earlier, the questionnaire was helpful as it helped to build up and review the interview questions before proceeding with the qualitative data collection. In the following section, the fundamental findings of the interviews along with the data analysis will be discussed. The follow up interviews allowed the participants to share their experiences, insights, attitudes and reflect on the SI module with its positives and negatives, as well as their recommendations for improving the crucial issues they highlighted on both the administrative and the personal level. In other words, the use of mixed methods was extremely beneficial in this complex area of study and interdisciplinary research. As mentioned earlier, my interview questions were shaped by the questionnaire results.

5.2. Findings from the Participants' Interview Analysis

5.2.1. Learning about Diglossia in SI

Among the five graduates interviewed, four of them acknowledged that they were unaware of diglossia before the interview and that they had not heard about it before. On the other hand, one participant provided a definition of diglossia that showed that they have a misconception of the concept.

Conversely, the participants demonstrated a clear awareness of the fundamental differences between MSA and DA when asked to. The common answers involved the area of use, that is to say the exclusive use of MSA in academic settings and the use of DA in daily life interactions. In this respect, IP3 and IP4 respectively acknowledge: “for the modern I barely use it so like I don’t have much things to say about it. Emm, so the differences I might be summed up in the use of the modern Arabic exclusively in, is mostly used in academic settings”, “MSA we use it, as natives, just in the academic areas but we don’t use it in our daily life, we use the colloquial Arabic”.

In addition to that, as exemplified in the following quotations, others claim that the key differences lie in the register, the feature of each variety: spoken, written as well as grammar differences. In this respect, IP1 states: “*emm well we surely have many differences at the level of the written or the oral language, maybe also at the level of formality*” whereas IP5 claims “*I would like to start firstly by grammar, this is the first difference because standard Arabic has let’s say its own grammar and its own strict grammar. For let’s say local Arabic it is just like spoken it means its feature is spoken not written*”.

Moreover, IP2 claims “*I think it is the difference in grammar, in the use of the words, in the context and so on*”.

To these differences, IP5 adds the fact that MSA is a unified form among all Arabic speakers unlike spoken dialects, which might be unintelligible even among people of the same country. IP5 says:

Also the difference for standard Arabic we can say is understood by all people of the Arab world and even Arabic learners from other countries who are not native speakers of the language, but if we talk about our local Arabic whether it is Algerian spoken dialects or Touggourt spoken dialects, Touggourt means the city where I’m living, we

find that Touggourti or Algerian are only understood by few people who can understand the language and even in the same country, we can find another one from another city can't understand the language.

According to the participants' answers, they seem to be aware of the existence of diglossia in the Arabic language but unaware of it as a concept or as a linguistic phenomenon. Accordingly, they were asked to explain how these differences, in other words Arabic diglossia, affected their SI classroom practice. The common answer was that the absence of MSA in daily life interactions made it harder to interpret from and into MSA in SI classes. It might be that the students required further training and support from the programme as well to perform well. IP1 confirms that these differences had an impact on their SI practice, *“yes, yes, it did yes, because as you said that sometimes we do not use the, it's not sometimes it's actually all the time, we do not use the standard Arabic in our daily life but while interpreting, we are asked or the standard Arabic usage is required”*. Furthermore, IP2 mentions their lack of MSA vocabulary made the interpreting task in some way challenging *“yes, it makes the translation of the SI somehow difficult because sometimes we don't know the exact words, of the word in Arabic in standard Arabic”*.

On the other hand, IP5 states *“yes of course, I find it harder in let's say in standard Arabic in comparison to interpreting into spoken, Algerian spoken Arabic”*. Then adds:

The amount or the big amount of words in Arabic and vocabulary and even some idioms in the Arabic language make it harder for me to translate, but when I translate into Algerian spoken Arabic, I mean colloquial or local language, let's say I'm not restricted to grammar because in standard Arabic I'm let's say limited by grammar, I'm forced to use grammar correctly to let's say deliver the meaning but in local Arabic I have just to speak without even respecting the grammar and I can deliver the message.

In other words, the infrequent use of MSA in daily life interactions results in the lack of spontaneous use of MSA when interpreting simultaneously, and given the time constraints embodied in this mode of interpreting, the interpreter needs more time to think about grammar and vocabulary, which may not be possible in SI.

Consistent with IP1, IP2 and IP5's answers, IP4 shares the same argument and mentions the two points:

Yes, sure and clearly, it affected our interpreting. Because if you are a native, we are natives in using our Arabic language, so since we are using more than maybe 70% in our daily life in colloquial Arabic, so it will be very difficult to use MSA when interpreting into another language. You have to have a big baggage in your memory or in your mind in order to convey the meaning by interpreting into another language.

Thus, the participants agreed that MSA use in SI classes imposes a mental load on the students of SI.

Furthermore, three participants acknowledged that they prefer to use MSA when communicating with Arabic speakers from outside the Great Maghreb to ensure comprehension. IP3 states *“I used modern so to avoid being misunderstood or, I use standard Arabic yes, modern standard Arabic. Because I find it more, better because I want always to avoid being misunderstood that’s why I use Arabic”*. IP4 shares this argument and explains *“I prefer to use MSA better than our colloquial maybe because they don’t understand what we are saying to them when we use our colloquial, it would be better to use MSA than the colloquial”*. In line with IP3 and IP4’s arguments, IP2 also attributes the use of MSA with Arabic speakers from other countries to comprehension. IP2 states *“yes, I always use the standard Arabic with the people from other countries, from the Arabic countries”*. When asked why would they prefer MSA use, IP2 explained:

There is a difference between, not the accent but.. different in the use of the words for example in Morocco they use some words which are not common in Algeria, we use some words which are not common or they don’t understand it so we need to use a common language or a language which is common between us which is Arabic language, Arabic standard language.

On the other hand, IP1 confirms that they do not prefer using MSA: *“actually no even though I have friends from different Arab countries but I always try to use the colloquial language or the Algerian Arabic”*. When asked if they understand the Algerian spoken Arabic, IP1 replied *“they can understand it because I do not use words which are very difficult for example words which are used only in Algeria”*. In this case, IP1 might be unconsciously referring to Educated Spoken Arabic or Middle Arabic.

IP5 provides a more detailed explanation in which they seem to be unconsciously using ESA as IP1's argument illustrates but adds that the choice of the language variety depends on the setting, differentiating between social media and formal emails as an example. IP5 explains

In social media I always don't use standard Arabic I'm always using a language which is mixed between standard Arabic and let's say, because as you know our Algerian accents or our Algerian Arabic are somehow harder for the other let's say Arabic from Egypt and other countries. That's why I prefer to use, I avoid standard Arabic but not exactly standard Arabic, it is a mixture between standard Arabic and some Algerian Arabic or some even Egyptian let's say, gulf Arabic so they can understand me. That is if we talk about social media or if we talk about something informal but if I am dealing with emails or something formal like employment interview on Skype or has something related to jobs or academic research or something formal I always prefer to use standard spoken Arabic.

The participants' responses continue to show their awareness of the fundamental differences between MSA and DA, the majority claim that they feel uncomfortable and awkward when using MSA in informal settings. However, IP1 associates MSA use among friends and family with pride and comfort, *"I feel too proud to use the standard Arabic, even with my friends in the, we have a kind of for example clubs or something like this, we feel more comfortable to use standard Arabic"*. Similarly, IP2 uses both forms in different informal settings *"with my friends I use the standard Arabic but with my family I use the colloquial language"*. IP2 proceeded to justify their choice by asserting:

I feel it is easy to write or to talk or chat with people with the standard Arabic I don't know why but with my family maybe because the level of the education of my sister for example, with my sister I need to use the colloquial language, she cannot understand the standard Arabic.

In this regard, Cote (2009) states that MSA is acquired through formal education exclusively and it is the only form of Arabic taught in all stages of formal education which means that those who do not receive formal education in MSA will not be able to grasp or use this form of language.

5.2.2. Interpreting from and into MSA

Following the definition of the AIIC (Association Internationale des Interprètes de Conférence), a “B” language is a language that the interpreter speaks fluently and therefore is an active language. Interpreters can work into B language but in comparison to consecutive interpreting, they tend to prefer working into B in consecutive interpreting as this mode of interpreting is not as instant as SI. In other words, according to the participants’ answers, interpreting into an active language, in this case into English, seems to be challenging. This is the reason why the majority of the participants argue that English into MSA is their interpreting direction preference.

Consequently, in order to investigate in depth the graduates’ attitudes towards MSA and its use in SI, they were asked about their SI experience and whether MSA use was among the challenges embodied in SI.

When the participants were asked about their interpreting direction preferences, from MSA into English and vice versa, one participant claimed that they prefer to interpret from MSA into English due to their lack of the relevant English vocabulary.

The other four participants preferred to interpret from English into MSA because their MSA vocabulary is richer than their English vocabulary.

Another fundamental finding is that all the participants consider MSA as an L1 despite its infrequent use in daily life interactions. IP3 states:

I have always considered Arabic as my first language. It is a first language but it is exclusively used in formal use and academic use, when it comes to communication we use colloquial Arabic. It is exclusively, very exclusively used in formal settings, like schools and for legal documents, but when it comes to communication we use colloquial, it is always colloquial. People tend to use it more and find it a bit weird to use MSA in their daily life.

Consistent with IP3’s argument, IP4 claims “no, no, I consider MSA as the first language but even if we aren’t using it in our communication”. Furthermore, IP5 confirms “my first language is the standard Arabic, and I will never consider local Arabic or local Algerian Arabic as the very first language”.

On the other hand, IP1 and IP2 have a slightly different justification for considering MSA as an L1. IP1 claims:

It is a first language, why because I was born in a family in which we used to use the standard Arabic in our daily life. Because my father and my mother were teachers so yes when I was a child I faced many problems actually because of this, this ... this thing it means using the standard Arabic in school or something like this but for me yes it is a mother language. Because at home we use standard Arabic.

Furthermore, IP2 states “*it is the language of Quran*”. In this respect, Ferguson (1959) stipulates that the high variety of language, MSA in this case, is perceived ‘superior’ to the low variety, and that the preference of the high variety is due to its association with religion. In this light, it is evident that the participants consider MSA as their L1 despite the fact that dialectal Arabic “is acquired naturalistically as mother tongue” whereas MSA “requires formal schooling” (Aronin and Singleton, 2008, p.23). Consistent with Ferguson’s (1959) viewpoint, Aronin and Singleton (2008) elucidate that MSA is derived from CA, which is the language of Quran, which accordingly explains why MSA is held in high the self-esteem. On the other hand, dialectal Arabic requires no schooling, this justifies why all the participants consider MSA as their L1.

It follows from the above discussion that the concept of the first language is deeply contestable. As a result, the classification of the working languages involved in interpreting suggested by the AIIC (Association Internationale des Interprètes de Conférence), is questionable. In other words, could MSA be considered as an L1 even if it is not spoken spontaneously in daily communications and therefore be regarded as an ‘A’ language in interpreting? Pöchhacker (2016, p.180) explains “among the contentious issues that have been discussed in the literature, but not resolved, are SI training into the B-language”.

Concerning considering MSA as a challenge in SI classes, IP1 who previously asserted that they use MSA frequently among family at home claimed “*it wasn’t, it was too easy for me to use it in class*”. IP3 and IP4 respectively agreed that:

I think it is not a challenge, because as an interpreter or a learner you should learn both languages. So, learning and acquiring new words and enriching your vocabulary would solve this. As a learner you are asked to do this rather than consider it as challenge, you should challenge yourself and update and enrich your vocabulary,

And “*Emm in our class, no, I didn’t consider the use of MSA as a challenge*”.

However, IP5 considers MSA use in SI as a challenge attributing this to their deficiency in MSA vocabulary.

Yes , of course it is challenging (...), because we studied Arabic in school for years but we didn’t use the correct Arabic but when we went to MA classes at university for the specialty of translation and interpreting we discovered a lot of things in Arabic that we couldn’t see before, that we couldn’t be aware of before. So that’s why we found it like we are beginning as second parts of our language. I cannot say that starting from zero or it is like a new language but at least second parts because we were not aware about let’s say the correct vocabulary (...). I mean from my speech that it is challenging because Arabic is one of the hardest languages in the world even for the native speakers not just for the non-native speakers. It is challenging in many aspects, grammar, morphology, in its oral aspects, and especially for translation and interpreting students especially SI because it is hard to find the right word in the right context. If the student or the translator was not prepared before and was not like, or has not sorry, like the very big amount of vocabulary and knowledge and cultural knowledge, let’s say accuracy and fluency of standard Arabic, yes it’s challenging.

IP2 also perceives MSA use in SI classes challenging, “*because in our daily life we use colloquial language, then when we enter to the class, we are obliged to use the standard Arabic so there is what we call it تصادم ‘clash’* . According to IP2’s answer, the duality of the Arabic language, Arabic diglossia, seems to have a negative impact on SI students’ classroom performance. In this regard, IP2 considered the lack of knowledge about the topic that students will deal with as the main challenge and states “*the main problem was that you don’t have idea about the topic*”. In this sense, Díaz-Galaz, Padilla, and Bajo (2015) conducted an experimental study to explore what impact preparation has on SI by comparing professional interpreters and interpreting students. The working languages involved in this study were Spanish, the participants’ A language which they interpreted into, and English, they language they interpreted from. The participants were asked to perform two SI tasks of presentations; the only difference between the two tasks is that in one of them the participants were provided with preparation materials in advance. The study highlighted the vital role of advance preparation as both groups performed better when they were given the opportunity to familiarise themselves with the materials (Díaz-Galaz, Padilla, and Bajo, 2015). Nolan (2005, p.18) also

pinpoints the importance of preparation in conference interpreting “gaining familiarity with the subject matter to be discussed at an upcoming assignment is important”. Nolan (2005) highlights the importance of having a full mastery of the TL along with good command and understanding of the SL in both translation and interpreting tasks. Nolan (2005, p.3) argues that “for most interpreters, the target language will be his or her native tongue”.

Participants who did not regard MSA use in SI classes as a challenge, considered their lack of the specific vocabulary as the main challenge. As IP1 claims “*I have been always facing the problem of the lack of vocab. In English, in interpreting from English into Arabic*”, Whereas IP3 asserts:

The challenge is the vocabulary and being unable to understand the context clearly and culture is always the... especially when dealing with literary texts. Yeah when dealing with literary texts, as I've said earlier some contexts are really culturally bounded so we need to be aware of the original text or speech or the discourse you are translating from.

Or their lack of vocabulary in both languages as illustrated in the following quotation

The main challenge, as we have seen with our teachers at university, is the lack of vocabulary, it was so hard when we didn't find the equivalent, the clear or the total equivalent directly in order to convey the meaning, so it's the main challenge for me (...). In all of them, maybe because in one moment you are interpreting from English into Arabic after a moment you start interpreting from Arabic into English so maybe the main challenge is the lack of vocabulary in both languages (IP4).

Whether it is the lack of MSA or English vocabulary students of SI seem to be facing difficulties at the linguistic level. Kalina (2000, p.4) explains:

The linguistic skills of interpreters have to be excellent, which means more than being ‘fluent’ in one’s working languages. They include not only command of the general or conversational but also specialised languages such as banking, medical or data processing language, differences in usage, style, register, cultural norms and peculiarities etc. (declarative and semantic knowledge).

Interpreting in general and SI in particular necessitates high skills including proficiency in both working languages. However, according to the participants’ answers, they were struggling to

meet even this fundamental requirement, which is MSA and English fluency. Thus, this study was conducted to explore graduates' attitudes on this matter and investigate to what extent they are aware of the nature of the challenges they were facing when interpreting simultaneously in their SI classes.

Therefore, participants suggested several recommendations to enrich one's vocabulary. IP1 claims "*reading, yes because I think that through reading I could, I could get over this problem of the lack of vocabulary*". IP3 also encourages interpreters to strengthen their vocabulary in both languages involved in interpreting "*interpreters should always update their knowledge about both languages and new words, and try to study all the aspects of the language*". On the other hand, IP4 similarly highlights the importance of practice in enriching interpreters' vocabulary in both languages:

To resolve this challenge you have to practice more and more and you have to maybe to memorise as much as you can vocabulary and the equivalent of words. And you have to practice by using channels and by listening to other interpreters in order to improve your English or your Arabic.

IP2 equally emphasizes the importance of practice in order to help resolve the challenges embodied in the task of SI "*practise, maybe practise. Practise more*". Moser-Mercer (2001) asserts that practice and experience are considered as the main elements of skill acquisition, therefore producing cognitive changes contributing to easing cognitive challenges that are present in complex tasks, and SI is no exception (as cited in Moser-Mercer, 2008, p.7).

On the other hand, IP5 expands the challenges embodied in SI and tackles four areas such as time constraints, the direction of interpreting (English into Arabic is easier), the context, and the culture, as shown below:

The first challenge is the time because in SI we interpret by seconds and by words not just by let's say we don't have so much time to think. The second challenge depends as I told you before on to whom I am translating, if I am translating to simple workers or to my little brother or to..., it is easier to use let's say local Algerian Arabic but if I am translating into standard Arabic in academia or in a conference, it is harder because we have, I have very few seconds or part of seconds to interpret a lot of words and a lot meanings and choose them, analyse them and apply them to deliver my message to the listener or to the receiver. The third challenge I consider, as I told you before,

depends if I am translating from English into Arabic or translating from Arabic into English. If I'm translating into English as a second language into Arabic it is easier for me. But if I'm translating from my native language, which is Arabic into English which is my second language I find it harder this is the third challenge. And also the context of the text (...). Also another point I can add is the cultural elements.

Accordingly, IP5 suggests some solutions to resolve the challenges embodied in SI focusing more on the administrative level rather than the personal level such as the use of new methods and technology as well as teacher selection and student admission criteria.

The departments of translation in Algeria should be more equipped and let's say more prepared (...). In every university, there should be a translation lab; this is the first one because in Ouargla University we didn't have a lab in our MA degree. So, because when I say lab I mean using the technology (...). The second thing I'll talk about preparation, by preparation I mean using the best, the best, the best teachers of let's say translation and interpreting or translation and interpreting at universities and especially the ones who have doctorate degrees. Because here I'm talking about their capacities, I'm talking about their ability, I'm talking about let's say, the experience they have to deliver that experience and that capacity to their students. So the second point I mean the teacher should be well selected because it is a hard specialty (...) this is another, I mean this is the third point, which is the methods and approaches that should be developed also. The other thing, which I emphasise on, is the selection of students (...). So here are not dealing with just English but English, Arabic and even more languages if available. So the challenge here is two languages that I have to master their grammar, structure, vocabulary, and even their culture. Because I see that, the students of translation and interpreting should be like, have a lot of amount of vocabulary and idioms concerning the cultural elements. I mean the culture of the students here plays a role and their level of standard Arabic and their level of English should be good that's why the administration should select the right students when accepting that in the MA degrees and doctoral degrees in interpreting (IP5).

When IP5 suggested translation and interpreting teacher selection, they mentioned that it would be preferred to assign teachers who hold a PhD degree in this field in order to ensure that students are getting their expertise. In this light, Weber (1989, p.8) states "another difficulty lies in the fact that most instructors of interpretation do not possess a Ph.D.". Then continues

to explain “I am definitely not advocating that all those who teach interpretation should obtain a doctorate, as I see it as a useful exercise only if it leads to a direct improvement of the teaching methods” (p.8). This argument is consistent with IP5’s point of view, as they believe that a complex area such as interpreting requires a competent teacher of interpreting that assumedly has a PhD. However, this is their opinion.

In addition to that, consistent with IP5’s call for integrating new methods in the SI module, Fernández (2005) argues “training programmes need to be developed in such a way that they reflect the latest tendencies in the profession” (p.120). As discussed earlier, the transition phase plays a vital role in preparing the students for the interpreting process by using preparatory exercises including “transfer exercises such as cloze tasks, sight translation/interpreting, dual tasking, simultaneous paraphrasing and shadowing for beginning interpretation” (Shaw, Grbic, and Franklin, 2004, p.72). These exercises could help students familiarise themselves with SI process, mainly multi-tasking, before starting the real SI tasks. In this respect, Bartłomiejczyk (2009) also highlights the importance of beginning with translation and less complex modes of interpreting before indulging in SI “it is also often suggested that other types of translation tasks, i.e. sight translation and CI, should be used as preparatory exercises for SI” (p.415).

Pöchhacker (2016) discusses interpreting pedagogy including five main aspects: curriculum, selection, teaching, assessment and meta-level training. Pöchhacker (2016, p.177) refers to curriculum as an “organizational structure framing and guiding teaching practice”. Furthermore, he emphasises the key requirements that interpreting training programs require before candidate admission. Overall, the list consists of “knowledge (of languages and of the world), cognitive skills (relating to analysis, attention and memory) and personality traits (including stress tolerance and intellectual curiosity)” (p.180). Pöchhacker (2016, p.180) proceeds to explain that in the case of conference interpreting, “language acquisition must precede training in interpreting” however, underlines also the importance of cultural knowledge and competence. On the other hand, when discussing SI teaching, he refers to ‘dual-task’ characterised exercises in which students are introduced to listening while performing another task, giving the example of reading aloud or counting backwards. Pöchhacker (2016, p.184) comments on dual-tasks and asserts “the performance of cognitively unrelated tasks does not approximate the processing demands of SI”. In the case of SI classes at the University of Ouargla, dual-tasks were used at an early stage to familiarise SI students with the nature of this mode of interpreting that requires multi-tasking. In fact, listening while performing any

other task such as reading or counting backwards could be mentally exhausting and does not necessarily introduce students to listening and speaking simultaneously. Shadowing also was used for the same purpose, it refers to “the immediate repetition of auditory input in the same language” Pöchhacker (2016, p.184). However, in shadowing, “a crucial element is missing in those exercises: the active analysis of the speech input” (Kurz, 1992 as cited in Pöchhacker, 2016, p.185). In this light, Pöchhacker (2016) argues that didactic proposals aim to give less attention to the product and focus on the process, to teach interpreting students how to solve and deal with lexical and structural constraints, as well as to make trainings as approximate as possible to actual interpreting conditions. On the other hand, Bartłomiejczyk (2009) argues that despite the claims that shadowing skills might differ from SI skills and “even if not conducive to building up interpreting skills, shadowing in a foreign language may well perfect this language in terms of pronunciation, intonation etc.” (p.414).

According to the participants’ experiences, multi-tasking was not at the top of the list of the difficulties they encountered when interpreting. That is why they did not discuss the importance of preliminary exercises when they were asked to suggest recommendations for improvement. However, multi-tasking could be much more problematic when it is paired with inadequate command of the two working languages, which can lead to experiencing considerable difficulties when interpreting. In other words, multi-tasking is a universal challenge that every novice interpreter has to deal with, but interpreting from and into a diglossic language with deficiencies in the other working language as well as multi-tasking is what makes SI in the context of this study more complicated.

5.2.3. Awareness of Arabic Diglossia

The majority of the participants considered MSA and DA as two separate languages, whereas only two participants perceive them as one language.

However, IP3 thinks that DA cannot replace MSA in interpreting because it has a poor vocabulary “*I think it would be more challenging, because you, when you deal with let’s say when dealing with specialised texts you may not find the right words, the equivalent*”. While IP3 regards the poor DA vocabulary as an inconvenient, IP5 perceives it as an advantage as it enables the interpreter to interpret easily because there is a limited choice of words and less grammar restrictions. IP5 asserts:

Of course translation would be much easier if I translate from let's say the second language into my colloquial language or local colloquial language because it has just a few words and I don't need that strictness of grammar, structure and so on. So it is easier, much easier.

On the other hand, IP4 asserts that it would be easier to interpret into DA as it is the L1 “*maybe it can be easy if you understand the source language because by using colloquial Arabic it became our mother tongue by the way, it will be easy to use it directly after listening to the source in English*”.

Similarly, IP1, who is exposed to MSA at home, claims that “*maybe for some, for some those who use the spoken Arabic for example for those who do not use really the standard Arabic in daily life, in their daily life yes. Maybe it's going to be easier for them from and into the spoken Arabic*”. However, IP2 prefers the use of MSA in SI classes “*because it is the common language, because it is international language, we can consider it as international language. If we interpret into colloquial language we cannot understand it*”. IP2 explains that using DA in education would make SI classes less formal:

In teaching? It was very bad, ok. It is very bad to use Arabic. A lot of Arabic because the students will make it as casual, they will use a lot of Arabic and the session will turn into Arabic session not English, they will use a lot of Arabic.

In other words, in terms of function, the characteristics of the DA do not allow it to be used in formal education since it is a low variety used only for communication in informal settings. However, in terms of interpreting, it would be easier to interpret into one's L1.

5.2.4. Possibility of Reducing the Impact of Diglossia in SI Classes

One of the key research aims attempts to find out how the participants viewed Arabic diglossia and what are their perceptions of replacing MSA by ESA in education.

IP1 and IP2 were the only ones who think that Arabic diglossia has a negative impact on the pedagogy of SI. IP1 claims “*yes I think that it has a kind of negative impact also, yes it's considered as a point of weakness, it means teaching interpreting into or from a language which is not used in the students' daily life*”. On the other hand, IP2 asserts:

I think it is negative because when we want to interpret into Arabic sometimes we think of words which are colloquial and we use them in the context and so on for example

you are in a situation where you translate words or speech or a video, you use some words which belong to colloquial language not standard Arabic. So that makes the interpreting somehow difficult. I think it's negative.

IP2 explains that diglossia has a negative impact on SI because students in SI use DA more spontaneously.

In contrast, the majority of the participants highlight that Arabic diglossia has a positive impact; IP3 asserts that diglossia challenges the students to improve their MSA level “*the impact is I think positive because it pushes me to develop my vocabulary in MSA*”. Correspondingly, IP4 agrees with IP3 “*yes, directly by using the standard Arabic, from my point of view is better than to use colloquial Arabic, at least it makes us be familiar with the language and even for finding the equivalent in MSA is better than in colloquial Arabic*”.

IP5 states that by interpreting from and into MSA in SI classes, the students will be more aware of the Arabic language and its varieties:

I find it a very positive point, a good point because using this method can make the students of interpreting and translation be aware and much aware of his/her language you see? Emm and make a difference between local Arabic and standard Arabic and we give the students the opportunity to know more what's inside our local Arabic and what's inside the standard Arabic, we give the student the opportunity to develop his/her diglossia (...). The positive point here I say that students should develop their own standard Arabic very well and be aware of many things that they were not aware of before using Arabic in interpreting, it doesn't matter if it is standard or local Arabic. And those methods should be applied in classes at university to enhance the translation students' proficiency.

Participants were given a brief explanation of ESA before being asked about their opinions on replacing MSA by ESA in education.

IP1 thinks that the replacement of MSA by ESA in education is problematic and suggests introducing MSA use more often in daily life interactions. On the other hand, IP3 suggests using ESA as helping tool rather than replacing MSA completely by ESA. IP4 affirms that they are totally against this replacement. Similarly, IP5 asserts that ESA replacement would corrupt MSA unless we use ESA as a helping tool. Moreover, IP2 thinks that MSA replacement by

ESA in education would create confusion, as students will be exposed to many varieties belonging to the same language, each with a distinct role.

5.2.5. Experience of the SI Classes

The majority of the participants assert that they did not find the SI module helpful due to poor equipment, old teaching methods and insufficient time devoted to the SI module. In contrast, IP5 states that they benefited from the SI module, but invites Algerian universities to use equipment that is more advanced.

Therefore, participants were asked to give recommendations for improving the module based on their personal experiences. IP2 emphasizes the need of equipment and practice in order to improve the SI module *“we need materials, this module needs the use of a lot of materials, a lot of practice”*.

IP3 perceives that more time should be devoted to the SI module *“as I said to use more relevant methods, use the new technology and give SI more interest and more time”*. Similarly, IP1 also highlights the importance of devoting more time to this module and adds students' prior training in both languages before studying this module as a recommendation. In this respect, IP1 asserts:

Yes, well, emm first, it would be better to before getting in interpreting from and into another language it would be better to make students under training, in a training in both languages that they are going to translate from and into, this is one of the recommendations. And also devoting more time for this activity.

On the other hand, IP5 suggests teacher and student selection, use of technology and prior tests to evaluate students' levels in both languages. Asserting *“the selection of teachers, the level of teachers I mean they should be very capable, I've talked about the technological advancements, it is important. I've talked about making some tests in translation, some tests in Arabic and some tests in English and some tests in culture”*.

In line with IP5's suggestion regarding the necessity of prior tests to student admission, the Monterey Institute of International Studies (2021) requires students to take a test before being admitted to the course of translation and interpreting. The test consists of three phases evaluating the students' four skills. The first phase evaluates the reading and listening comprehension in 'A' and 'B' languages. The second phase aims at assessing speaking and

writing skills in each of the two languages, at this stage, students are asked to write an essay in each of the languages then provide a verbal comment. The third and last part of the test involves paraphrasing/retelling verbally and in writing between each of the languages (Language and Skills Test, n.d.). However, Pöchhacker (2016, pp.180-1) states “translation tests, in particular, have been rejected outright as a component of interpreter aptitude tests by some, defended by others, or questioned in hindsight”. Nevertheless, it might be difficult to some extent to evaluate candidates’ competence via tests, “aptitude tests have been criticized for their strong subjective component and, hence, lack of reliability” (Pöchhacker, 2016, p.181).

The participants’ weaknesses in their English vocabulary was widely considered the most challenging element when they were asked about the difficulties they encountered throughout their SI course. Consequently, they were asked to explain what impact their level of English had on their performance in SI classes. IP4 affirms *“for me I didn’t find myself good or excellent, maybe average. I can start doing this process but when I find a difficulty, I stop directly. And always it’s the lack of vocabulary in the English language”*. In addition, IP2 affirms that the lack of English vocabulary was an obstacle in SI classes *“negative because I couldn’t interpret, I have a lack of vocabulary. I face the problem of the lack of vocabulary that’s why when I want to interpret from English into Arabic, I face this problem, I don’t find the equivalent words”*.

As recommendations for the personal SI skill development, the participants highlighted some key elements that involve strengthening vocabulary in all domains through reading and practising. In this respect, IP1 states *“to develop my interpreting skills, emm as I said before, emm it’s, I would for example try to build a wider vocabulary in all contexts and in all domains, this is what I think”*. Furthermore, IP3 and IP4 respectively agreed on the importance of practice and training *“I should read more and train myself, do more training and read more”*, *“so to develop our interpreting skills, first of all I have to practice as much as I can by using channels, by listening and interpreting just with myself after that maybe by using a friend in order to be as an examiner”*. Consistent with IP3 and IP4’s arguments, IP2 encourages interpreters to practice, read and engage in trainings *“they must practice, practice, and practice. Read a lot of, a lot of books about vocabulary, specific vocabulary. That’s what we need as well as trainings”*.

IP5 also refers to reading in both languages as a way to improve vocabulary in both languages and encourages self-training as illustrated below:

I should let's say educate myself separately in the Arabic language because we don't know all the language (...). Also the same with English, if I everyday take to develop myself in interpreting I should be aware of the English vocabulary, and not just English vocabulary but English and Arabic terminology (...). Another point is to improve my interpreting skills is to read, read and read about culture especially culture. These are my three points to improve my skills. And also these are about the language level, the second level is self-training. Self-training in interpreting in interpreting itself, like I play a video and interpret, and put someone to control me or I record myself in a video to see what are the goods and the bads also to see and search for new methods and new approaches that are being used in interpreting nowadays.

In this respect, Bartłomiejczyk (2009) claims “the students have to be reminded repeatedly that one 90-minute class per week is not sufficient to acquire the skills necessary for SI over one or two semesters and, therefore, they need a lot of self-training outside classes” (p.416). This argument is consistent with the ones that my participants made as they underlined the importance of practice in improving their interpreting skills.

Reading and watching TV news were at the top of the list of the strategies suggested by the Monterey Institute of International Studies to help students of interpreting get prepared for the SI tasks (Ayob, 2010). In fact, learning foreign language strategies are largely similar to learning SI strategies as they both share ways of developing fundamental skills such as listening and speaking. The participants in this study addressed their English language vocabulary weaknesses and highlighted how these weaknesses were an obstacle while interpreting in both directions. Therefore, SI students can strengthen their English language vocabulary and improve their cultural knowledge through developing their L2 proficiency via reading, listening to the news and watching movies.

Most of the participants agreed that training plays an important role in helping interpreters gain experience in problem solving and therefore enhances their interpreting skills. In this regard, Ayob (2010) addresses the debatable question of whether training should be offered at a postgraduate level or at an undergraduate level. Although the latter is possible and applicable, Ayob (2010) claims that trainings at postgraduate levels are more common, attributing this to “the nature of the training, which requires a certain level of maturity, knowledge, and experience in a variety of fields. Individuals must also be mentally and physically ready to

undergo the tasks presented to them in the training, which, more often than not, are exhausting and stressful” (p.103).

It can be concluded from the participants’ answers that they were facing linguistic deficiencies in both languages, MSA and English, when interpreting. However, when discussing interpreting programs, Weber (1989) states that interpreting students are expected to be competent in both languages, therefore “NO language courses should be included in the curriculum, as students must be fluent in their languages before being admitted to the program” (p.14). This might be problematic in the Algerian context, given that the Arabic language is characterised by diglossia, MSA is not spontaneously spoken in daily life interactions, but it is still considered as students’ L1. English on the other hand is considered a foreign language. Consequently, it is to some extent hard to exclude language courses from interpreting pedagogy. Thus, diglossic languages need to be addressed differently, and language teaching could not be detached from interpreting pedagogy but rather needs to be increased.

The argument made by Weber (1989) three decades ago is questionable, mainly because interpreting teaching methods are evolving and as Nam (2018) points out “in recent years, the bridge between translator education and language teaching/learning has been subject to much attention” (p.248).

In this respect, Gile (2009) tackles the relationship between interpreting and language trainings. Gile (2009) states “a large number of interpreter training programs are part of or strongly associated with departments of modern languages where translator and interpreter training starts while language skills enhancement is still part of the curriculum” (p.221). However, when Gile (2009) referred to language skill enhancement, he did not specify what working languages (A, B or C) are involved. In Algeria, specifically at the University of Ouargla, the Master’s degree in Translation and Translation Studies is part of the department of Foreign Languages. Therefore, students study English for three years before starting their MA. In this case, they are expected to have a good command of their ‘B’ language (the English language), on the other hand, the Arabic language is not taught neither during the BA nor during the Master’s degree, presumably because it is considered as the students’ ‘A’ language. Consequently, students are required to be fluent in the Arabic language (MSA). It is worth highlighting that the participants of this study consider MSA as an L1, and therefore an ‘A’ language according to the AIIC classification. However, in reality MSA is not really an ‘A’ language because according to Cote (2009), it is nobody’s L1. In interpreting, it is by definition

incredibly hard to interpret within two-language combination in which none of them is an ‘A’ language but at the same time considered to be, which is far more problematic. For the participants in this study the real issue is interpreting simultaneously in two directions in the same module while not being fully competent in either of the languages (MSA and English).

Gile (2009) asserts that it is hard to base student admissions on the A, B and C language patterns, supporting his argument with three reasons. The first reason is, checking student language mastery is problematic because shortcomings may not be noticeable unless the student is working under severe cognitive pressure, and the strategies to deal with such weaknesses are not yet learnt. Furthermore, language proficiency can be achieved and improved through practice throughout the programme duration; therefore, assessing students’ competence at an early stage, before starting the course, might do an injustice to them. The final reason is, easing entry requirements in some programmes due to the market demand for certain language combinations can lead to admitting students who are incompetent in one or more working languages, which may affect students themselves resulting in failure or training institution diploma credibility loss (Gile, 2009).

In this regard, according to the participants’ answers, it is evident that they were not aware of their lack of competence in both languages until they started the SI classes, which consequently resulted in facing linguistic constraints when interpreting.

In this light, Gile (2009) suggests possible recommendations, which are as follows. The first one concerns introducing language enhancement courses. The second point tends to refer to students’ personal efforts to enhance their own linguistic skills including spending time abroad where the language they feel incompetent in is spoken or through reading, listening to the radio, watching television as well as practicing via exercises that help improve their language skills. Gile (2009) refers to Déjean Le Féal (1976) who suggests various exercises, which are listed below:

- “‘Complete reading’, which consists of reading a text sentence by sentence, and then repeating each sentence without looking at the text
- ‘Complete listening’, which consists in repeating sentences and linguistic structures heard from a native speaker in a foreign language
- Careful listening to the way native speakers unwittingly correct non-native speakers when they use clumsy constructions

- Occasionally concentrating on function words rather than on content words so as to learn their proper use
- Learning structures and idioms by heart
- ‘Shuttle exercises’ in which student try to seek systematically appropriate wordings in one language for ideas they hear in another” (pp.221-2).

English language terminology and culture shortages were the major challenges encountered by the participants. Therefore, the participants referred to reading and intensive practice as recommendations to resolve these challenges. However, according to the above discussion, listening is as important as reading and practice to interpreting students who aim to improve and expand their vocabulary.

It is significant to highlight the importance of the linguistic skills in interpreting. In this respect, Kalina (2000) asserts:

Among the prerequisites people generally think of as necessary for good interpreting are the linguistic skills, i.e. the knowledge of as many languages as possible, and being able to speak and listen at the same time. It is less widely appreciated that it is not only the purely linguistic skills (and even less the sheer number of languages) that are vital but the thorough knowledge of the cultures of the countries or regions concerned, including political, economic, social and ethnic differences, administrative structures, community life but also literature and the arts (p.3).

Fernandéz (2005) refers to Denissenko (1989) who favours retour interpreting to explain that comprehension of the source language is considered the most important phase in interpreting and therefore it can be easily achieved in the interpreter’s L1 (p.104). Fernandéz (2005) proceeds to highlight the importance of understanding, and asserts “this initial task has priority over all others, even though the final product may not be stylistically perfect” (p.104). Furthermore, Fernandéz (2005) argues that one’s L1 vocabulary is richer than their foreign language vocabulary, thus interpreting into-B tends to be easier due to having “fewer options to choose from” (p.104).

Following these arguments, while for the participants in this study, they regard their lack of the English vocabulary knowledge as a disadvantage, it may not be considered as a weakness when interpreting from MSA into English, in other words the direction of interpreting plays a vital

role in enhancing or reducing the difficulties encountered in SI. However, it can be a significant problem when interpreting from English into MSA.

It is to be noted that in the context of the current study, SI is taught as a module within the MA degree in Translation and Translation Studies and not as a separate diploma. Therefore, the parameters of entry requirements and the need to fulfil a certain language proficiency demands, such as the ones discussed earlier when tackling conference interpreting, might not be applicable to the case of SI as a module. This is due to several reasons. To begin with, only one hour and a half per week is devoted to the SI module, which in my opinion is considerably insufficient given the complexity of this mode of interpreting. Moreover, since the SI module is part of an MA degree belonging to a foreign language department and not an institute of interpreting, the availability of labs and equipment was very poor as the participants mentioned. Thus, this can be considered as limitation of this study and calls for future research as will be discussed in chapter 5. However, the structure of the programme could be adapted with the help of students' constructive feedback and therefore it is recommended to revisit the evaluation system and consider the students' comments.

“In everyday language, frequent words and expressions are encountered often and stimulation for maintenance is no problem. What is more problematic is stimulation for availability enhancement in less frequent words and expressions” (Gile, 2009, p.244). The argument that Gile made is consistent with what the participants in this study are stating. The participants agreed that the absence of MSA in daily life interactions made it harder to interpret from and into MSA as this form of language was not used spontaneously in SI. As IP1 notes *“sometimes we do not use the, it's not sometimes it's actually all the time, we do not use the standard Arabic in our daily life but while interpreting, we are asked or the standard Arabic usage is required”*. Furthermore, IP5 also confirms *“yes of course, I find it harder in let's say in standard Arabic in comparison to interpreting into spoken, Algerian spoken Arabic”*.

The fact that MSA words and expressions are hardly used in daily life interactions makes interpreting simultaneously from and into MSA even more problematic. Taking the example of interpreting from English into French and vice versa, these languages have the characteristics of ‘standard with dialects’ as Ferguson (1959, p.336) notes when he distinguished between diglossia and languages that have a standard form and a variety of dialects. Unlike the Arabic language, that has two forms, MSA and DA each with its distinct

role and area of use. SI seems to be less problematic when the two working languages are non-diglossic.

When the participants were asked in the interviews how they would develop as interpreters, reading, as a way to enrich their vocabulary, was the common answer, this may mean that SI skills have more to do with practice and self-instruction instead of being teachable. It is to be noted that the graduates' suggestions to improve SI skills were more concerned about linguistic expertise. However, interpreting expertise in general is very vague and cannot be explicitly identified (Liu, 2008).

Another question arises, are there certain skills particular to SI that interpreters have to learn or they are general skills that interpreting students already have. In this respect, Dillinger (1989) examined comprehension tasks during SI and during listening with regard to syntactic processing, proposition generation, and frame-structure processing and concluded that there is no significant difference between the two tasks. Dillinger (1989) outlines "comprehension in interpreting is not a specialized ability, but the application of an existing skill under more unusual circumstances" (as cited in Liu, 2008, p.161). This could mean that SI students had already difficulties in understanding the source language when interpreting or the unusual circumstances entailed in SI such as special working conditions, time constraints and cognitive load played a vital role in making SI harder.

The majority of the participants claimed that when English was the source text, they faced comprehension difficulties due to their lack of English vocabulary. This could be problematic since the comprehension phase in interpreting is very important. Furthermore, the interview data revealed that the graduates also faced difficulties in MSA production when it was the target language because they do not use this form of language spontaneously. Consequently, these two factors make SI extremely difficult.

5.3. Summary

It was clear from the above discussion that this study fills in the gap in the literature. This study endorses the fact that MSA is nobody's L1 has a negative impact on the pedagogy of SI. Among the key new findings, in accordance with the participants' perceptions, is that not only their lack of competence in MSA is what makes SI challenging, but also their lack of knowledge of the vocabulary in the English language in the various contexts.

In theory, the participants' L1 is DA. The tension however is that they perceive MSA as their L1. Nonetheless, as the literature reveals, MSA is not the first language of Arabic speakers (Cote, 2009; Dendane, 2010), and this form of language is used exclusively in formal settings. In the interviews, the participants explained that they perceive MSA as a prestigious form of language and therefore there is a strong bond between MSA and their identity.

Chapter 6: Conclusion

6.1. Introduction

This study aims to explore the potential implications of Arabic diglossia on my participants' perceptions of the pedagogy of simultaneous interpreting; in particular, the difficulties that students of SI may experience when interpreting simultaneously from a non-L1 to a non-L1, that is to say MSA-English-MSA.

The first chapter was an introductory chapter in which I introduced the aim of this research, established the significance of the topic, the rationale of this study and the outline of the thesis.

In Chapter two, I provided the contextual background of this research. The chapter also discussed the history of Algeria, and how it affected the language-planning situation and therefore the educational system.

In chapter three, I examined the literature, discussed and reviewed the previous studies in related fields in order to generate an understanding and knowledge of the perspectives, bodies of work that have been undertaken in the field of my research. This allowed me to gain a foundation of knowledge on the topic and hence identify the gap in the literature, which this study aims to fill.

In chapter four, I examined different methodologies I could have used and explored the research methods used in my field and the principles that underpin them. This allowed me to choose the approach that best matches my research objectives and the methodology that was most convenient to provide answers to the proposed research questions. Furthermore, in this chapter I introduced the sampling design, data collection and data analysis procedures.

Chapter five presented the data analysis, discussion and the findings derived from the online survey and the interviews. In this chapter, I interpreted, presented the findings in light of the previous studies and highlighted the new knowledge that my study generates.

In this chapter, answers to the key research questions will be presented along with the limitations of this study, autobiographical reflection, recommendations and possible future research areas.

6.2. Answers to the Research Questions

The findings are interpreted in terms of addressing the following research questions:

- What are the potential implications of Arabic diglossia on the pedagogy of SI from Arabic into English and vice versa for graduate Masters' students of SI at the University of Ouargla?
- What are SI learners' attitudes towards interpreting from and into MSA even if it is not their first language (L1)?
- To what extent are postgraduate learners of SI aware of Arabic diglossia?
- To what extent would a proposed ESA, as a mixture between Literary and Colloquial Arabic, help reduce the impact of diglossia in the field of teaching SI?
- What is the students' experience of the SI classes:
 - What impact did their perceived level of English had on their performance in SI classes?
 - What did the students consider to be positive about the class?
 - What recommendations would the students make for improvement?

This section will provide a brief overview of the findings of the study and their relationship to previous research in these areas.

- What are the potential implications of Arabic diglossia on the pedagogy of SI from Arabic into English and vice versa for graduate Masters' students of SI at the University of Ouargla?

Findings from questionnaires carried out among 21 respondents suggest that the students' English language level was at the top of the list of the most challenging elements in their SI classes.

However, English did not seem to be the only biggest challenge. When delving deeper into the interviews, the data show that MSA was also a significant issue in SI and was perceived as a hindering factor that influenced their SI classroom performance. The data show that Arabic diglossia has indeed several implications on the SI students' perceptions of the pedagogy of SI in Algeria. According to the students' experience, the fact that the formal form of Arabic (MSA) is exclusively used in formal education and barely used in daily life interactions

prevented them from using it spontaneously when interpreting simultaneously in class. These findings are broadly in line with those of researchers such as (among many others, Abdulaziz, 1986; Maamouri, 1998; Haeri, 2000; Cote, 2009; Ibrahim, 2009; Dendane, 2015) who claim that Arabic diglossia has a negative impact on the educational system in the Arabic speaking world. However, this study is the first one to interview graduates of schools who were interpreting from and into MSA in a multilingual society as complex as the Algerian one.

- What are SI learners' attitudes towards interpreting from and into MSA even if it is not their first language (L1)?

According to the participants' answers, despite the fact that MSA neither is used in daily life interactions among family and friends nor is the form of language they learnt at an early age, they still consider it as an L1. On the other hand, they admit that they found SI from English into MSA and vice versa incredibly challenging because they felt they did not have the competence that SI requires in either languages. In the Algerian educational context and in SI in particular, this could be very problematic. If the participants are not even aware of the fact that MSA is not their L1, yet still encounter difficulties using this form of language in SI classes, they are less likely to try to improve their MSA level. The online survey data show that eight the respondents claimed that they have an excellent MSA oral language proficiency, whereas nine respondents rated it as good. However, speaking a language is significantly different from interpreting from and into that language due to the difficulties embodied in SI as a task. This finding arose from my data.

This could be a dilemma as in the Arabic speaking world the Arabic language with its two forms is regarded as a native language regardless of the significant differences between these two forms that are not used interchangeably. In this respect, there seem to be a clear lack of understanding of the classification of the L1. All the participants claimed that they regard MSA as an L1, yet the majority also think that MSA and DA are two separate languages.

These findings differ from Dendane's (2010) argument, which states that MSA is nobody's L1. Furthermore, Holes (2004) argues that "the spoken Arabic dialects are the varieties of the language which all native speakers learn as their mother tongue before they begin formal education" (p.3). Moreover, the fact that there is a mutual unintelligibility between the local Arabic dialects, that tends to increase between distant Arabic speaking countries, proves that MSA and DA are indeed two separate languages.

My participants' paradoxical consideration of MSA as an L1 but at the same time regarding it distinct from their local dialects might be because they perceive MSA as "the language of power and control, as opposed to the language of intimacy and domesticity (the dialect)" (Holes, 2004, p.5). These are the characteristics of the high and the low varieties of diglossic languages as Ferguson (1959) points out, that is to say, the participants feel more prestigious when they refer to MSA as their L1 since they feel that it is superior to their local dialects. This is connected to the language status and identity.

Furthermore, Saidat (2010) states that non-standard Arabic is the Arabic native speakers' L1 "despite the fact that most of them deny that" (p.241). In his study, that investigates language attitudes in Jordan, Saidat (2010) found out that "Islam seems to be the greatest motivator for valuing MSA" and "there is a wide belief that NSA forms of Arabic do not have grammar and are leftovers of colonial systems" (p.235). These findings align with the findings of the present study in which the participants favour MSA and think that it should not be replaced by ESA in education. In addition to that, although the participants demonstrated a clear understanding of the L1 notion, which prevents MSA from being an L1 since it is not acquired from birth, they still deny that their L1 is one of the spoken dialects.

However, in the case of SI, there must be a clear distinction between the two forms of Arabic in order to know how to classify them properly since in SI one of the languages has to be the interpreter's L1. In this light, in diglossic languages, interpreters encounter more challenges. Dendane (2010, np) states that interpreters "will find difficulties not only in speaking that H variety in a spontaneous manner which the conference or the event normally requires, but also to convey equivalent meanings and expressions of the SL".

It is far more problematic when the students of SI interpret from and into languages for none of them is their L1, yet they still perceive MSA as their L1. This explains why they found SI very difficult and this is one of the fundamental findings of this research. Arabic diglossia has have an impact on the pedagogy of SI in Algeria as was perceived and reported by the participants of the interviews. Therefore, there is a possible link between language and SI pedagogy, the participants claimed that their MSA as well as their English level did not allow them to interpret efficiently. Hence, there is a need to review the quality of language instruction in the Algerian universities.

- To what extent are postgraduate learners of SI aware of Arabic diglossia?

The interview findings show that the participants were aware of the key differences between MSA and DA but unaware of diglossia as a linguistic phenomenon. All the participants said they have no understanding of diglossia.

In other words, they perceived this duality of language as a standard with dialects. They were unconscious of the main reasons that made SI extremely difficult. I also noticed that the participants were using 'Arabic' as an umbrella term to talk about both MSA and DA in many answers without a clear distinction. I could only understand the distinction between the two forms through the context in which the interview questions were asked. While some oppose into-B interpreting, claiming that it affects the interpreting quality and only advocate interpreting into the 'A' language, SI students in Algeria are required to interpret in both directions from and into two languages that neither is their L1. It is a major concern that the students are unaware of the challenges resulted from not using their L1 in SI. This is a significant finding, as it relates to identity and indeed status as discussed earlier in the literature review.

- To what extent would a proposed ESA, as a mixture between Literary and Colloquial Arabic, help reduce the impact of diglossia in the field of teaching SI?

All the participants agreed that ESA should not replace MSA. Among the main reasons is the possibility of creating confusion since there exist already numerous varieties in the Arabic language, unless ESA is used as a helping tool instead of replacing MSA. Furthermore, the participants suggested improving the MSA level in the Arabic speaking world rather than resorting to another form of language. Two possible explanations of this choice could be suggested. The participants' answers showed a strong bond between MSA and their identity, that is to say, they consider MSA as a sacred form of language that should not be corrupted. Alternatively, students should work on improving their MSA level. The second possible explanation is that in Algeria, there are already numerous spoken dialects; some of them might be unintelligible to even residents of the neighbouring cities. Consequently, improving MSA level in education and in SI is a better solution as the language situation in Algeria is already complex. Suggesting another form of Arabic (ESA) may serve oral communication but in writing, MSA would still be needed.

- What is the students' experience of the SI classes:
 - Impact of their perceived level of English on their performance in SI classes?
 - What did the students consider to be positive about the class?
 - What recommendations would the students make for improvement?

As mentioned earlier, both the questionnaire and the interview data showed that the students' level of English had an impact on their SI performance. They think that SI requires a higher level of English than the level they had. Moreover, the majority of the participants believed that insufficient time was devoted to the SI module and the equipment as well as the methods of teaching were poor. New SI teaching methods that meet the students' needs should be introduced. In this light, Kelly (2014) notes:

For a long time in the history of translator training trainers have assumed that students or apprentices learn to translate simply by translating. As professional translators with little time to devote to reflection on how to organize teaching and learning, many early trainers limited class activity to asking for on-sight (oral) translation of journalistic and literary texts, with little or no prior preparation on the part of the students, and to offering their own "correct" version as a model after public confirmation that the students' versions lacked professional quality. This approach to training was essentially a pedagogical, and of course extremely frustrating for students (p. 11).

In my interviews, the participants' suggestions for improvement fall under two main broad areas: the first one is concerned with teaching English as a foreign language whereas the other one focuses on strengthening one's vocabulary and skills through reading, as explained below.

- Institutional suggestions: the participants argue that it is necessary to replace the outdated teaching methods of SI by new methods. Furthermore, they highlighted the need of more practice in teaching English as a foreign language in order to prepare the students for SI.
- Personal suggestions: since practice plays an important role in improving the four skills, the participants claimed that personal effort should be made outside the classroom through watching TV channels and reading in order to improve their English level and therefore strengthen their vocabulary, which accordingly contributes to facilitating interpreting from and into a foreign language.

I would like to highlight two key findings, which I was not expecting from the research: the first one was that the participants' own level of English affected their interpreting performance; and the second related issue is their level of MSA, and this leads to extra challenges when it comes to SI. In other words, they face a double challenge when it comes to SI because they are not interpreting into MSA, their perceived L1.

6.3. Limitations of the Study

It is to be noted that the present research fulfilled what it aimed for but there are some limitations that should be highlighted.

I should stress that my study has been primarily concerned with teaching SI as a module as part of an MA degree in Translation and Translation Studies at the University of Ouargla and not as a separate SI course. Thus, the findings of my study might be limited to the pedagogy of SI as a module. I thought of collecting my data at an institute of translation in Algeria where SI is taught. However, my study focuses on language practice in SI from Arabic into English and vice versa, and Arabic diglossia is still present whether SI is taught as a module or as a separate course. Furthermore, since the study aims to explore SI students' attitudes towards interpreting from and into MSA, the focus is on SI students' perceptions on MSA use in SI classes regardless of whether SI is a separate course or a module.

Several suggestions were proposed for data collection but they did not seem to work because of a few issues. One of these that was the failure to get the permission from the teachers at the University of Ouargla to collect the data from the current students of SI. One hypothesis is they might be worried that the students would criticise the course. My alternative was to select graduates of SI who graduated from university.

One of the limitations of the sample choice is that the participants of my study were my former fellow students. This could have resulted in a lack of anonymity. However, data collected during this study was solely accessed by myself and by my supervisory team. It was stored on a password protected USB. The findings of this study will be used for research purposes only, neither the participants' names nor their personal information will be identified and their anonymity was respected throughout the process. Confidentiality and anonymity were assured and carried out.

Another limitation of the project relates to validity, the fact that the participants were not current students of SI may have affected their ability to recall their SI experience vividly. As

a solution, I carefully chose the wording of my interview questions, for example Q11: do you think the task of SI would be easier if you were interpreting from and into DA instead of MSA? Imagine using DA in class instead of MSA, would it be easier? (See appendix E).

However, this could be regarded as an advantage as the participants were open about sharing their experiences without being afraid of being judgmental or critical of their teachers as they would if they were current students. Moreover, as a researcher, having prior familiarity with the participants and a mutual learning experience made them feel understood and therefore they were more comfortable to share their ideas.

In this respect, Dwyer and Buckle (2009) highlight that what is more important in a researcher role is not an insider or an outsider, rather authenticity; honesty; openness; interest and accuracy in representing the participants' experiences. Furthermore, they assert that being an insider provides easy access to the participants that might be difficult if the researcher is an outsider. Furthermore, considering the fact that the researcher is part of the same population as the participants allows them to be more open assuming that there is a high level of understanding of their mutual experiences (Dwyer and Buckle, 2009) and that is how I felt when I was interviewing my former colleagues. In this light, "shared experience may act as a catalyst that helps to generate new avenues of inquiry by opening up and extending the depth of a discussion" (McEvoy, 2001, p.52).

Among the ethical considerations that one should take into account when interviewing colleagues is that this kind of relationship the researcher has with his/her fellows may make them feel they are implicitly obliged to take part in the research and therefore have to make this decision (McEvoy, 2001). As a result, McEvoy (2001) continues to explain "this could infringe my ethical duty to respect their autonomy" (p.55). In order to reduce the impact of the participation in research on the researcher/participant relationship, the participants were clearly informed from the beginning (in the participant information sheet) that their participation in the research is completely voluntary and any decision not to take part will not affect the researcher/participant relationship in any way. Therefore, in this research, interviewing former colleagues is regarded as an advantage rather than a drawback.

Additionally, I was extremely aware of my positionality with regard to my participants and consequently tried to avoid any possibility of potential bias by the way I framed the questions and doing it remotely, in which that distance was helpful. In this light, researchers claim "Skype

allows people not to look at someone in the eye during an interview, might actually be an advantage in helping shy people to open up” (Lo Iacono, Symonds and Brown, 2016, p.12).

Among the various advantages of online interviewing, time and location of the interview are not problematic, as there is flexibility of agreement concerning when and where the interview is going to be conducted (Cohen, Manion, and Morrison, 2018). In addition to that, in situations where the participants are hard to reach due to either geographical restrictions or availability purposes, remote interviewing helps minimising travel expenses and time consumption (King, Horrocks, and Brooks, 2018). Hewson (2007) comments on these advantages by stating that they facilitate participation “from, and interaction amongst, respondents across different geographical regions and time zones” (p.413). All these criteria are present in my study. Thus, Skype interviews were the most convenient. Nevertheless, Skype interviews also had other advantages that I benefited from.

It must be noted though that there are shortcomings of online interviews. I had hoped to conduct face-to-face interviews with my participants but it was not possible as they live in Algeria in different parts of the country. As a result, the data collection had to take part online. Furthermore, there were some issues in terms of internet disruption; also, the time difference between the UK and Algeria when the interviews were conducted made it harder to arrange the interviews. As a solution, despite the time differences between the two countries and the busy schedules of both the interviewees and I, we did agree on a time that suits both of us. Giving them the freedom to choose the time and date that suited them best made it a lot easier to commit to it.

I did not face any difficulties when I was collecting quantitative data as the respondents were pleased to participate but there were some issues around qualitative data collection. A large number of the questionnaire respondents showed willingness to take part in the Skype interviews, however, when I contacted them to get their consent and arrange the interview, only a few were still interested. The participants were going to be selected from the respondents who expressed their willingness to participate in the interviews, through providing their details at the end of the questionnaire as requested. From these, five participants were to be invited to the interview depending on their answers to two questions in the questionnaire. The first regarding their L1 and current job; the second, question 9, ‘Please select among the following options the one you found most challenging in your SI classes: your level of English language, your level of MSA, classroom use of MSA and not dialectal Arabic’. However, as mentioned

above, not all the respondents who showed willingness to participate in the interview were still interested. Therefore, I only interviewed the ones who were willing to take part. This fortunately had not a major effect on the data I got as it was still varied and provided different perspectives and insights into the topic under investigation.

Another limitation concerns the methodology; the sample size was relatively small. Consequently, the results cannot be over-generalised and they need to be used with care. A mixed methods approach was chosen in this research since the study focuses on exploring how Arabic diglossia affects the SI students' perceptions on the pedagogy of SI in Algeria, which entails the need for in-depth data regarding individual perceptions.

The qualitative researcher will need fewer participants when each interview provides a large amount of useful data (Morse, 2000). That is why I opted for longer interviews with in-depth analysis.

Denscombe (2014, p.56) claims that case study approach provides rich data by enabling the researcher to “delve deep into the intricacies of the situation”. It is more convenient to opt for a mixed methods approach in this research since its focus is to investigate how Arabic diglossia affects my participants' perceptions of the pedagogy of SI in Algeria, which entails the need for in-depth data, as a researcher I have no control over the behavioural events and finally the study explores a contemporary phenomenon. Furthermore, “the use of interviews in small-scale research tends to involve the use of semi-structured interviews to investigate attitudes and issues in detail, and is generally used as part of qualitative research” (Denscombe, 2014, p.182).

6.4. Reflection on the Process of the Research

A comparative study between two universities in Algeria where SI is taught would also have answered my research questions effectively. However, this was not possible because of several reasons, among which were time and difficulties to get the permission to interview current students.

In addition to that, interviewing not only SI students but teachers as well might have explored the topic under investigation more deeply and provided richer data. Investigating teachers' perceptions and attitudes towards the impact of Arabic diglossia on the pedagogy of SI would have been interesting. This is an area for future study. See below.

6.5. Autobiographical Reflection

Undertaking this research overseas has been an invaluable opportunity that had an impact on many aspects of my life, not only improved my academic skills but also contributed to my personal growth. The skills that I learnt such as autonomy, critical thinking, perseverance and resilience made me who I am today. I acknowledge that I am privileged to have learned from the challenges I encountered throughout my journey, which helped me develop as a researcher. Reflecting on my own experience and on how my project evolved, made me realise how far I have come. However, I had to deal with extra challenges of completing my PhD during the pandemic, which reshaped my university life. Among the challenges I faced was not being able to visit my family back home during 2020 because of the lockdown, consequently I had no annual leave that year.

I was on my own for a long period of time in the hall of residence, which affected my mental health during this outbreak. I also did not have the chance to develop my oral English skills because of the decreased social interactions due to physical distancing measures. Furthermore, I was concerned about my academic performance and unable to have on-campus meetings with my supervisors and had no library access. It has been a difficult time, however, having overcome this critical situation taught me resilience as I learned positive coping mechanisms and gave me a better understanding of the UK culture and what it is like to be a PhD student in a foreign country.

The support that the staff at the University of the West of Scotland provides to their international students made the journey much easier. I am grateful for this whole learning experience as it improved my oral skills through communication and interactions with other students from all over the world. Living in a flat in a hall of residence with fellow postgraduate students was a very positive experience because it encouraged us to speak English, which significantly contributed to the development of my oral skills, and thus my writing skills.

Furthermore, I learnt how to embrace diversity and recognised that we perceive the world differently. The more I learnt, the more I understood how to think outside the box and realised that there is no absolute truth.

I have always been afraid of public speaking but this fear was conquered when I had to present my work at the transfer event in front of an expert panel, dozens of academics and fellow PhD students, which was critical but helpful. This experience boosted my self-confidence and

helped me step out of my comfort zone. I was also very fortunate to be given support by my fellow students with whom I had a shared understanding of the difficulties of the PhD journey, as well as my supervisory team whose guidance and constant encouragement made a huge difference.

I also learnt a lot from looking at the lived experiences of my participants and perceived the topic under investigation from different angles. It was also a great opportunity to catch up with my previous colleagues with whom I had not previously the chance to discuss their learning experiences.

6.6. The potential Impact of my Research and Recommendations to Universities in Algeria/the Government/the Wider Society

6.6.1. Recommendations to the Government

Students in Algeria are not given the chance to give their feedback on the teaching methods of SI. In this respect, my study offers suggestive evidence, for the specific course and programme of study, for proposing an evaluation system to include the students' comments and feedback in order to improve the pedagogy of SI. If the pedagogy of SI improves then the practice of SI may improve.

6.6.2. Recommendations to the University Language Education Departments

The students should be made more aware of the diglossic nature of the Arabic language in order to improve their MSA level and understand the difficulties they encounter when they interpret simultaneously from and into MSA. The transition phase, that is, between learning English and developing interpreting skills, is of a significant importance as the present study's findings show that the participants did not feel confident about their competence in both languages.

In this light, mother tongue instruction could not be a possible solution as Algeria is a multilingual society as evidenced by the use of Berber, DA, MSA and French in everyday interactions. That is to say, the inhabitants of Algeria have various spoken vernaculars that have many borrowed words from foreign languages, mainly French, and are lexicalised and given the features of the spoken dialects such as pronunciation and grammar. Therefore, when interpreting into DA, the students may lack the necessary vocabulary only available in MSA.

6.6.3. Recommendations to Language Schools

Although English language instruction precedes the MA degree, all participants felt that the instruction of English was not of sufficient quality to prepare the students for the SI module; therefore, policy makers and educationists might consider incorporating English language instruction in interpreting and translation courses.

Another suggestion is that the quality of the learning of English should be reviewed. However, the participants' view of their English language level was not the only issue, as according to their answers, they are also not wholly confident in their MSA. In other words, their DA could not be used in formal contexts such as education because it lacks proper grammar, vocabulary etc., and their MSA level was not good enough to fulfil SI tasks. Yet, they rejected replacing MSA by ESA in education. Therefore, a better quality language instruction in both MSA and English offered in the course is of great importance in order to improve the students' MSA and English levels.

Among the hardships and constraints SI participants were facing was their lack of competence in MSA. Although the participants perceive MSA as their L1 and in the questionnaire 17 out of the 21 participants claimed that they had excellent or good knowledge of MSA, in the interviews, my five participants outlined, in a deeper exploration of the issues, that they had some difficulties in the mastery of MSA. One of the key findings of this PhD was that the participants in this study were finding the SI practise harder and more constraining because of their lack of MSA competence. This led to particular difficulties when interpreting (speaking skill) in comparison to translating (writing skill) due to a number of factors: time pressures; the high demand of successful spoken linguistic communication; the necessity to handle the speaker's articulation; the possibility of technical flaws; and no chance for corrections to be made once the interpretation is delivered (Riccardi, 2002). However, there is an assumption that students of SI are fully competent in MSA, since everybody in Algeria studies it for at least twelve years before reaching the higher education level, as Arabic is the official language of Algeria.

In addition, this teaching approach does not reflect the fact that the Arabic language is considered diglossic; it is often taken for granted that being a citizen in an Arabic speaking country, one is able to translate from and into Arabic (i.e. MSA) (Masoud, 1988, as cited in Deeb, 2005, pp.1-2).

As a result of this assumption, students are not required to pass a language test to assess their command of MSA; in other words, they are accepted at university to study translation and interpreting based on other criteria, such as the overall score that the university demands, but not an MSA proficiency evaluation. Nevertheless, a very high level of competence in MSA is required to be successful in SI at the Master's level; the participants suggested that they had not actually reached this level despite responding in the questionnaire that they felt they had a good level of oral and written MSA. In other words, they did not have the good command of MSA that enables them to use it spontaneously when interpreting simultaneously as they would use DA. They had not reached the level that SI requires. The participants revealed that despite the use of DA in SI class, which can give them the impression that they can interpret easily, their MSA level, was not as strong as it should be.

It is important to highlight that the everyday use of languages is complex and not straightforward. This linguistic crossing tends to be non-linear, unconscious and therefore can be a challenge to explore. This is instinctive to the speaker and therefore becomes a challenge when the speaker is using MSA specifically.

Thus, in the field of SI, the classifications of the languages involved in interpreting are crucial, as discussed in section 3.24. on page 79. In this respect, according to the literature, MSA is not the first language of Arabic speakers (Cote, 2009; Dendane, 2010) yet all the participants of this study claimed that their L1 is MSA and not one of the spoken varieties. However, two participants out of five explained that they do use ESA unconsciously when they interact with other Arabic speakers who find it difficult to understand the Algerian DA. Furthermore, all the participants stated that they have not heard of diglossia as a linguistic phenomenon and they therefore perceive this duality of use of language as a standard with dialects. This explains, as stated above, that the use of language is complex and non-linear.

6.7. Contribution to Theory and Knowledge in the Field of SI

Although it may not be possible to generalise the findings, as this small-scale study may not be generalizable, as these findings relate specifically to the 2016 cohort of students on the Masters' degree of Translation and Translation Studies. There is scope for further research as in all Arabic speaking countries the L1 is one of the spoken dialects and not the MSA form.

Accordingly, another area of research that is worth further exploring is to check whether the findings of this study are relevant in other Arabic speaking countries. However, I believe that

the sample within this study has provided some new insights into the specific context of SI and the challenges of DA, MSA and ESA as well as a profound understanding of the area under investigation in one specific context through the use of in-depth interviews.

Moreover, the findings have importance because they inform the pedagogy of SI through an exploration of the SI students' perceptions when interpreting from and into a diglossic language; however, this whole area requires further study.

6.8. Future Research Areas

Although research on Arabic diglossia has intensified over the past decade, more research should be conducted in this area. One avenue for further study would be research into how to reduce the impact of Arabic diglossia on the pedagogy of SI. As mentioned earlier, interviewing SI teachers could help explore the area under investigation from a different angle and lead to comparative data, comparing teachers and learners' perspectives. In other words, since the pedagogy of SI entails both teaching and learning, it would be also important to explore SI teachers' perceptions of using MSA in SI classes in the Arabic speaking countries. Another suggestion for future research could be research into the perceptions and attitudes of interpreters and students of interpreting on directionality and how does it affect their performance, which is an area that should be investigated further incorporating diglossic languages.

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Appendices

Appendix A: Participant Consent Form

Consent form

Name of department: School of Education, University of the West of Scotland (UWS)

Title of the research project: The Potential Impact of Arabic Diglossia on the Pedagogy of Simultaneous Interpreting in Algeria.

- I confirm that I have read and understood the information sheet for the above study and the researcher has answered any questions to my satisfaction.
- I understand that taking part is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw from the study at any time, without having to give a reason and without any consequences.
- I understand that I can withdraw my data from the study.
- I understand that any information recorded during the study will remain confidential and no information that can identify me will be made public.

(PRINT NAME)	Hereby agree to take part in the above study
Signature of Participant:	Date:

Appendix B: Questionnaire Participant Information Sheet

School of Education

University of the West of Scotland

February 2019

Participant Information Sheet

Title of the study: The Potential Implications of Arabic Diglossia on the Pedagogy of Simultaneous Interpreting in Algeria.

My name is Sally Othmane. I am conducting a study as part of my Ph.D. programme at University of the West of Scotland. I would now formally like to invite you to take part in my research study, but before making your decision, please take time to read this information sheet. If you have any questions, please do not hesitate to contact me via e-mail, which is as follows:

E-mail address: [REDACTED]

What is the study about?

The main objective of this study is to explore the potential implications of Arabic diglossia on the pedagogy of simultaneous interpreting in Algeria.

Diglossia as a linguistic phenomenon refers to cases where two linguistic varieties of the same language exist alongside referred to as high variety and low variety. The (H) variety refers to the high variety utilized in formal contexts such as education whereas the (L) variety refers to the low variety that is employed in daily interactions within the context of family and friends (Ferguson, 1959). In the Algerian context, shedding light on the Arabic language, H variety is the Modern Standard Arabic and the L variety is the spoken variety of Arabic.

The study intends to:

1. Explore students' attitudes towards Arabic diglossia;

2. Identify the difficulties that the students of SI are subjected to when asked to interpret simultaneously from and into Modern Standard Arabic although this variety of language is not used in daily life communications.

Why have you been invited to take part in this study?

The participant selection is based upon a variety of criteria mainly:

- Algerian students who graduated with an MA degree from University of Ouargla in 2016;
- Studied simultaneous interpreting as an MA module for two years throughout the MA course; and
- Graduated three years ago, therefore presumably can recall their experience as students of simultaneous interpreting.

Do you have to take part?

For those interested in taking part in the research, you should know that your participation in this research is totally voluntary. However, the participants won't be able to withdraw their data after they submit their response due to the fact that it won't be possible to identify their data, because all responses will be anonymous. By completing this questionnaire, you consent for you data to be used in this study.

It is important to mention that our relationship as colleagues will not be affected in any way if you are unable to participate or decide to withdraw for any reason at any stage. However, I hope that you will consent to take part in this project.

What will you do?

If you accept to participate in this study:

1. You will then be asked to complete a short online questionnaire and
2. You may be invited to take part in a Skype interview.

Will your participation be confidential?

Data collected during this study will be solely accessed by myself and my supervisory team. The findings of this study will be used for research purposes only, neither your name nor your personal information will be identified and your anonymity will be respected throughout the process. Confidentiality, and anonymity are assured.

Who has approved the research?

The proposal was reviewed by the Ethics Committee of the School of Education, University of the West of Scotland.

What will happen next?

I would be very much delighted if you express your willingness to take part in this research. Yet, if you cannot, then I would like to thank you for taking the time to read this document.

After submitting the thesis to the university, it will be available online. If you are interested in accessing a copy, please let me know and I will send you the link.

N.B. Thank you for reading this information, if you wish to discuss any aspects of the study or this document then please do not hesitate to contact me via the aforementioned contact details.

Thank you.

Appendix D: Interview Participant Information Sheet

School of Education

University of the West of Scotland

February 2019

Participant Information Sheet

Title of the study: The Potential Implications of Arabic Diglossia on the Pedagogy of Simultaneous Interpreting in Algeria.

My name is Sally Othmane. I am conducting a study as part of my Ph.D. programme at University of the West of Scotland. I would now formally like to invite you to take part in my research study, but before making your decision, please take time to read this information sheet. If you have any questions, please do not hesitate to contact me via e-mail, which is as follows:

E-mail address: [REDACTED]

What is the study about?

The main objective of this study is to explore the potential implications of Arabic diglossia on the pedagogy of simultaneous interpreting in Algeria.

Diglossia as a linguistic phenomenon refers to cases where two linguistic varieties of the same language exist alongside referred to as high variety and low variety. The (H) variety refers to the high variety utilized in formal contexts such as education whereas the (L) variety refers to the low variety that is employed in daily interactions within the context of family and friends (Ferguson, 1959). In the Algerian context, shedding light on the Arabic language, H variety is the Modern Standard Arabic and the L variety is the spoken variety of Arabic.

The study intends to:

3. Explore students' attitudes towards Arabic diglossia;

4. Identify the difficulties that the students of SI are subjected to when asked to interpret simultaneously from and into Modern Standard Arabic although this variety of language is not used in daily life communications.

Why have you been invited to take part in this study?

The participant selection is based upon a variety of criteria mainly:

- Algerian students who graduated with an MA degree from University of Ouargla in 2016;
- Studied simultaneous interpreting as an MA module for two years throughout the MA course; and
- Graduated three years ago, therefore presumably can recall their experience as students of simultaneous interpreting.

Do you have to take part?

For those interested in taking part in the research, you should know that your participation in this research is totally voluntary. However, I will need your written approval. Thus, a consent form will be sent to you shortly via Facebook, to approve that you agree to participate in the study. Note that you can withdraw at any time and without giving any reasons, and at any stage of the process.

It is important to mention that our relationship as colleagues will not be affected in any way if you are unable to participate or decided to withdraw for any reason at any stage. However, I hope that you will consent to take part in this project.

If you are willing to be involved in this study, would you please sign and return the consent form by **20/08/2019**.

What will you do?

If you accept to participate in this study, you will be invited to take part in a Skype interview.

The interview questions will be open-ended and it is to be noted that they will be recorded after expressing your approval, but note that the recordings will be used for research purposes only and will be stored in a password protected USB. The interview will last for approximately 30 minutes and will take place in April, and the date and time will be scheduled according to your availability.

Will your participation be confidential?

Data collected during this study will be solely accessed by myself and my supervisory team. The findings of this study will be used for research purposes only; neither your name nor your personal information will be identified and your anonymity will be respected throughout the process. Confidentiality, and anonymity are assured.

Who has approved the research?

The proposal has been reviewed by the Ethics Committee of the School of Education, University of the West of Scotland.

What will happen if I do not carry on with the study?

In case you withdraw from the study, all the data collected from you will be deleted.

What will happen next?

I would be delighted if you express your willingness to take part in this research. Yet, if you cannot, then I would like to thank you for taking the time to read this document.

After submitting the thesis to the university, it will be available online. If you are interested in accessing a copy, please let me know and I will send you the link.

N.B. Thank you for reading this information, if you wish to discuss any aspects of the study or this document then please do not hesitate to contact me via the aforementioned contact details.

Thank you.

Appendix D: Questionnaire

Find it online:

https://www.surveymonkey.co.uk/r/GLWJTSN?fbclid=IwAR2ntv9cv7Ez7luJXm0gQEGdCo8-fPUbvP7rYNBV5gR4YVSu_DRo9kR9-SA

Dear colleague,

You are kindly invited to complete this survey, which explores the attitudes and insights of simultaneous interpreting students towards their experience in studying this module. This study aims to explore students' attitudes towards Arabic diglossia and to identify the difficulties that the students of SI are subjected to when asked to interpret simultaneously from and into Modern Standard Arabic although this variety of language is not used in daily life communications.

Please note that this survey will take around five minutes to complete. I understand the aims of the research. The participants will not be able to withdraw their data after they submit their response due to the fact that it won't be possible to identify their data, because all responses will be anonymous. By completing this questionnaire, I consent for my data to be used in this study.

Respondent's details:

What is your first language?

What is your current job title?

.....

Please complete the following by placing a tick in one space only.

- 1) Overall, in your opinion, how effective were the teaching methods of simultaneous interpreting within your major at your university?

Extremely effective Effective Satisfactory Somewhat ineffective
Ineffective

- 2) In your opinion, how helpful were the classroom assignments to your interpreting skill development?

Extremely helpful Helpful Satisfactory Somewhat unhelpful Not helpful at all

3) How would you rate quality of SI teaching materials?

Excellent Good Satisfactory Poor Very poor

4) How would you rate the facilities in your university to develop your SI skills (EG labs, teaching materials,)

Excellent Good Satisfactory Poor Very poor

5) How would you rate your Modern Standard Arabic oral language proficiency?

Excellent Good Satisfactory Poor Very poor

6) How would you rate your Modern Standard Arabic writing language proficiency?

Excellent Good Satisfactory Poor Very poor

7) Please select among the following options the one you found most challenging in your SI classes

Your level of English language

Your level of MSA

Classroom use of MSA and not dialectal Arabic

- Can you explain your choice in just a few words?

.....
.....

N.B. As part of my research, I am also conducting Skype interviews, if you are interested in being interviewed, would you please leave your contact details below and I will get in touch with you shortly.

Contact details: (email, Skype username)

.....

Thank you for taking the time to complete this survey. I appreciate your valuable cooperation.

Yours sincerely.

Appendix E: Interview

Interview Protocol and Interview Questions

The Potential Impact of Arabic Diglossia on the Pedagogy of Simultaneous Interpreting in Algeria

Introduction: topic of the interview, ethics, informed consent

We are now recording. First, I would like to thank you for agreeing to take part in this interview. You were selected voluntarily based on previously administered online survey responses. This interview will take approximately 30 minutes to maximum one hour and you have the right to stop at any time without giving reasons. The purpose of this interview is to investigate the potential impact of diglossia on the pedagogy of SI. I am interested in hearing your personal experiences and perceptions towards the topic under investigation. Please take into account that there are no right or wrong answers, thus I would like you to feel comfortable during this conversation, if you do not understand any question, please do not hesitate to ask for further clarifications. Remember that the information you provide will remain confidential and will be used only for research purposes. Prior to the interview, you were sent an informal message; a participation information sheet, in which you found all the details of this project and whom to contact if you have any queries; and a consent form to be signed and returned to me before the interview. If you do not have any further questions, let us begin.

Main body of the interview:

- 1) Have you heard of diglossia?
 - If yes, could you define it? If not ...
 - What is your understanding of diglossia?
 - How did you develop this understanding?
- 2) What for you are the key differences between MSA and spoken dialects?
- 3) Do you think these differences affected your SI classroom practice in any way?
 - Could you give a brief explanation?
- 4) What is your preferred language direction when interpreting simultaneously? From English into MSA or from MSA into English?
 - Why?

- 5) Would you choose MSA to communicate with Arabic speakers from outside the Great Maghreb?
 - Why?/ Why not?
- 6) Would you feel comfortable communicating in MSA in informal settings (with friends and family)
 - Why?/ Why not?
- 7) What is your definition of L1?
- 8) Have you ever considered MSA as a non-L1?
 - Could you explain that?
- 9) What, for you, is the main challenge of SI?
 - What can be done to resolve this challenge?
 - Among the challenges embodied in SI, do you consider the use of MSA one of them?
- 10) Do you consider MSA and DA as two forms belonging to the same language or two separate languages?
 - Why?
- 11) Do you think the task of SI would be easier if interpreting from and into dialectal Arabic instead of MSA?
 - Why?
- 12) If you are working as a teacher, do you use dialectal Arabic to explain the lesson?
 - Why? / Why not?
- 13) From your personal experience, do you think that Arabic diglossia has an impact on the teaching methods of SI?
- 14) Educated Spoken Arabic is a form of language that is neither purely standard nor purely colloquial; what are your thoughts on replacing MSA in education by ESA?
- 15) In your opinion, what impact did your level of English have on your performance in SI classes?
- 16) Could you highlight any areas where the course was particularly helpful?
- 17) What recommendations do you have for improving the SI module?

- Extra:

In what ways could you improve as an interpreter?

End of the interview: thanks, additional points and queries

This is the end of the interview; I would like to thank you for your valuable time and attention.

If you do have any comments that you wish to add, please do not hesitate.

Appendix F: Coding Categories

Thematic analysis

Theme	Sub-theme	Quotes
Learning about diglossia in SI	Unawareness of diglossia	<p>IP1: <i>“I haven’t heard about it before”.</i></p> <p>IP2: <i>“No, I’ve never heard of it”.</i></p> <p>IP3: <i>“I think no, no. I didn’t hear about this”.</i></p> <p>IP4: <i>“It means to take two languages, to translate between or interpret between two languages, the source language and the target language”.</i></p> <p>IP5: <i>“I’ve heard about it just from this research. It means two languages I mean in one language”.</i></p>

Theme	Sub-theme	Quotes
Interpreting from and into MSA	From MSA into English due to the lack of English vocabulary	IP1: <i>“because emm I do not have, I feel always that I do not have enough vocab in the English language”.</i>
	From English into MSA because their MSA vocabulary is richer	IP2: <i>“from English to standard Arabic. It is better I think. From Arabic to English I find it somehow”.</i>

difficult especially when I want to translate into English I have to take into consideration the grammar or sometimes the punctuation and so on, so it is somehow difficult but from English to Arabic I find myself good”.

IP3: “emm I prefer, because I do that all the time, I translate from English into Arabic especially when I teach”.

IP4: “I choose to start from English into Arabic better than from Arabic into English. It’s a matter of vocabulary”.

IP5: “from English into Arabic because it is let’s say easier to find vocabulary in my mind because I’m used to using Arabic more than maybe to use English because Arabic is my native language but English is my second language that’s why I most of the time prefer to let’s say translate from English into standard Arabic

		<p><i>because I don't consume or take so much time to search for the vocabulary or let's say putting the correct grammar and the correct structure to deliver the message whereas if I'm translating from Arabic into English I find it harder because I find some challenges in selecting the right and the correct and the exact vocabulary and structure of the English language".</i></p>
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Theme	Sub-theme	Quotes
Awareness of Arabic diglossia	MSA and DA are two separate languages	<p>IP1: <i>"Emm, well for me I think that the Arabic that we use in our daily life is completely different from the standard Arabic because of many reasons. For example, here in my region we have words in our daily life which are not really Arabic words, emm like we have kind of I don't know if we can call it a language which is 'Chelha', yes they are not words from the Arabic language, emm</i></p>

also words from the French. Yes that's why we find sometimes some expressions that do not have any kind of relation with the Arabic language”.

IP2: “for me they are different languages. In some cases, we consider the Arabic of the standard Arabic language and the colloquial language as different languages. We cannot say they are the same language. Because in colloquial language we use some words that we bring from for example foreign languages like French, like English words, we use them in our daily life. But in some cases we use some words in colloquial language which are originally from the standard Arabic like for example العرصة الزردة ‘feast’. Here we can consider it as one language but for some words like يزاف ‘so much’ here we consider them as different languages”.

		<p>IP5: <i>“I consider them separated, too much separated (...).They are very separate, the standard Arabic and let’s say local Arabic because if they were very close. We could say that every single Arabic speaker can understand the Algerian and the Moroccan local Arabics, but they are different because local is based mostly on only the oral side but the standard very organised, very unique and very well formed”.</i></p>
	<p>MSA and DA are one language</p>	<p>IP3: <i>“They are one, they belong to one language but for the colloquial it’s .. some used words are, they don’t belong to MSA. They belong merely to the same language but you find some, let’s say borrowed words or adapted words in the colloquial”.</i></p> <p>IP4: <i>“they are the same but we can just describe them as, the colloquial Arabic is a mixture of many languages in comparison to the pure MSA”.</i></p>

Theme	Sub-theme	Quotes
<p>Possibility of reducing the impact of diglossia in SI</p>	<p>ESA cannot replace MSA</p>	<p>IP1: <i>“Emm I think in this way we are going to, to make the problem extend. We would rather try for example use the standard Arabic in our daily life rather than creating a new language which is called, which you called Middle Arabic”.</i></p> <p>IP2: <i>“Yes, it’s possible. But it will make confusion. Because we use in our daily life colloquial language, then we read for example the Quran in the standard Arabic then they will ask us to use middle language, I think it will make a lot of complications”.</i></p> <p>IP3: <i>“I think we shouldn’t replace it completely, but rather we should use it for helping the students understand more, but we keep MSA and we use this ESA, right? Just to help the students understand MSA, but keep MSA and use ESA as a kind of help”.</i></p>

		<p>IP4: <i>“No not at all, no. it doesn’t work at all. The standard Arabic remains the best one when compared to the Middle Arabic”.</i></p> <p>IP5: <i>“No, no no I’m totally against this because I know that the world needs an easier way to communicate and to understand each other but I’m total against this replacement. Because students and teachers are the ones who should upgrade their level and challenge themselves to use the standard Arabic but not the middle Arabic as you said. So if we put it as an assistant language or as a helping language yes I’m for because as I said before as a student of translation I should take all the forms and all the categories of the Arabic language. Because we can as graduates or beginners let’s say beginners translators may need any type of these categories whether it is the middle or the colloquial or</i></p>
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		<p><i>the standard Arabic. As a helping yes but to replace it I'm totally against and that will damage the Arabic language level and will damage the Arabic language so I can't go with this replacement. It is a good thing to use this type of language but as I mentioned as a helping tool or as a helping method, a helping language, a helping category but not as a replacement because it will damage our language when we replace it totally".</i></p>
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Theme	Sub-theme	Quotes
Experience of the SI classes	Poor equipment and methods	<p>IP2: <i>"for me I think it was not helpful, because we need practice, we need materials, this module needs materials, needs a lot of practice not just theories, not just two or three videos. I think we interpreted just four or five videos in two years. I think it had no advantages in fact".</i></p> <p>IP3: <i>"I didn't find it helpful, I didn't find it helpful because we weren't studying as it</i></p>

	<p>Insufficient time devoted to SI module</p>	<p><i>should be I mean we were not using the right equipment, the right methods because the equipment and methods were poor, very poor, it was very normal and the help was poor, poor, let's say poor".</i></p> <p>IP4: <i>"No, it was clear that it wasn't enough to help us, so SI isn't an easy task by the way, so to learn it and study it for just one semester or one year it's not enough. No, it wasn't helpful at all, we didn't have any equipment".</i></p>
	<p>The module was very helpful</p>	<p>IP5: <i>"the module of SI is very, very, very interesting and very useful (...). That module first always made me updated about what is happening in the world because in every session new news, new articles, new political speeches, or personal etc. So it made updated to the news, it made me updated to culture (...). And I here ask the</i></p>

		<i>universities of Algeria to develop more this module and to make a labs and some software, advanced software, developing this module to help students get their confidence and prepare them well to be interpreters”.</i>
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